

15th World Conference

on Thermophotovoltaic Generation of Electricity

UHTES

SECOND INTERNATIONAL WORKSHOP
ULTRA-HIGH TEMPERATURE THERMAL ENERGY STORAGE,
TRANSFER AND CONVERSION

Book of Abstracts

1 - 3 October 2024 / Madrid - Spain

15th World Conference

on Thermophotovoltaic Generation of Electricity

Book of abstracts

15th World Conference on Thermophotovoltaic Generation of Electricity

Organized alongside the

2nd International Workshop on Ultra High Temperature Thermal Energy
Storage, Transfer and Conversion

1-3 October 2024, Madrid (Spain)

This volume contains abstracts submitted to and presented at the TPV-15 Conference.

Only abstracts for which authors provided explicit consent during the submission process are included in this booklet. In accordance with the authors' authorization, these abstracts will be made publicly available in an online repository no earlier than six months after the conclusion of the conference.

Conference name: 15th World Conference on Thermophotovoltaic Generation of Electricity

Conference Date: 1-3 October 2024, Madrid (Spain)

Organized by: Instituto de Energía Solar – Universidad Politécnica de Madrid

Sponsors and Collaborator:

Golden Sponsors: Antora Energy, Rondo Energy

Silver Sponsors: European Energy Research Alliance (EERA), Silbat, Thermophoton

Bronze Sponsors: Vesuvius

Collaborator: Horizon EU Project SUNSON (101083827)

Conference chairs:

Alejandro DATAS

Pablo GARCÍA-LINARES

Esther LÓPEZ

Conference Series Committee:

Peter BERMEL (Purdue University - USA)

Alejandro DATAS (UPM - Spain)

Takuya INOUE (Kyoto University - Japan)

Myles STEINER (NREL - USA)

Bong Jae LEE (KAIST - Korea)

Andrej LENERT (University of Michigan - USA)

Georgia PAPADAKIS (ICFO - Spain)

Makoto SHIMIZU (Tohoku University - Japan)

Eric TERVO (Wisconsin University - USA)

Rodolphe VAILLON (CNRS - France)

TPV-15 Program Committee:

Madhan K. ARULANANDAM (Arizona State University)

Alessandro BELLUCCI (CNR)

Peter CARRINGTON (Lancaster University)

Kehang CUI (Shanghai Jiao Tong University)

Alejandro DATAS (Universidad Politécnica de Madrid)

Sheila EDALATPOUR (University of Maine)

Ryan FRANCE (NREL)

Pablo GARCÍA-LINARES FONTES (Universidad Politécnica de Madrid)

Iván GARCÍA (Universidad Politécnica de Madrid)

Maxime GITEAU (PROMES-CNRS)

Bong Jae LEE (KAIST - Korea)

Andrej LENERT (University of Michigan)

Esther LÓPEZ (Universidad Politécnica de Madrid)

Isidro MARTÍN (Universitat Politècnica de Catalunya)

Elyes NEFZAOU (University Gustave Eiffel)

Georgia PAPADAKIS (ICFO)

Chapuis P-OLIVER (CNRS - INSA Lyon)

Keunhan PARK (University of Utah)

Rodolphe VAILLON (LAAS-CNRS)

Makoto SHIMIZU (Tohoku University)

Raphael St-GELAIS (University of Ottawa)

Eric TERVO (University of Wisconsin-Madison)

Daniele M. TRUCCHI (CNR)

Zhuomin ZHANG (Georgia Institute of Technology)

TPV-15 Local Organizing Committee

Ignacio IZQUIERDO (Thermophoton - Spain)

Nicolas LOUBET (UPM - Spain)

Alvaro Manuel MEDRANO (UPM - Spain)

Daniel MILOVICH (Thermophoton - Spain)

Juan VILLA (UPM - Spain)

Myrto ZENELI (UPM - Spain)

Conference sessions

Instituto de Energía Solar

ETSI Telecomunicación, Building "C"

Avda. Complutense 30, Moncloa - Aravaca, 28040 Madrid

Welcome Reception & Dinner

(September 30, 19:30 - 21:30)

Teatro Real, Pl. de Isabel II, s/n. Centro, 28013 Madrid

Gala Dinner

(October 2, 19:30 - 22:00)

Café de Oriente

Museo del Traje, Av. de Juan de Herrera, 2

Moncloa - Aravaca, 28040 Madrid

	September 30 (TPV-15)	October 1 (TPV-15)	October 2 (TPV-15 & UHTES-2)	October 3 (TPV-15)
8:00			Registration	
8:30				
9:00		Registration	Opening Session 2 (OPS2)	
9:30				
10:00		Opening Session 1 (OPS1)	Coffee Break	
10:30			Oral Session 3 (OS3) <i>Ultra-High Temperature Thermal Batteries Developers</i>	Oral Session 5 (OS5) <i>TPV emitters</i>
11:00		Coffee Break		
11:30			Coffee Break	Coffee Break
12:00		Oral Session 1 (OS1) <i>TPV cells</i>	Round Table <i>Ultra-High Temperature Thermal Batteries Developers</i>	Oral Session 6 (OS6) <i>Near Field TPV</i>
12:30				
13:00				
13:30		Lunch	Lunch	Lunch
14:00				
14:30				
15:00		Oral Session 2 (OS2) <i>TPV systems</i>	Oral Session 4 (OS4) <i>Ultra-High Temperature Energy Storage, transfer, and Conversion</i>	Oral Session 7 (OS7) <i>Novel Concepts</i>
15:30				
16:00				
16:30				Coffee Break
17:00		Coffee Break	Coffee Break	
17:30				Closing Session (CS)
18:00		Poster Session 1 (PS1)	Poster Session 2 (PS2)	Farewell Drinks
18:30				
19:00				
19:30				
20:00	Welcome reception & Dinner		Gala Dinner	
20:30				
21:00				
21:30				
22:00				

September 30 – Welcome reception and networking dinner

19:30-21:30 Welcome reception and networking dinner
Venue: Teatro Real - Pl. de Isabel II, s/n, Centro, 28013 Madrid

October 1 – TPV-15 Conference (day 1)

Opening Session 1 (OPS1)

10:00-11:00

Chair: Alejandro Datas (UPM)

10:00-10:30 [OPS1.1] Opening remarks

Alejandro Datas (Chair of the TPV-15 Conference, UPM)

Manuel Sierra (Director of Telecommunication School - UPM)

Ignacio Antón (Director of the Solar Energy Institute - UPM)

10:30-11:00 [OPS1.2] Combined Heat and Power via Thermal Energy Storage and Thermophotovoltaics

Brendan Kayes (Invited)

Antora Energy (USA)

11:00-11:30 Coffee break

Oral Session 1 (OS1) - TPV cells

11:30-13:30

Chairs: Eric Tervo (University of Wisconsin-Madison) and Brendan Kayes (Antora Energy)

11:30-12:00 [OS1.1] Air-bridge TPV Cells: Current Performance and Future Possibilities

Andrej Lenert (Invited)

University of Michigan (USA)

12:00-12:15 [OS1.2] Fundamental Advantages of Multijunction Thermophotovoltaic Cells

Richard R. King

Arizona State University

12:15-12:30 [OS1.3] High TPV performance n/p and p/n InGaAs cells

I. García, A. Cano, P. Martín, V. Orejuela, I. Rey-Stolle

Universidad Politécnica de Madrid (Spain)

12:30-12:45 [OS1.4] Experimental Efficiency of 11.2 % in Germanium Thermophotovoltaic Devices

A. M. Medrano¹, E. López¹, Pablo García-Linares¹, J. Villa¹, G. Rivera², M. Gamel², G. López², M. Garín³, I. Martín², C. Cañizo¹, A. Datas¹

¹ Universidad Politécnica de Madrid (Spain), ² Universitat Politècnica de Catalunya (Spain), ³ Universitat Central de Catalunya (Spain)

12:45-13:00 [OS1.5] Electrical and Optical Performance of Epitaxial-free Low-doped Germanium Thermophotovoltaic Devices

M. Gamel¹, G. Rivera¹, A. M. Medrano², J. Villa², G. López¹, P. García-Linares², A. Datas², M. Garín³, I. Martín¹

¹ Universitat Politècnica de Catalunya (Spain), ² Universidad Politécnica de Madrid (Spain), ³ Universitat Central de Catalunya (Spain)

13:00-13:15 [OS1.6] Evaluation of TPV devices in different irradiation environments

N. Das, H. Hier, W. Allmon, S. Karnani, C. M. Waits

Army Research Laboratory (USA)

13:15-13:30 [OS1.7] GeSn Mid-Infrared Thermophotovoltaic Cells Monolithically Integrated on Silicon for Power Beaming and Heat Conversion

G. Daligou¹, R. Soref², P. Del Vecchio¹, A. Attiaoui¹, M. R. M. Atalla¹, O. Moutanabbir¹

¹ Ecole Polytechnique de Montréal (Canada), ² University of Massachusetts Boston (USA)

13:30-15:00 Lunch

Oral Session 2 (OS2) - TPV systems

15:00-17:00

Chairs: Andrej Lenert (University of Michigan) and Walker Chan (Mesodyne)

15:00-15:30 [OS2.1] Narrow Bandgap Intersubband Thermophotovoltaic Cells

Eric Tervo (Invited)

University of Wisconsin-Madison (USA)

15:30-15:45 [OS2.2] Development and experimental characterization of highly packed Ge thermophotovoltaic mini-modules

J. Villa¹, P. García-Linares¹, I. Izquierdo^{1,2}, A. M. Medrano¹, E. López¹, A. Datas¹

¹ Universidad Politécnica de Madrid (Spain), ² Termophoton (Spain)

15:45-16:00 [OS2.3] Experiment assessing the use of GaSb array with filters for waste heat recovery in the cement, steel, and glass Industries

G. Buckley, C. M. I. Hussain, B. Norton

Technological University Dublin (Ireland)

16:00-16:15 [OS2.4] Effective Emissivity: How cavity reflectivity affects emitter operating point?

S. Karnani, H. Hier, W. Allmon, N. Das, and C. Mike Waits

Army Research Laboratory (USA)

16:15-16:30 [OS2.5] Experimental Investigation of Improving Thermophotovoltaic Energy Conversion via Photon Recycling with Ellipsoidal Optical Cavities

N. Talebzadeh, S. Homaei, K. Ramparsad, P. G. O'Brien

York University (Canada)

16:30-16:45 [OS2.6] Design of Optical Cavity for Thermophotovoltaics Considering Thermal Conditions in Cells

H. Wang, M. Shimizu, H. Yugami

Tohoku University (Japan)

16:45-17:00 [OS2.7] Enhancing the Capabilities in Thermophotovoltaic Systems by Harnessing Multiple Heat Sources

S. Homaei, N. Talebzadeh, P. G. O'Brien

York University (Canada)

17:00-17:30 Coffee break

Poster Session 1

17:30-18:30

PS1.1 Silicon Materials Mid-Infrared Direct Spectral Emissivity Measurement at Intermediate Temperatures

*E. Akiki, G. Hamaoui, A. Herve, F. Marty, L. Rousseau, T. Bourouina, P. Basset, E. Nefzaoui
Univ. Gustave Eiffel (France)*

PS1.2 Design strategies for very low bandgap InAs/InAsSb thermophotovoltaic cells

B. Roux¹, J-P. Perez¹, F. Martinez¹, S. Parola¹, L. del Campo², L. Cosson², O. Rozenbaum², P. Christol¹, R. Vaillon³

¹ Univ. Montpellier (France), ² CNRS-CEMHTI (France), ³ Université de Toulouse (France)

PS1.3 Interdigitated Back Contacted c-Ge thermophotovoltaic devices

M. Gamel¹, G. Rivera¹, G. López¹, M. Garín², I. Martín¹

¹ Universitat Politècnica de Catalunya (Spain), ² Universitat Central de Catalunya (Spain)

PS1.4 IR laser-fired contacts for rear surface of c-Ge TPV devices

G. Rivera¹, M. Gamel¹, G. López¹, M. Garín², I. Martín¹

¹ Universitat Politècnica de Catalunya (Spain), ² Universitat Central de Catalunya (Spain)

PS1.5 Revisiting the Role of Auger Recombination in Germanium Thermophotovoltaic Converters

P. Martín, V. Orejuela, A. Cano, I. García, I. Rey-Stolle

Universidad Politécnica de Madrid (Spain)

PS1.6	Greenhouse gases emissions and energy payback time of thermophotovoltaic electricity generation <i>D. Garrain¹, A. Pino², S. Romero³, V. Medina³, P. García-Linares³, A. Datas³</i> <i>¹CIEMAT (Spain), ² Thermophoton (Spain), ³ Universidad Politécnica de Madrid (Spain)</i>
PS1.7	Modeling thermophotovoltaics and combustion heat sources for portable power generation <i>S.V. Karnani, W. R. Allmon, H. Hier, N.C. Das, C. Mike Waits</i> <i>Army Research Laboratory (USA)</i>
PS1.8	Study of Cell Interconnection for the Design Optimization of Thermophotovoltaic Modules Under Inhomogeneous Illumination <i>I. Izquierdo^{1,2}, P. García-Linares¹, J. Villa¹, A. Datas¹</i> <i>¹ Universidad Politécnica de Madrid (Spain), ² Thermophoton (Spain)</i>
PS1.9	Photon utilization in near-field thermophotovoltaics <i>K. N. Nimje, M. F. Picardi, J. Legendre, G. T. Papadakis</i> <i>ICFO – Institut de Ciències Fotoniques, The Barcelona Institute of Science and Technology, Castelldefels (Spain)</i>
PS1.10	Radiative Transfer Mechanism and Performance Analysis of Near-Field Thermophotovoltaic System with Plasmonic Emitter <i>S. Li¹, J. Zhao^{1,2}</i> <i>¹ Harbin Institute of Technology (China), ² Key Laboratory of Aerospace Thermophysics (China)</i>
PS1.11	Spectral Efficiency Optimized Near-field Thermophotovoltaics Using Germanium-based PV Cells <i>N. Boubrik¹, M. Giroux¹, G. Forcade¹, A. Boucherif², S. Molesky³, K. Hinzer⁴, R. St-Gelais¹</i> <i>¹ University of Ottawa (Canada), ² University of Sherbrooke (Canada), ³ Polytechnique Montreal (Canada), ⁴ SUNLAB (Canada)</i>
PS1.12	An Experimental Study of the Near-Field Behaviour of PIN Junctions <i>M. Thomas¹, T. Châtelet¹, B. Behaghel², I. Radevici², L. van der Krabben³, A. Shahahmadi², J. J. Schermer³, J. Oksanen², P-O. Chapuis¹</i> <i>¹ Univ. Lyon (France), ² Aalto University (Finland), ³ Radboud University (Netherlands)</i>
PS1.13	Development of TPV cells based on inverted epitaxial Indium Gallium Arsenide <i>D. Milovich^{1,2}, E. López¹, A. M. Medrano¹, A. Datas¹</i> <i>¹ Universidad Politécnica de Madrid (Spain), ² Thermophoton (Spain)</i>
PS1.14	A radiative thermal device for refrigeration: the near-field thermophonic cooler <i>T. Châtelet, J. Legendre, P.-O. Chapuis and O. Merchiers</i> <i>CNRS – INSA – Université Lyon (France)</i>
PS1.15	Experimental study and theoretical limits of a new high-power TPV device concept <i>Longji Cui</i> <i>University of Colorado Boulder (USA)</i>

October 2 – Hybrid TPV-15 Conference (day 2) & UHTES-2 (single day)

Opening session 2 (OPS2)

9:00-10:00

Chair: Alejandro Datas (UPM)

9:00-9:10 [OPS2.1] Opening remarks

*Alejandro Datas
UPM (Spain)*

9:10-9:20 [OPS2.2] Heat decarbonization and the Iberian clean-tech ecosystem

*Bianca Dragomir (Invited)
Cleantech for Iberia (Spain)*

9:20-9:40 [OPS2.3] The Role of the European Innovation Council in heat decarbonization and thermophotovoltaics

Marco Pantaleo and Paolo Bondavalli (Invited)
European Innovation Council and SMEs Executive Agency (EISMEA)
Imperial College London, and past program manager at EISMEA

9:40-10:00 [OPS2.4] The Role of Breakthrough Energy in heat decarbonization and thermophotovoltaics

*John Lemmon and Alberto Toril (Invited)
Breakthrough Energy (USA)*

10:00-10:30 Coffee break

Oral Session 3 (OS3) - Ultra-High Temperature Thermal Batteries Developers

10:30-11:40

Chair: Alberto Toril (Breakthrough Energy)

10:30-10:40 [OS3.1] Antora Energy (USA)

Brendan Kayes (Invited)

10:40-10:50 [OS3.2] Rondo Energy (USA)

John O'Donnel (Invited)

10:50-11:00 [OS3.3] Fourth Power (USA)

John Lloyd (Invited)

11:00-11:10 [OS3.4] Kraft Block (Germany)

Martin Schichtel (Invited)

11:10-11:20 [OS3.5] Thermophoton (Spain)

Alan Pino (Invited)

11:20-11:30 [OS3.6] Exergy3 (United Kingdom)

Adam Robinson (Invited)

11:30-11:40 [OS3.7] Silbat (Spain)

Ignacio Luque (Invited)

11:40-12:10 Coffee break

Round table - Ultra-High Temperature Thermal Batteries Developers

12:10-13:30

Chairs: Alberto Toril and John Lemmon (Breakthrough Energy)

12:10-13:30 Round Table

Breakthrough Energy (USA), Antora Energy (USA), Rondo Energy (USA), Fourth Power (USA), Kraft Block (Germany), Thermophoton (Spain), Exergy3 (United Kingdom), Silbat (Spain)

13:30-15:00 Lunch

Oral Session 4 (OS4) - Ultra-High Temperature Thermal Energy Storage, Transfer and Conversion
15:00-17:00

Chairs: Alejandro Datas, Esther López and Pablo García-Linares (UPM)

-
- 15:00-15:30 [OS4.1] Mesodyne LightCell: commercializing thermophotovoltaics for fuel-flexible power, anytime, anywhere**
Walker Chan (Invited)
Mesodyne (USA)
-
- 15:30-15:45 [OS4.2] Storage-integrated solar thermophotovoltaics: model and experiments**
Maxime Giteau
CNRS-PROMES (France)
-
- 15:45-16:00 [OS4.3] Laboratory-Scale Prototype of Thermal Energy Grid Storage (TEGS) System**
K. Buznitsky, C. Kelsall, S. Verma, A. LaPotin, M. Pishahang, A. Henry
Massachusetts Institute of Technology (USA)
-
- 16:00-16:15 [OS4.4] Power-To-Heat-To-Power Storage Systems Used for Cogeneration Hybridized with Lithium-Ion Batteries and Heat Pumps**
A. López-Ceballos, I. Antón, C. Cañizo, A. Datas
Universidad Politécnica de Madrid (Spain)
-
- 16:15-16:30 [OS4.5] Metallic phase change materials for high temperature applications**
P. L. Z. Lo Biundo, W. Polkowski, J. M. Jiao, M. Wallin, M. Tangstad
Norwegian University of Science and Technology (Norway)
-
- 16:30-16:45 [OS4.6] Thermal design of high-temperature devices for liquid metal based processes**
A. Abánades, L. F. González-Portillo, E. Alonso
Universidad Politécnica de Madrid (Spain)
-
- 16:45-17:00 [OS4.7] Horizon Europe project BLAZETEC: Novel high-temperature solid-state converters under development**
Daniele M. Trucchi¹ and the BLAZETEC consortium^{2,3,4,5,6,7}
¹ Consiglio Nazionale delle Ricerche (Italy), ² Universidad Politécnica de Madrid (Spain), ³ RGS Development (Netherlands), ⁴ Ionvac Process (Italy), ⁵ The Cyprus Institute (Cyprus), ⁶ Centre Suisse d'Electronique et de Microtechnique (Switzerland), ⁷ Thermophoton (Spain)

17:00-17:30 Coffee break

Poster Session 2 (PS2)

17:30-18:30

-
- PS2.1 Competitive Analysis for Silbat's LDES Technology**
R. Golchha, I. Luque-Heredia
Silbat Energy Storage Solutions SL (Spain)
-
- PS2.2 Environmental footprint of a latent heat thermophotovoltaic system for long duration high density electrical and thermal energy storage**
D. Ruiz¹, G. San Miguel¹, R. Molinero², A. Benito², I. Luque-Heredia²
¹ Universidad Politécnica de Madrid (Spain), ² Silbat Energy Storage Solutions SL (Spain)
-
- PS2.3 Heat losses assessment of an ultra-high temperature latent heat thermophotovoltaic system coupled with concentrated solar power**
M. Zeneli, A. Datas
Universidad Politécnica de Madrid (Spain)
-
- PS2.4 Manufacturing ultra-high temperature FeSiB phase change material via aluminothermic reduction**
J. Jiao, M. Wallin, M. Tangstad
Norwegian University of Science and Technology (Norway)
-

PS2.5	Micro-encapsulation of Fe-Si ultra-high temperature phase change material <i>W. Polkowski¹, P. L. Z. Lo Biundo¹, J. M. Jiao¹, M. Wallin¹, B. Kalicki², J. Ciftci², A. Polkowska³, A. Bętkowska³, F. Kateusz³, M. Tangstad¹</i> <i>¹ Norwegian University of Science and Technology (Norway), ² AMAZEMET (Poland), ³ Łukasiewicz Research Network – Krakow Institute of Technology (Poland)</i>
PS2.6	Multiphysics Modelling of an Ultra-High Temperature Storage integrated in the SUNSON-BOX Solar-To-Heat-To-Power system <i>A. Hernández, I. Fernández-Pacheco, L. E. Acevedo, P. Royo</i> <i>IDENER (Spain)</i>
18:30-19:30	Free time – Walk to Gala Dinner venue (20-minute walk)
19:30 - 22:00	Gala Diner Venue: Museo del Traje - Av. de Juan de Herrera, 2, Moncloa - Aravaca, 28040 Madrid
October 3 – TPV-15 Conference (day 3)	
Oral Session 5 (OS5) – TPV Emitters	
10:00-11:30 Chairs: Bong Jae Lee (KAIST) and Makoto Shimizu (Tohoku University)	
10:00-10:30	[OS5.1] Fundamental limits in thermophotovoltaic systems and avenues to approach them Georgia Papadakis (Invited) <i>ICFO – Institut de Ciències Fotoniques, The Barcelona Institute of Science and Technology, Castelldefels (Spain)</i>
10:30-10:45	[OS5.2] Enhancement of TPV power density with surface-engineered emitters <i>S. Verma¹, M. Park², S. Lubner³, A. Henry¹</i> <i>¹ Massachusetts Institute of Technology (USA), ² Lawrence Berkeley National Laboratory (USA), ³ Boston University (USA)</i>
10:45-11:00	[OS5.3] Balancing Power Output and Efficiency in Thermophotovoltaics through Spectral Shaping of Selective Emitters <i>N. Hanouf, J. Drévilion, F. Enguehard</i> <i>Université de Poitiers-ISAE-ENSMA (France)</i>
11:00-11:15	[OS5.4] Silicon-Air Metasurface Fabrication and Characterization for Thermophotovoltaic Selective Filters <i>P. Bermel, D. Kortge</i> <i>Birck Nanotechnology Center (USA)</i>
11:15-11:30	[OS5.5] Directional radiative properties of high-temperature materials: results from the MSCA IF HEASERS project <i>C-A. Asselineau^{1,2,3}, B. Rousseau⁴, J. González-Aguilar¹</i> <i>¹ IMDEA Energy (Spain), ² UPM (Spain), ³ ANU (Australia), ⁴ LTeN UMR CNRS (France)</i>
11:30-12:00	Coffee break
Oral Session 6 (OS6) – Near Field TPV	
12:00-13:30 Chairs: Rodolphe Vaillon (CNRS-LAAS) and P-Oliver Chapuis (CNRS-INSA)	
12:00-12:30	[OS6.1] Near-Field Thermal Radiation and Thermophotovoltaic Energy Conversion <i>Bong Jae Lee (Invited)</i> <i>KAIST (Korea)</i>
12:30-12:45	[OS6.2] Large-Area Near-Field Thermophotovoltaic Power Generation Measuring 1.2 mW at 460°C <i>J. Selvidge¹, R. M. France¹, J. Goldsmith¹, P. Solanki², M. A. Steiner¹, E. J. Tervo^{1,2}</i> <i>¹ National Renewable Energy Laboratory (USA), ² University of Wisconsin-Madison (USA)</i>

12:45-13:00	[OS6.3] Selectively enhanced near-field radiative transfer between Tungsten and GaSb with Si 2D gratings for thermophotovoltaics <i>T. Wang, S. Li, J. Zhao</i> <i>Harbin Institute of Technology (China)</i>
13:00-13:15	[OS6.4] Micro/nanoscale spacers for enhanced thermophotovoltaic and thermionic energy conversion: a comprehensive review <i>N. Loubet, K. Bezdjian, E. López, A. Datas</i> <i>Universidad Politécnica de Madrid (Spain)</i>
13:15-13:30	[OS6.5] Improved Near-Field Thermophotovoltaics with Matched Radiator and Receiver <i>M. Giroux¹, S. Molesky², R. St-Gelais¹, J. J. Krich¹</i> <i>¹ University of Ottawa (Canada), ² Polytechnique Montreal (Canada)</i>
13:30-15:00	Lunch
Oral Session 7 (OS7) – Novel Concepts	
15:00-16:45	Chairs: Maxime Giteau (CNRS-PROMES) and Peter Bermel (Birck Nanotechnology Center - Purdue University)
15:00-15:30	[OS7.1] An analysis of the state of the art and re-introduction of vertical multijunction cells for thermophotovoltaics <i>Rodolphe Vaillon (Invited)</i> <i>LAAS-CNRS (France)</i>
15:30-15:45	[OS7.2] Dual radiative heat engines: combining a TPV cell with an active emitter <i>J. Legendre, P-O. Chapuis</i> <i>Univ. Lyon (France)</i>
15:45-16:00	[OS7.3] Photon-Enhanced Thermionic Emission Devices with Perovskite Photovoltaic Anodes for Conversion of Concentrated Sunlight <i>A. Bellucci¹, L. Vesce², M. Mastellone¹, Y. Raoui², A. Di Carlo^{1,2}, D. M. Trucchi¹</i> <i>¹ Consiglio Nazionale delle Ricerche – Istituto di Struttura della Materia (Italy), ² Università di Roma Tor Vergata (Italy)</i>
16:00-16:15	[OS7.4] Multi-junction thermoradiative cells <i>P. Bohm, A. K. Menon, Z. M. Zhang</i> <i>Georgia Institute of Technology (USA)</i>
16:15-16:30	[OS7.5] Designing a near-field thermophotonic device in the planar configuration for energy conversion <i>W. Sghaier¹, M. Thomas¹, K. Kontou¹, Thomas Châtelet¹, L. M. van der Krabben², B. Behaghel³, P. Kivisaari³, I. Radevici³, N. Gruginskie², J. J. Schermer², J. Oksanen³, P-O. Chapuis¹</i> <i>¹ Univ. Lyon (France), ² Radboud University (Netherlands), ³ Aalto University (Finland)</i>
16:30-16:45	[OS7.6] Infrared light management with emergent materials and structures for thermal nanophotonics <i>J. Toudert, C. Ruiz Herrero, J. le Rouzo, H. A. Yasset, D. Duché</i> <i>Aix Marseille Université (France)</i>
16:45-17:15	Coffee break
Closing session	
17:15-17:45	
17:45-18:45	Farewell Drinks

Combined Heat and Power via Thermal Energy Storage and Thermophotovoltaics

Brendan Kayes, Leah Kuritzky, Moritz Limpinsel, Emmett Perl, Cece Luciano, Ben Johnson, Carson Townsend, Ian Spearing, Melissa Kreger, Keyur Shah, Jacob Ng, Amit Gupta, Rubén Rodríguez Lopez, Isaiah Wilkes, Geordie Zapalac, Hamsini Gopalakrishna, Manny Guth, Scott Kato, Jonatan Ram, Sean Gray, Donald Haines, Alec Burns, Jamal Lorta, Chiranjeev Kalra, Jason Tolentino, Jordan Leventhal, Chris Briere, Lisa Wang, Raghavendra Pai, Leah Kirkland, Ry Storey-Fisher, Haley Gilbert, David Bierman, Justin Briggs, Andrew Ponec

Antora Energy, Sunnyvale, California, U.S.A.

Abstract — The manufacturing sector represents 30% of global greenhouse gas emissions, two-thirds of which are due to energy inputs. There is an urgent need to decarbonize both the thermal and electrical inputs into industrial processes, and to date there has been no cost-effective solution to tackle these emissions. Antora Energy proposes to combine thermal energy storage (TES) with thermophotovoltaics (TPV) to convert intermittent renewable electricity into reliable heat and power, providing a cost-effective pathway to decarbonizing heavy industry.

I. INTRODUCTION

Today, nearly every industrial facility in the world burns fossil fuels and/or uses grid electricity to provide massive amounts of heat and power. Across the globe, manufacturers already spend ~\$250B annually on fossil fuels for combined heat and power (CHP) systems, and hundreds of billions more in utility bills. This has a correspondingly large impact on the issue of climate-warming emissions. Indeed, industrial sources represent 30% of global greenhouse gas emissions, two-thirds of which are due to energy inputs. [1] [2] [3]

Thermal energy storage (TES) is an emerging class of energy storage technologies that promises lowest-in-class marginal cost of energy storage. This technology decarbonizes industrial heat inputs by providing the same baseload heat that is available from fossil fuels such as natural gas, but at lower costs and without carbon emissions.

Thermophotovoltaics (TPV) is a breakthrough technology that efficiently converts heat into electricity with a small modular footprint, low cost, and no moving parts. Combined with TES, TPV allows for CHP products that are powered solely by renewable electricity, allowing for the decarbonization of thermal and electrical inputs to industrial processes. Antora has demonstrated high TPV heat-to-power conversion efficiencies and is pioneering TPV manufacturing at scale. [4] [5] [6] [7]

II. ANTORA'S APPROACH TO TPV

Antora's TES system platform comprises solid carbon blocks enclosed in an insulated box the size of a small shipping container. The carbon blocks can be resistively heated to

temperatures above 2000 °C, resulting in a highly energy-dense energy storage system. Both the storage medium and the insulation are made of carbon, enabling an inexpensive system without combustion risk. The heat can be extracted at a range of temperatures, and a first product is commercially available that generates 24/7 heat for lower-temperature industrial applications such as food and chemicals.

Alternatively, radiant heat from the carbon blocks can be directed to an array of TPV modules, which we call a "panel." The amount of heat radiating onto the panel can be controlled, which in turn controls the power output from the TPV. Antora has developed a TPV device that has been optimized for operation under a such a blackbody spectrum.

Fig. 1. Schematic of TPV operation. On the left is glowing-hot carbon, emitting light at hundreds of times the intensity of sunlight. On the right is a TPV module.

III. PROTOTYPE DEMONSTRATION

In an initial demonstration, Antora showed electric discharge from TPV modules in a product-realistic environment (see Fig. 2). All control subsystems were de-risked.

Fig. 2. Photograph of Antora's commercial-scale TES system near Fresno, California.

IV. MANUFACTURING SCALE UP

Generous funding from the California Energy Commission (CEC) enabled Antora to lease the facility and purchase the equipment for a TPV cell fab with a capacity of 2-megawatts per year. [8] Further funding from the Advanced Research Projects Agency–Energy (ARPA-E), announced earlier this year, will enable Antora to scale up TPV manufacturing, including cell and module production, to a 10-megawatt per year capacity. [9] This will help address the growing demand for long-duration energy storage in synergy with clean but intermittent energy sources. In addition, Antora will be

Fig. 3. Antora's TPV manufacturing facility in Sunnyvale, California.

accelerating its work on productizing the integration of TPV into its upcoming CHP thermal battery product.

V. CONCLUSIONS

TPV has a significant and as-yet unrealized role to play in the decarbonization of industrial energy. When coupled with TES, TPV has the potential to open a new design space for CHP products that are powered purely by renewable electricity, which in turn holds the promise of decarbonizing heavy industry and other so-called "hard to decarbonize" sectors.

ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

The entire Antora Energy team has contributed to the development of the technology described herein. This work has benefited immensely from the contributions of our consultants, especially Ben Bierman at Integration Advantage. We acknowledge the contributions of many wonderful interns, past and present. We would also like to acknowledge our funding sources, including but not limited to the CEC and ARPA-E. [10]

REFERENCES

- [1] <https://breakthroughenergy.org/our-approach/grand-challenges/>
- [2] <https://www.ica.org/commentaries/clean-and-efficient-heat-for-industry>
- [3] https://www.energystar.gov/industrial_plants/decarbonizing_industry/sources_industrial_greenhouse_emissions
- [4] E. J. Tervo et al., "Efficient and scalable GaInAs thermophotovoltaic devices," *Joule* 6, 2566–2584 November 16, 2022, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.joule.2022.10.002>.
- [5] M. Steiner et al., "Record Efficiency InGaAs Thermophotovoltaic Cells For Energy Storage Applications", NREL, Golden, CO (United States), NREL/PR-5900-82094, oct. 2022.
- [6] T. C. Narayan et al., "Platform for Accurate Efficiency Quantification of > 35% Efficient Thermophotovoltaic Cells," 2021 IEEE 48th Photovoltaic Specialists Conference (PVSC), Fort Lauderdale, FL, USA, 2021, pp. 1352-1354, doi: 10.1109/PVSC43889.2021.9518588.
- [7] T. C. Narayan et al., "World record demonstration of > 30% thermophotovoltaic conversion efficiency," 2020 47th IEEE Photovoltaic Specialists Conference (PVSC), Calgary, AB, Canada, 2020, pp. 1792-1795, doi: 10.1109/PVSC45281.2020.9300768.
- [8] <https://antoraenergy.com/tpv>
- [9] <https://antoraenergy.com/scaleup>
- [10] A list of our partners can be found at <https://antoraenergy.com/>

Narrow Bandgap Intersubband Thermophotovoltaic Cells

Morgan Turville-Heitz¹, Vida Nooshnab¹, Zhenxiang Xu¹, Jeremy Kirch¹, Luke Mawst¹, & Eric Tervo^{1,2}

¹Department of Electrical & Computer Engineering, University of Wisconsin-Madison, USA

²Department of Mechanical Engineering, University of Wisconsin-Madison, USA

Abstract — Narrow bandgap thermophotovoltaic cells are needed to reach high power density with low temperature sources. However, bulk junction narrow gap cells face challenges including high nonradiative losses, challenging epitaxial growth, and high-cost substrates. An alternative approach is to use quantum-engineered structures comprised of wider bandgap materials to obtain low effective bandgaps. Here, we describe one such device, an intersubband photovoltaic cell, which operates similarly to a quantum cascade photodetector. We experimentally measured power generation from a quantum cascade cell illuminated by a thermal source, and we performed optoelectronic simulations to identify strategies for improved cell performance.

I. INTRODUCTION

Many proposed applications for thermophotovoltaic (TPV) converters only offer source temperatures well below 1,000 °C, which motivates the use of narrow bandgap photovoltaic (PV) cells to obtain reasonable power density. Unfortunately, the performance of bulk junction narrow gap PV cells significantly lags their higher bandgap counterparts [1] due to difficulties in mitigating nonradiative losses. Additionally, narrow gap materials can be more difficult to grow by metalorganic chemical vapor deposition (MOCVD) as they typically require precursor gasses to pyrolyze at lower growth temperatures.

This has led researchers to examine more exotic structures based on quantum cascade lasers and photodetectors, which include interband cascade and intersubband cascade devices [2,3]. Interband cascade PV cells leverage interband transitions between valence and conduction minibands, while intersubband cascade PV (ISPV) cells utilize transitions between conduction subbands. Interband cascade PV cells have received considerable experimental attention [4], but ISPV cells have only been examined analytically by a few authors.

Because ISPV cells use transitions between conduction subbands, they are unipolar, majority carrier devices with small effective bandgaps defined entirely by wider bandgap materials. This means they can be grown on more readily available GaAs or InP substrates, their growth is facilitated by the use of wider bandgap materials, they are self-passivating, and they are insensitive to material defects because the activation energy of trap states is large compared to the intersubband gaps.

To begin to explore the potential of these devices, we performed transport modeling to design an initial ISPV cell, finite element electromagnetic modeling to examine light-coupling methods, and experimental measurements of a quantum cascade device under thermal illumination. Our

results suggest that IPV cells have potential to be significantly improved and compete with bulk junction cell performance.

II. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

We grew an intersubband quantum cascade laser (QCL) by MOCVD to test in a power generation configuration, even though this particular structure is not optimized for PV operation. Deep-etched (~20 μm wide x 3mm long) ridge waveguide QCLs were fabricated, which consists of 40 stages of digitally graded GaInAs/AlInAs quantum wells and barriers, and it has an emission/absorption peak at about 4.6 μm [5]. We exposed the QCL to an electrically-driven thermal IR source as illustrated in Fig. 1(a), which has a peak intensity near 3 μm, and this light was collimated and then focused onto the edge of the QCL. Current-voltage (IV) scans were taken of the QCL for varying powers supplied to the IR source. The resulting current-voltage characteristics of the QCL are shown in Fig. 1(b). The QCL rapidly heats up to an elevated steady-state temperature under illumination, which causes the change in slope of the IV trace near the origin. As the illumination intensity is increased, we observe a clear photocurrent associated with the negative y-intercept and increasing power generation associated with the

Figure 1. (a) Schematic of the measurement setup and (b) measured current-voltage characteristics in dark conditions (dashed line) and under illumination from a thermal emitter.

IV curve in the fourth quadrant. Even though the voltages, currents, and powers are quite small, to the best of our knowledge this experiment is the first demonstration of power generation with an ISPV cell from a thermal source, and it provides critical evidence that these devices can indeed be used as TPV cells.

We also performed quantum optoelectronic simulations of several different types of structures. These included a quantum cascade laser (QCL) similar to that tested, a modern intersubband QCD designed for operation at $4.3\ \mu\text{m}$ [6], and an improved ISPV design that we developed with some limited optimization. Current-voltage characteristics assuming a $1\ \mu\text{m}$ thick active region are shown in Fig. 3(a). Band structures for a single stage at the maximum power point for the QCD and ISPV devices are shown in Figs. 3(b) and (c), respectively. The

Figure 2. (a) Simulated current-voltage characteristics under illumination for a QCL, QCD, and our ISPV design, all assuming a $1\ \mu\text{m}$ thick active region. The band structures for the QCD and ISPV devices are shown in (b) and (c), respectively.

QCL structure achieves a relatively low photocurrent as expected, because the optical wells are undoped and not designed for absorption. The QCD shows a much higher photocurrent at low voltages, but it is not intended for power production and the voltage falls off quickly with forward bias. The new ISPV design, on the other hand, exhibits a relatively flat current at zero bias and a much higher fill factor and open-circuit voltage compared to the QCD. By comparing the band structures of the QCD and ISPV devices in Fig. 3(b) and 3(c), we see that the ISPV cell has much fewer wells and barriers in a single stage (allowing for more stages), higher barriers next to the optical well (reducing thermionic emission), and slightly tapered wells and barriers. Finally, there is reduced overlap between adjacent coupled states in the cascade region. Although more study is required to fully understand why each of these effects leads to the substantial power generation improvement compared to a traditional QCD structure, there is clearly potential to design these to operate with substantial power generation.

III. CONCLUSIONS

Our results suggest that intersubband quantum cascade devices can be designed to produce power when operated in a photovoltaic configuration. The optimum structure for this is substantially different than a traditional QCD. Additional simulations of electromagnetic coupling, not provided here, indicate that structures can be fabricated to effectively couple light into the active region and meet polarization selection criteria. Future research will elucidate the underlying behavior and demonstrate high-performance ISPV cells.

REFERENCES

- [1] B. Roux, C. Lucchesi, J.-P. Perez, P.-O. Chapuis, and R. Vaillon, "Main performance metrics of thermophotovoltaic devices: analyzing the state of the art," *Journal of Photonics for Energy*, vol. 14, no. 4, p. 042403, 2024, doi: 10.1117/1.JPE.14.042403.
- [2] R. T. Hinkey, Z.-B. Tian, S. M. S. S. Rassel, R. Q. Yang, J. F. Klem, and M. B. Johnson, "Interband Cascade Photovoltaic Devices for Conversion of Mid-IR Radiation," *IEEE Journal of Photovoltaics*, vol. 3, no. 2, pp. 745–752, 2013, doi: 10.1109/JPHOTOV.2013.2239360.
- [3] J. Yin and R. Paiella, "Multiple-junction quantum cascade photodetectors for thermophotovoltaic energy conversion," *Optics Express*, vol. 18, no. 2, pp. 1618–1629, 2010, doi: 10.1364/OE.18.001618.
- [4] R. Q. Yang, W. Huang, and M. B. Santos, "Narrow bandgap photovoltaic cells," *Solar Energy Materials and Solar Cells*, vol. 238, p. 111636, 2022, doi: 10.1016/j.solmat.2022.111636.
- [5] D. Botez *et al.*, "High-efficiency, high-power mid-infrared quantum cascade lasers [Invited]," *Optical Materials Express*, vol. 8, no. 5, pp. 1378–1398, 2018, doi: 10.1364/OME.8.001378.
- [6] A. Harrer *et al.*, " $4.3\ \mu\text{m}$ quantum cascade detector in pixel configuration," *Optics Express*, vol. 24, no. 15, pp. 17041–17049, 2016, doi: 10.1364/OE.24.017041.

An analysis of the state of the art and re-introduction of vertical multijunction cells for thermophotovoltaics

Basile Roux,^a Oriol Teixidó,^b Christophe Lucchesi,^c Jean-Philippe Perez,^a Pierre-Olivier Chapuis,^c Daniel Chemisana,^b Rodolphe Vaillon,^d

^aIES, Univ Montpellier, CNRS, Montpellier, France

^bApplied Physics Section of the Environmental Science Department, University of Lleida, Lleida, Spain

^cCNRS, INSA-Lyon, CETHIL, UMR 5008, Villeurbanne, France

^dLAAS-CNRS, Université de Toulouse, CNRS, Toulouse, France

Abstract — The presentation will be divided in two parts. First, an analysis of the state of the art, based on more than thirty articles reporting on experimental data, will reveal trends in electrical power density, pairwise efficiency and heat power density. Some lessons will be learned or re-learned. Second, vertical multijunction cells will be re-introduced, and their interest in thermophotovoltaic conversion explained. Recent tests of a silicon vertical multijunction cell in thermophotovoltaic illumination conditions will be presented and discussed.

I. INTRODUCTION

The first World Conference on Thermophotovoltaic Generation of Electricity (TPV-1) was held in July 1994. Thirty years later, it seems useful to analyze the state of the art in terms of experimental performance. To do so, a specific viewpoint was chosen in our recent work [1]: a close examination of the main performance metrics, i.e. electrical power density (p_{out}) and pairwise efficiency (η_{pair}), plus heat power density generated in the cell (q_{heat}). This last quantity indicates the amount of heat power that had to be dissipated to obtain the specified cell operating temperature. In the first part of the presentation, results from ref. [1] extended with new datapoints will be discussed. Taking the detailed balance limit as a reference, the analysis will show the progresses made to date, draw lessons from certain observations, and draw attention to the issues that remain to be resolved.

At TPV-1, Bernard L. Sater introduced vertical multijunction (VMJ) cells for thermophotovoltaic conversion (preceding article published in 1995 [2]). Although all the expected advantages of these cells were described in B.L. Sater's article, no experimental demonstration was carried out for thermophotovoltaics. Almost thirty years later, we used a commercial silicon VMJ cell to test the performances of such cells in TPV illumination conditions [3]. In the second part of the presentation, VMJ cells will be re-introduced and the results of our recent work extended with new data [4] will be presented and discussed.

II. ANALYZING THE STATE OF THE ART

Using data from articles reporting on different (> 30) TPV experiments, analyses in pairwise efficiency, electrical power density, and heat power density generated in the cell, provide a great deal of information about the trends in TPV design strategies adopted until now. Conveniently the performance metrics can be compared against detailed-balance calculations of the maximum performance achievable in the far field [1].

Fig. 1. Pairwise efficiency (η_{pair}) and electrical power density (p_{out}) of the selected experimental data, normalized by the corresponding value in the detailed-balance limit ($\eta_{pair,lim}$) and ($p_{out,lim}$), considering the same emitter and cell temperatures, and same cell bandgap as in the experiment. Figure adapted from [1] with additional datapoints.

As an example, Figure 1 shows that TPV devices operating in the far field do not seem to aim at maximizing power output. The purpose of using near field effects is to have power output exceeding the (far-field) detailed balance limit. Nevertheless, it appears that only one near-field TPV device achieves that purpose, but at the expense of cooling down the cell to cryogenic temperatures.

Fig. 2. Heat power density generated in the cell as a function of electrical power density, for the selected experimental data. The color lines depict the linear relation between q_{heat} and p_{out} for selected values of the pairwise efficiency (η_{pair}): 1%, 10%, 20%, 40%, 50%, and 60%. The symbols of Figure 1 are used. Figure adapted from [1] with additional datapoints.

Figure 2 is presented here to draw attention to the heat power that needs to be dissipated for the cell to operate at a temperature close to 25°C (for the vast majority of experiments). Cell cooling is often taken for granted, whereas some datapoints show that cooling cannot have been that easy. It is also clear that as electrical power density increases, pairwise efficiency must improve at the same time, otherwise maintaining the cell at a reasonable temperature is likely to be a serious problem.

III. RE-INTRODUCING VERTICAL MULTI-JUNCTION CELLS

Under high illumination conditions, Joule losses are known to be huge and to have an impact on electrical power in the first place, but also on efficiency, resulting in a larger thermal load. The so-called vertical multijunction cell (edge-illuminated cell composed of dozens of junctions connected in series) is a solution to that issue, thanks to a large reduction of current and series resistance. Proposed in the seventies for ultrahigh concentrating solar cells, the idea of using VMJ cells for thermophotovoltaics was proposed thirty years ago [2], but not experimentally assessed.

Using a 1 cm² commercial silicon VMJ cell in the conditions of thermophotovoltaic operation, measurements confirm the main expected advantages (see Figure 3): low current (few mA), large voltage (~30 V when the cell is at 25 °C), and very low Joule losses (< 80 nW) [3]. As we expect that in real TPV devices it will be very challenging to operate the cells close to 25 °C in high illumination conditions, sensitivity of performances to temperature was assessed. Advantageously, thanks to operation at high voltage, the temperature coefficient

of electrical power is smaller (-0.18 %/°C) than that of conventional Si cells. However, as the Si VMJ cell was not designed for TPV conversion, spectral selectivity is poor and pairwise efficiency modest (~11%) but improvable (up to over 50%). As we foresee more advantages than drawbacks, it seems worthwhile to re-open this line of research.

Fig. 3. Current vs voltage for the Si VMJ cell under a thermal radiation emitter at 2100 °C as a function of cell temperature. Figure adapted from [3].

ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

The presentation is dedicated to Bernard (“Bernie”) L. Sater, who suggested using VMJ cells for TPV conversion some thirty years ago, who passionately shared as much information as he could with us, and who sadly passed away recently. Financial supports by the French National Research Agency (ANR) under grant ANR-21-CE50-0018 (LOW-GAP-TPV), by the European Commission under grant 2020-EIC-FETPROACT-2019/GA951976 (TPX-Power), and by CNRS INSIS (project-team TREE) are acknowledged. D. Chemisana thanks Institució Catalana de Recerca i Estudis Avançats (ICREA) for the ICREA Acadèmia award.

REFERENCES

- [1] B. Roux et al., “Main performance metrics of thermophotovoltaic devices: analyzing the state of the art”, *Journal of Photonics for Energy*, vol. 14, n.o 4, article n.o 042403, 2024.
- [2] B.L. Sater, “Vertical multi-junction cells for thermophotovoltaic conversion”, *AIP Conference Proceedings*, vol. 321, 1995.
- [3] D. Chemisana et al., “Silicon Vertical Multijunction Cell for Thermophotovoltaic Conversion”, *ACS Energy Letters*, vol. 8, n.o. 3, 2023.
- [4] D. Chemisana et al., “Experimental performance of a silicon vertical multijunction cell for thermophotovoltaic conversion”, *Proceedings of the 1st International Conference of Net Zero Carbon Built Environment*, 2024.

Fundamental limits in thermophotovoltaic systems and avenues to approach them

Maxime Giteau¹, Julien Legendre¹, Kartika Nimje¹, Michela Picardi¹, Georgia T. Papadakis^{1*}

¹ICFO-Institut de Ciències Fotoniques, The Barcelona Institute of Science and Technology, Spain

* georgia.papadakis@icfo.eu

Thermophotovoltaic systems are becoming increasingly more relevant as an approach to harness light for renewable energy that is complementary to solar photovoltaics. Although recent heat-to-electricity conversion efficiencies have already exceeded the Shockley-Queisser limit [1], I will demonstrate that there still exists a large parameter space for further performance enhancement [2]. I will present two distinct approaches for reaching ultra-high conversion efficiencies near the Carnot limit: enabling near-field interactions between the emitter and cell [3] and leveraging hot-carrier photovoltaic cells for harnessing high-energy thermal photons [4]. I will additionally discuss two recently introduced approaches to leverage nonreciprocity for accessing high thermodynamic efficiencies in the case of solar photovoltaics [5] and thermophotovoltaics [6] that rely on tandem cells in transmission mode [7]. Finally, I will introduce a thermodynamic figure of merit for the universal classification of experimentally demonstrated performances of thermophotovoltaic devices with respect to their thermodynamic limits [8].

References

- [1] *Thermophotovoltaic efficiency of 40%*, A. LaPotin *et al*, Nature 604, 287-291 (2022)
- [2] *Thermodynamics performance bounds for radiative heat engines*, M. Giteau, M. Picardi, G. T. Papadakis, Phys. Rev. Applied 20, L061003 (2023)
- [3] *Thermodynamics of light management in near-field thermophotovoltaics*, G. T. Papadakis, M. Orenstein, E. Yablonovitch, S. Fan, Phys. Rev. Applied 16, 064063 (2021)
- [4] *Hot carrier thermophotovoltaic systems*, K. Nimje, M. Giteau, G. T. Papadakis, Journal of Optics, 10.1088 (2024)
- [5] *Reaching the Ultimate Efficiency of Solar Energy Harvesting with a nonreciprocal multijunction solar cell*, Y. Park, B. Zhao, S. Fan, Nano Lett. 22, 448-452 (2022)
- [6] *Nonreciprocal thermophotovoltaic systems*, Y. Park, Z. Omair, S. Fan, ACS Photonics 9, 3943-3949 (2022)
- [7] *Nonreciprocity in transmission mode with planar structures for arbitrarily polarized light*, M. Picardi, V. Moerbeek, M. Pascale, G. T. Papadakis, arXiv: 2405:06066v1 (2024)
- [7] *Thermodynamics figure of merit for thermophotovoltaics*, M. Giteau, M. Picardi, G. T. Papadakis, Journal of Photonics for Energy, 14, 4 (2024)

Funding

We acknowledge funding from “la Caixa” Foundation (ID 100010434), from the PID2021-125441OA-I00 project funded by MCIN/AEI/10.13039/501100011033/ FEDER, UE, and from the European Union’s Horizon 2020 research and innovation program under the Marie Skłodowska-Curie grant agreement No 847648. The fellowship code is LCF/BQ/PI21/11830019. This work is part of the R&D project CEX2019-000910-S, funded by MCIN/AEI/10.13039/501100011033/, from Fundacio Cellex, Fundacio Mir-Puig, and from Generalitat de Catalunya through the CERCA program.

Micro-encapsulation of Fe-Si ultra-high temperature phase change material

Wojciech Polkowski¹, Paolo Lai Zhong Lo Biundo¹, Jian Meng Jiao¹, Maria Wallin¹, Bartosz Kalicki², Jakub Ciftci², Adelajda Polkowska³, Aleksandra Bętkowska³, Filip Kateusz³, Merete Tangstad¹

¹ Department of Materials Science and Engineering, Norwegian University of Science and Technology, Alfred Getz vei 2, 7491, Trondheim, Norway

² AMAZEMET Sp. z o.o. [Ltd], Al. Jana Pawła II 27, 00-867 Warsaw, Poland

³ Łukasiewicz Research Network – Krakow Institute of Technology, Zakopiańska 73 Str, 30-418 Krakow, Poland

Abstract — In this work, a micro-encapsulation approach was introduced for the first time to a binary Fe-Si phase change material. The alloy composition was developed through a thermodynamic modelling. After that, a multistep processing was designed and applied to fabricate spherical microcapsules having a structure of SiO₂ shell and the Fe-Si alloy core. Finally, basic thermophysical properties of encapsulated Fe-Si powders were experimentally validated in DSC studies.

- A transition from ternary eutectic Fe-Si-B alloy towards B-free binary eutectic Fe-Si alloys, to decrease potential costs and technical difficulties coming from using of boron.
- An implementation of “micro-encapsulation” approach in order to increase a durability and lifetime of high temperature PCMs.

I. INTRODUCTION

Latent heat thermal energy storage (LHTES) has been recognized as an attractive method for supporting renewable energy sources in terms of energy availability during blackout periods [1]. One of the main features of each LHTES system is a phase change material (PCM), i.e. a substance that can absorb and release energy (as a heat) on demand. Thermophysical properties of PCM (including heat of fusion, thermal conductivity and volumetric expansion) determine the overall performance of the energy storing unit [2].

In our recent projects, we have developed a ternary eutectic Fe-26Si-9B (wt%) alloy as a new candidate to be applied in ultra-high temperature LHTES system [3]. The alloy utilizes a concept of using extraordinarily high latent heat of both pure Si and B, while Fe is added to ensure a low volumetric thermal expansion upon solid↔liquid phase changes. Nevertheless, as application of PCMs at ultra-high temperatures brings several intrinsic challenges, some new material design approaches ought to be taken into consideration, in order to further increase durability and accessibility of LHTES devices.

A. From Fe-Si-B to Fe-Si based PCMs

Although the Fe-26Si-9B alloy has proved its high applicability as high temperature PCM, there are still some economic and technological issues that ought to be solved. One of them is related with a very high price and geographically limited availability of boron [4]. Furthermore, addition of boron increases a reactivity with most of carbon-, oxide- or nitride-based refractory ceramics, what makes a selection of materials for PCM container quite difficult. Therefore, in this work we propose to impose the following new strategies:

B. Micro-encapsulation concept

A widely documented high reactivity of Si-containing melts should be considered as detrimental in terms of potential premature degradation of the PCM's as well other components of the LHTES devices. In this regard, a concept of “micro-encapsulation” of a PCM through the pre-oxidation treatment appears as a promising path to develop highly durable LHTES solutions. The basic concept behind this process consists of at least two steps:

- a fabrication of the alloy in the form of spherical powders,
- a thermochemical heat-treatment focused on a development of continuous and stable shell/core like structure.

Indeed, it has been recently documented by Han et al. [5] that the micro-encapsulation of the Al-based PCMs can provide excellent cyclability in terms of both the latent heat and melting point values in consecutive melting/solidification phase changes, even up to 3000 operational cycles.

In this work, we propose for the first time to use this approach to ultra-high temperature PCMs from the Fe-Si system.

II. MATERIALS AND METHODS

A. Material selection and processing

The material investigated was a Fe-Si alloy developed and selected by using thermodynamic modelling in FactSage 8.1. The alloy was produced by an induction melting of a mixture of commercially available ferrosilicon and metallurgical grade Si (Elkem, Norway). The materials processing route is schematically shown in Fig. 1. Firstly, the alloy ingots were transformed into spherical powders by using novel ultrasonic assisted atomization technique provided by the AMAZEMET rePowder system (Warsaw, Poland). After that, the powders

were subjected to a two-step thermo-chemical treatment that included:

- (i) an impregnation of powders with silica suspension and;
- (ii) a high temperature heat treatment (annealing in air).

The main purpose of both steps was to activate the surface of particles and then to build up continuous stable SiO_2 layer protecting the PCM alloy against structure/properties degradation.

Fig. 1. A scheme of the applied materials processing.

B. Materials characterization

At every stage of the process, microstructure of involved materials was characterized by using light and scanning

electron microscopy coupled with the X-ray Energy Dispersive Spectroscopy (SEM/EDS) method. A special attention was given to qualitative and quantitative analysis of the effect of processing on the chemical composition and morphology of the developed oxide shell.

Thermophysical properties of the as-cast Fe-Si alloy, atomized and encapsulated powders, were examined and compared in differential scanning calorimetry (DSC) experiments. The DSC technique was used to evaluate melting/solidification behavior of the materials in terms of temperature ranges, as well as to quantify the latent heat of fusion.

Furthermore, thermocycling experiments, i.e. consecutive heating/cooling cycles, were performed for the sake of assessing cyclability and stability of the developed PCM microcapsules.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

SUNSON project has received funding from Horizon Europe Research and Innovation Action programme under Grant Agreement no 101083827, funded by the European Union. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or CINEA. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

REFERENCES

- [1] I. Sarbu, C. Sebarchievici, "A Comprehensive Review of Thermal Energy Storage," *Sustainability*, vol. 10, p. 191, 2018.
- [2] K. Pielichowska, K. Pielichowski, "Phase change materials for thermal energy storage," *Progress in Materials Science*, vol. 65, p. 67–123, 2014.
- [3] J. Jiao, B. Grorud, C. Sindland, J. Safarian, K. Tang, K. Sellevoll, M. Tangstad, The use of eutectic Fe-Si-B alloy as a phase change material in thermal energy storage systems, *Materials*, 2019; 12, 2312
- [4] S. Betharia, "Boron," in *Encyclopedia of Toxicology* (Third Edition), The Netherlands, Academic Press, 2014, pp. 536-539
- [5] C. Han, H. Gu, M. Zhang, et al., "Al-Si @ Al_2O_3 @ mullite microcapsules for thermal energy storage: Preparation and thermal properties," *Solar Energy Materials and Solar Cells*, vol. 217, p. 110697, 2020.

Power-To-Heat-To-Power Storage Systems Used for Cogeneration Hybridized with Lithium-Ion Batteries and Heat Pumps

Alicia López-Ceballos¹, Ignacio Antón¹, Carlos Cañizo¹, Alejandro Datas¹

¹Instituto de Energía Solar – Universidad Politécnica de Madrid. Avenida Complutense 30, Madrid 28040

Abstract — Power-to-Heat-to-Power Storage (PHPS) systems are a cheap approach to store excess of renewable energy generation. The relatively low Heat-to-Power (H2P) efficiency of PHPS can be offset using the waste heat for cogeneration applications. Supplying low-grade heat to buildings with the waste heat can serve as a cost-effective method of decarbonizing this energy sector. Alongside PHPS cogeneration, heat electrification in buildings through PV installations, energy storage and heat pumps has been studied to enhance decarbonization. This study aims to assess the impact of the building typology on the optimum configuration of a hybrid system with Lithium-Ion batteries and PHPS. In particular, the focus is on a large building fully electrified with PV installation, heat pumps and energy storages.

I. INTRODUCTION

Buildings are responsible for 26 % of the global emissions [3] and their consumption account for 30 % of the global energy demand. Electrifying the heat demand in buildings is a cost-effective way of decarbonizing this sector [4], typically achieved through Photovoltaic (PV) installations for self-consumption and heat pumps. This approach can be further improved by incorporating an energy storage device to enhance PV self-consumption. Lithium-ion (Li-ion) batteries are used in decentralized PV installations, but their high cost tend to low optimal energy capacities (short-duration purposes), and ultimately low PV self-consumption ratios. As a result, some studies have proposed hybridizing Li-ion batteries with cheaper storages (e.g., flow batteries [5], [6]), more suited for long-duration purposes, to leverage their complementary advantages. A possible cheap long-duration storage could be the Power-to-heat-to-power storage (PHPS) system.

PHPS transforms renewable energy surpluses into heat with a Power-to-Heat (P2H) converter (e.g., electrical furnace) and store it in form of sensible or latent heat at low cost. Whenever the electricity is required, a Heat-to-Power (H2P) converter (e.g., Thermo-Photovoltaic generator) transforms heat back into electricity on demand. Due to its low Cost per Energy Capacity (CPE, €/kWh) linked to the storing and insulation materials (a few 10's of €/kWh [1]), it can store large amounts of energy. The combination of the low CPE with its high Cost per Output Power (CPP_{out}) [1], and relatively low thermal-to-electric conversion efficiency; makes PHPS more suitable for long-duration applications. Nonetheless, if the low-grade waste heat occurring in the H2P conversion is used to supply heating demand, the overall Round-Trip conversion Efficiency can be increased. Supplying space and water heating demand in buildings which represent almost 40 % of their consumption [2]

could be a commendable opportunity to harness the H2P waste heat and decarbonize this energy sector. Some studies have already concluded that PHPS are better suited to large-scale applications [1]. However, given the variability in buildings' heating and electricity demand profile with its typology (i.e., hospital, block of apartments, etc.), this study aims to analyse the differences between buildings. In a previous study [7] we have compared a hybrid configuration of: Li-ion batteries and PHPS, against only Li-ion battery in an electrified building with PV. Hybridizing PHPS, better used for long-duration purposes; with a Li-ion battery, better for short-duration; resulted into a cost-effective solution. Other studies analysed how PHPS could be a better solution than Li-ion batteries in different configurations [1], [8]. However, to the authors' knowledge, no previous study has assessed the impact of the building typology on the PHPS systems in its feasibility when hybridized with Li-ion batteries and heat pumps. Furthermore, this study aims determine the advantages of using the waste heat occurring in the H2P conversion.

II. METHODOLOGY

In this study we have compared the Hybrid with the baseline configuration: Li-ion system. Fig. 1 depicts the baseline in the top panel, and the Hybrid-system in the bottom panel. The figure shows the components and elements conforming the building installation.

The building is assumed to be fully electrified, meaning that in both configurations heat and electricity demand are supplied using electricity from the grid or generated by the PV installation. Surplus of PV generation is stored either in the electrical storages (Li-ion and PHPS) or in a Low Temperature Energy Storage (LTES) system. The LTES system is comprised of an air-to-water heat pump that warms up the water and stores it in a Hot Water Storage (HWS) tank. The PHPS system comprises both P2H and H2P converters along with a High Temperature Energy Storage (HTES) unit. In this case, a resistive heater is considered for the P2H converter. The H2P converter is assumed to be a heat engine (Thermophotovoltaics, Brayton, Stirling, Rankine, etc.) with certain discharge efficiency. Additionally, the HTES has associated some self-discharge losses. Finally, the Li-ion battery is composed of an AC/DC converter and the Li-ion battery cells.

The system performance is modelled following an energy decision making tree determining the priority orders of the energy flows between the components within the system to

cover the building energy demand. Decisions on the energy flow do not change based on the time horizon, nor include electricity cost, energy demand or PV generation forecasting. The input electricity to the system will be used to: (1) cover the electricity demand, (2) or the heating demand, which includes the Space Heating (SH) and the Domestic Hot Water (DHW); (3); and charge the energy storage units.

Additionally, a tool has been developed to optimize the main components' capacities (power and energy capacity of the PHPS and Li-ion batteries, PV and heat pump power capacity and HWS energy capacity) to minimize the Levelized Cost of Energy (LCOE). The optimal solution for the Hybrid-system configuration can result into an installation incorporating: (1) only a PHPS storage (i.e., 100 % PHPS, thus, completely replacing Li-ion battery); (2) only Li-ion battery (i.e., 100 % Li-ion, coinciding with the base-line configuration); or (3) hybridizing both storages.

Fig. 1 Electricity and heating energy flows and components of the Li-ion (baseline, top panel) and Hybrid (bottom panel) configurations.

III. PRELIMINARY RESULTS AND CONCLUSIONS

To fulfil the objectives of this study, we are going to make a parametric study varying the Coefficient of Performance (COP) and H2P efficiency for two buildings. An initial study has already been conducted assuming a block of apartments located in Madrid with a yearly electricity and heating demands of 580 MWh and 280 MWh respectively. Fig 2 depicts the optimum configuration when varying the heat pump COP and the H2P efficiency, being red when the optimum is 100 % PHPS, blue when the optimal solution is the baseline configuration, and in-between colours for the Hybrid configuration. The panel in the right indicates that the hybrid and ultimately the PHPS system performs better than single Li-

ion when using the waste heat. A lower H2P efficiency can be tolerated if the PHPS waste heat is leveraged, specially at low COP values. Further studies will determine whether the type of building has an impact on the optimum hybrid system.

Fig. 2. Optimum configuration depending on heat pump COP and H2P efficiency for the case of not using the waste heat (left panel) and using it (right panel) assuming a block of apartments building. Red (Blue) regions represent cases in which the optimum solution is 100 % PHPS (Li-ion), whilst the purple regions are hybrid cases. Black lines show the LCOE reduction of the optimum solution with respect to the base line scenario (100 % Li-ion) in percentage.

REFERENCES

- [1] A. Datas, A. López-Ceballos, E. López, A. Ramos, and C. del Cañizo, "Latent heat thermo-photovoltaic batteries," *SSRN Electronic Journal*, pp. 1–26, 2021, doi: 10.2139/ssrn.3908778.
- [2] International Energy Agency, "World Energy Outlook 2023," 2023. [Online]. Available: www.iea.org/terms
- [3] IEA, "Tracking Clean Energy Progress," Analysis. Accessed: Apr. 18, 2024. [Online]. Available: <https://www.iea.org/reports/tracking-clean-energy-progress-2023>
- [4] K. Kavvadias, J. P. Jiménez-Navarro, and G. Thomassen, *Decarbonising the EU heating sector - Integration of the power and heating sector*. 2019. doi: 10.2760/943257.
- [5] L. N. Palaniswamy, N. Munzke, C. Kupper, and M. Hiller, *Optimized Energy Management of a Solar and Wind Equipped Student Residence with Innovative Hybrid Energy Storage and Power to Heat Solutions*. Atlantis Press International BV, 2023. doi: 10.2991/978-94-6463-156-2_24.
- [6] M. Möller *et al.*, "SimSES: A holistic simulation framework for modeling and analyzing stationary energy storage systems," *J Energy Storage*, vol. 49, no. March 2021, p. 103743, 2022, doi: 10.1016/j.est.2021.103743.
- [7] A. López-Ceballos, C. del Cañizo, I. Antón, and A. Datas, "Integrating Lithium-Ion and Thermal Batteries with Heat Pumps for Enhanced Photovoltaic Self-Consumption," 2024, doi: 10.2139/SSRN.4743029.
- [8] A. Datas, A. Ramos, and C. del Cañizo, "Techno-economic analysis of solar PV power-to-heat-to-power storage and trigeneration in the residential sector," *Appl Energy*, vol. 256, no. September, p. 113935, 2019, doi: 10.1016/j.apenergy.2019.113935.

Thermal design of high-temperature devices for liquid metal based processes

Alberto Abánades, Luis F. González-Portillo, Elisa Alonso

Thermal Energy for Sustainability (TE4S) research group, Universidad Politécnica de Madrid

Abstract — Thermal Energy for Sustainability (TE4S) research group from Universidad Politécnica de Madrid (UPM) has been working on liquid metal technology for almost two decades. First on nuclear fusion [1] and transmutation of nuclear wastes [2], and nowadays on the development of the application of liquid metal technology to ultra-high temperature (>1100 °C) methane pyrolysis reactors. In this communication, we will showcase our experience with specific thermal and material aspects that must be considered for the design of liquid metal applications in the context of energy storage.

I. INTRODUCTION

Almost any added value process is based on a material transformation strongly dependent on how energy is applied and which level of temperature would be achievable. Exergy is, in fact, one of the most important thermodynamic properties defining the quality of the energy to be used in chemical, industrial and power processes. The efficiency of direct utilization of thermal energy is increasing with its exergy content, mainly derived from the temperature at which a process can be run. Therefore, operating at very high or ultra-high temperatures is one of the challenges for the development of advanced processes in many fields. Materials and energy carriers in those processes must be able to operate at temperatures well above 1000 °C, what is very far from the capabilities for current coolants and engineering materials. New materials, fluids and manufacturing techniques must be developed for high temperature processes.

Liquid metals are fluids of great interest due to their high thermal conductivity and diffusivity, as well as their stability at ultra- high temperature [3]. These properties make liquid metals ideal fluids as coolants and heat carriers in many power applications such as solar [4], energy storage [5] and nuclear energy [6]. There are also many chemical reactions requiring ultra-high temperatures and good heat transfer media to provide the reaction enthalpy and activation energy to the molecules needed to close many cycles in the circular economy [7].

II. LIQUID METAL FLUID-MECHANICS.

It is crucial to understand the fluid mechanics of liquid metals to optimize their use in high-temperature processes. One key characteristic of these metals is their low Prandtl number due to their high viscosity and conductivity. Based on our previous

analysis [8], several issues must be addressed to characterize low Prandtl number fluids:

- Characterization of bubble evolution in pools or channels and the evaluation of their flow regime.
- Validation of assumptions for solving the Navier-Stokes equation (RANS) to grant reduction of computational power to implement direct simulation models (DNS).
- Validation of CFD codes with low Prandtl number (Pr) fluids such as liquid metals to estimate heat convection/conduction transfer phenomena.
- Improvements in the static porous bed treatment models.

III. THERMAL ANALYSIS.

The challenge of scaling industrial processes is directly related to the heat and mass transfer characteristics of materials. For instance, for thermal energy storage (TES) applications, thermal diffusivity is a key parameter that limits the design respect to power exchange, as ion transfer capacity (mA/m²) determines membrane size of electro-chemical batteries. Specific heat is a very important parameter for the volumetric storage capacity.

High temperature processes require high conductivity structural materials to reduce temperature differences. High thermal conductivity of structural materials reduces as well thermo-mechanical stress. Gaseous coolants and heat carriers suggest the use of liquid coolants, which increase convective heat transfer processes. Additionally, radiative properties are of great importance and have to be adapted for the design. The availability of thermal insulation materials for high temperature processes is important as well. Multilayer insulations is the option for a cost-efficiency balance and thermal losses reduction.

As an example, Fig. 1 shows the reflectance of a liquid metal as tin. That will be important for the evaluation of its radiative properties. The high reflectance in the infrared region means a low absorptance and emittance above 600 μm wavelength.

IV. MATERIAL COMPATIBILITY

Liquid metals are known to be very corrosive with steel. As an example, iron as main component of most of steels, forms tin alloys as shows the phase diagram of tin and iron in Fig. 2. Therefore, specific surface coatings must be applied for the use of refractory steels in contact with liquid metals. There are other metals such as tungsten or rhenium that can be used, but their costs make them unfeasible.

Fig. 1. Reflectance of tin and its comparison with solar spectrum.

Fig. 2. Phase diagram of iron and tin alloys.

An alternative to metal materials is ceramics. Corrosion rates have been reported to be greatly reduced in composites with ceramic materials such as alumina (Al_2O_3), silicon carbide (SiC), mullite ($\text{Al}_6\text{Si}_2\text{O}_{13}$) or graphite [9]. These low corrosion rates make the use of such materials viable for constructing high-temperature liquid metal reactors.

Special attention should be paid towards the manufacturing techniques available for ceramic materials, given their significant promise for the implementation in ultra-high temperature devices.

V. DISCUSSION

Growing interest in developing ultra-high temperature applications aims to surpass the limitations of current energy systems. However, the use of liquid metals as coolants or storage media has been limited, primarily due to compatibility issues with common structural materials. Materials such as lead and tin are particularly suitable for these applications due to their broad liquid phase temperature range.

For the past decade, the Thermal Energy for Sustainability (TE4S) research group at Universidad Politécnica de Madrid (UPM) has been working on the use of liquid metal in high-temperature applications. We will show our experience regarding the design of ultra-high temperature devices based on liquid metal technology, focusing on the use of tin. We will also showcase the latest designs and experiments involving liquid metal reactors.

REFERENCES

- [1] A. Abánades, A. García, N. Casal, J. M. Perlado, and A. Ibarra, "Conceptual design of the liquid metal laboratory of the TECHNOFUSION facility," *Fusion Eng. Des.*, vol. 87, no. 2, 2012, doi: 10.1016/j.fusengdes.2011.12.003.
- [2] A. Abánades and A. Peña, "Steady-state natural circulation analysis with computational fluid dynamic codes of a liquid metal-cooled accelerator driven system," *Nucl. Eng. Des.*, vol. 239, no. 2, 2009, doi: 10.1016/j.nucengdes.2008.10.028.
- [3] N. Lorenzin and A. Abánades, "A review on the application of liquid metals as heat transfer fluid in Concentrated Solar Power technologies," *Int. J. Hydrogen Energy*, vol. 41, no. 17, pp. 6990–6995, 2016, doi: 10.1016/j.ijhydene.2016.01.030.
- [4] A. Heinzl *et al.*, "Liquid Metals as Efficient High-Temperature Heat-Transport Fluids," *Energy Technology*, vol. 5, no. 7. Wiley-VCH Verlag, pp. 1026–1036, Jul. 2017. doi: 10.1002/ente.201600721.
- [5] A. Ramos, E. López, C. del Cañizo, and A. Datas, "Cost-effective ultra-high temperature latent heat thermal energy storage systems," *J. Energy Storage*, vol. 49, p. 104131, 2022, doi: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.est.2022.104131>.
- [6] V. I. Subbotin, M. N. Arnoldov, F. A. Kozlov, and A. L. Shimkevich, "Liquid-Metal Coolants for Nuclear Power," *At. Energy*, vol. 92, no. 1, pp. 29–40, 2002, doi: 10.1023/A:1015050512710.
- [7] T. Keijer, V. Bakker, and J. C. Sloopweg, "Circular chemistry to enable a circular economy," *Nat. Chem.*, vol. 11, no. 3, pp. 190–195, 2019, doi: 10.1038/s41557-019-0226-9.
- [8] A. Abánades-Velasco and Á. Martínez-Rodríguez, "Challenges for the Development of Numerical Models for Methane Pyrolysis With Liquid Metal Reactors," *Dyna*, vol. 98, no. 4, pp. 413–419, 2023, doi: 10.6036/10880.
- [9] Y. Zhang *et al.*, "Containment materials for liquid tin at 1350 °C as a heat transfer fluid for high temperature concentrated solar power," *Sol. Energy*, vol. 164, pp. 47–57, 2018, doi: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.solener.2018.01.085>.

Manufacturing ultra-high temperature FeSiB phase change material via aluminothermic reduction

Jianmeng Jiao^{1*}, Maria Wallin¹, Merete Tangstad¹

¹ Department of Materials Science and Engineering, Norwegian University of Science and Technology, 7491, Trondheim, Norway.

*Corresponding author. Email: jian.m.jiao@ntnu.no

Abstract — Fe₆₅Si₂₆B₉ (wt.%) is proposed to be a high-temperature phase change material (PCM) for a thermal energy storage system, due to its high latent heat of fusion and minimal volume change during solidification. Currently, the production of Fe₆₅Si₂₆B₉ alloy involves mixing FeSi alloys with either pure boron or FeB alloys. The use of pure boron is high cost, while the carbothermic reduction of FeB alloy results in significant greenhouse gas emissions and high energy consumption. In this regard, the aluminothermic reduction is proposed to use FeSi alloys, aluminum waste and iron metals, and calcinated colemanite for producing this FeSiB PCM. According to the experimental results, the equilibrium is achieved after 3h holding at temperatures range from 1550°C to 1650°C. By varying the slag/metal (S/M) ratio from 0.6 to 1.4, the boron content in the FeSiB alloys can be increased from 5.2wt.% to 15wt.% after 3h holding at 1650°C. Maintaining the S/M ratio at 1, the produced FeSiB alloys exhibit a boron content between 9-13 wt.%, Si and Fe ranging in 24-30wt.% and 61-64wt.%, respectively. The theoretical energy consumption is estimated to be around 1182kWh/t metal. Therefore, aluminothermic reduction can be an efficient and sustainable method for producing FeSiB alloys.

Keywords: FeSiB, B₂O₃, Aluminothermic reduction, PCM, Thermal Energy Storage

Acknowledgment

The THERMOBAT project received funds from European Commission under grant agreement 10105754. The sole responsibility for the content of this publication lies with the authors. It does not necessarily reflect the opinion of the European Union. Neither the REA nor the European Commission is responsible for any use that may be made of the information contained therein.

Directional radiative properties of high-temperature materials: results from the MSCA IF HEASeRS project

Charles-Alexis Asselineau^{1,2,3}, Benoit Rousseau⁴ and José González-Aguilar¹

¹ IMDEA Energy, High Temperature Processes Unit, Móstoles, Spain

² UPM, E.T.S.I. Industriales, Madrid, Spain

³ ANU, School Of Engineering, Canberra, Australia

⁴ LTeN UMR CNRS 6607, Nantes, France

Abstract — The MSCA IF HEASeRS project focused on simulation and characterization of spectro-directional properties of a range of high-temperature materials from November 2021 to March 2024. Results of this project include, on the experimental side, the collection of datasets regarding the surface roughness of high-temperature applications materials and their associated bi-directional reflection function; and the demonstration of a new concept to improve the directional absorptance/emittance of high-temperature materials. On theoretical aspects, the integration of techniques from the computer graphics community to radiative heat-transfer modelling reveals the potential of directional approaches to optimize the design of radiant systems.

I. INTRODUCTION

A. Motivations

Researchers are developing new and improved thermal energy conversion and/or storage concepts to contribute to the decarbonization of High-Temperature Processes (HTP) and electricity production [1, 2]. At temperatures above ~ 650 °C, radiation emerges as the dominant heat-transfer mechanism and therefore plays an important role in the intensification of heat transfers in HTP. The mechanical and chemical stability of most economically viable coatings used to modify the optical properties of materials is compromised at very high temperatures, and the radiative properties of bulk materials need to be relied upon. Fundamentally, the efficiency of HTP strongly relies on the control of the spectrum and directionality of radiation, however, these aspects are usually idealized and simplified significantly in system design for two main reasons:

- Fully coupled heat-transfer simulations are complex, not-mentioning integration in optimization methods.
- There is a lack of spectro-directional radiative data available for HTP-relevant materials.

In CSP, ThermoPhotoVoltaics (TPV) and HTP in general, most efforts to date have been focused on spectral control to improve the efficiency of CSP receivers and TPV cells while directional aspects are relatively overlooked.

B. Project objectives

The High-Temperature Angular-Selective Radiant Surfaces (HEASeRS) project [3] ran from November 2021 to March

2024 focusing on the spectro-directional properties of HTP-relevant materials for temperatures from 650 °C to 1500 °C. The general objectives of the project were threefold:

- Develop understanding and modelling capabilities for real world, rough materials.
- Demonstrate directional radiation control using prescribed 3D-printed features.
- Collect experimental data to study the Bi-Directional Reflection Function (BDRF) HTP-relevant materials.

The project was organized in three work packages linked to specific length scales as illustrated in Fig. 1.

Fig. 1: MSCA IF HEASeRS project overview.

II. PROJECT RESULTS

A. Micro-scale

The state of the art on the optical properties of rough surfaces was reviewed, with particular focus on the geometrical regime and the transition between geometrical optics and electromagnetics. Interestingly, most of the modern literature on the topic can be found in computer graphics where the conservation of the first and second law of thermodynamics is not as critical as in radiative heat-transfers. Numerous developments were brought to the open-source ray-tracing program *Tracer* [4] to simulate the optical properties of rough surfaces from synthetic and real microscopy data, and to include BDRF models in larger length-scale models. In particular, a Kd-Tree acceleration structure was implemented

to significantly accelerate the simulation of triangulated geometries, new methods to handle broadband spectral simulations for complex geometries with prescribed complex refractive indices.

Optical profilometry and in-plane spectral BDRF in the NIR and MIR ranges were acquired on SiC and alloys 230 and 718 samples in collaboration with LTeN in Nantes (France). Within an EU Sfera III transnational access to Fraunhofer ISE in Freiburg (Germany), high-resolution profilometry and full-hemisphere BDRF were acquired for oxidized alloy 230, mullite, high purity alumina (this sample also including BTDF) and calcium silicate samples. Alloy 230 also underwent progressive aging in air to quantify the absorptance gain as the natural oxide layer develops, supported by ADM and SEM-EDX microscopy and elemental analysis.

Overall, the commonly assumed Lambertian assumption for rough surfaces is not particularly accurate. Retroreflective behavior was commonly found in measurements along with specularly at larger angles of incidence. Microfacet models from the literature describe such phenomena qualitatively, but quantitative models are typically not available for real materials.

B. Meso-scale

Ray-tracing simulations of meso-scale 3-D printed grooved surfaces was performed to support a parallel experimental campaign and revealed that tailored surface geometrical features provide a successful alternative method to both significantly increase the absorptance and alter its directional characteristics in opaque materials (Fig. 2).

Fig. 2: Illustration of the 3D printing study: (a) ray tracing model and (b), (c) and (d) the comparison between simulations and measures of directional absorptance (UV-Vis-NIR).

The general behavior of the 3D-printed alloy 718 samples was qualitatively well described with Lambertian wall properties, but this simplification led to non-negligible overestimation of the absorptance by the model with relative error $>10\%$ for normal incidence reaching higher values (25% to 30%) at larger incident angles. Simplified models do not

describe the measurements well in specific directions (triangular grooves, for example). This observation signals that advanced BDRF are needed to accurately estimate the behavior of complex geometries with rough walls. The temperature dependent spectro-directional emittance of the best-performing 3d-printed samples were measured and confirmed that directionality is also present in thermal emittance.

C. Macro-scale

A theoretical study was performed to evaluate the impact of increasing specularly on the optical properties of the inner walls of cylindrical cavities heated from an open end. This study reveals that specularly can increase or decrease the effective reflectivity, depending on the aspect ratio (length on diameter) of the cavity. Additionally, increased specularly is also shown to provide absorptance benefits even when the impact of increased cavity dimensions (aspect ratios >2.5) offers diminishing returns.

IV. CONCLUSIONS AND NEXT STEPS

The successful demonstration of the modification of the optical properties of HTP-relevant materials paves the way towards advanced radiant devices optimization considering detailed optical properties from models and experimental data. Applications to radiant cavity geometries, emitters and insulation components are of interest. This work is a first step in this direction but already reveals numerous interesting aspects to study and generalize. Challenges in future efforts include the prediction of the radiative behavior of materials across the geometric optics limits that will require the use of electromagnetics simulations, coupled with ray-tracing approaches. In terms of experimental progress, the procurement of high-temperature ceramics samples with prescribed geometries and roughness, and the acquisition of BDR/TF are significant challenges.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation program under the Marie Skłodowska-Curie grant agreement No 101027316.

REFERENCES

- [1] G. P. Thiel and A. K. Stark, "To decarbonize industry, we must decarbonize heat," *Joule*, vol. 5, no. 3, pp. 531–550, 2021, doi: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.joule.2020.12.007>.
- [2] A. LaPotin *et al.*, "Thermophotovoltaic efficiency of 40%," *Nature*, vol. 604, no. 7905, pp. 287–291, 2022, doi: [10.1038/s41586-022-04473-y](https://doi.org/10.1038/s41586-022-04473-y).
- [3] "HEASeRS Grant agreement ID: 101027316," CORDIS. <https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/101027316>
- [4] C.-A. Asselineau, "Tracer - a Pythonic general ray-tracing package." <https://github.com/casselineau/Tracer>

Heat losses assessment of an ultra-high temperature latent heat thermophotovoltaic system coupled with concentrated solar power

M. Zeneli, A. Datas

^a Instituto de Energía Solar, Universidad Politécnica de Madrid, Av. Complutense s/n, 28040, Madrid, Spain.

Abstract — This paper assesses the energy performance of a FeSiB-based latent heat thermophotovoltaic (LHTPV) system coupled with beam-down concentrated solar power (CSP) optics targeting for ultra-high temperature energy storage and conversion (~ 1250 °C). The basic unit is a compact device consisting of a charging (CSP), a storage (LHTES) and a heat-to-power conversion (TPV) system that can be replicated to form the CSP-LHTPV system, though a bottom-up approach. At such unprecedented temperatures, critical operating parameters, including excess heat losses arising mainly through the LHTES system walls and solar aperture, should be determined within all four possible operating modes, i.e. charging, discharging, simultaneous charging/discharging, and storage modes. A validated transient three-dimensional computational fluid dynamics (CFD) model is applied in ANSYS Fluent v22.R2 platform to give insights on the system thermal performance and prove its operability under various insulating methods (with thermal resistances within ~ 0.1 - 0.85 m²K/W). Based on the thermal analysis, the proposed concept meets several desirable key performance indicators, including solar concentration flux of > 1000 suns, input power within 10-20 kW_{th}, and charging/discharging period of 1-2 h / 4-8 h, paving, thus, the way as a competitive highly-efficient renewable energy technology.

I. INTRODUCTION

The urgent need for decarbonization necessitates a global switch towards clean energy alternatives. At the forefront of this ‘green energy’ transition is CSP technology, which although potent it suffers from the intermittency of solar energy. Thermal energy storage (TES) is a game changer technology, essential for optimizing the use of CSP, owing to its ability of directly storing concentrated solar energy in the form of heat, which can be converted into electricity on demand. By integrating TES into CSP plants the overall energy efficiency and dispatchability can be improved drastically. Therefore, by conceiving innovative TES concepts the deployment of CSP technology will be accelerated.

This paper presents a conceptual design of a CSP-LHTPV system targeting for energy storage and electricity generation at ultra-high temperatures. First, we describe the concept idea, and then we conduct a thermal assessment on the LHTES system as a core element of this concept. Operation at such temperatures provides higher efficiency ratios in TPV and LHTES systems, as they offer up to 10 times the storage capacity of molten salt-based storage. Through our analysis, we prove the system operability under targeted operating parameters and selected materials, addressing at the same time any challenges that might limit its efficiency, with the most critical ones being the thermal losses from the solar absorber and the LHTES sidewalls.

Fig. 1. CSP-LHTPV concept.

II. CONCEPT IDEA

The envisaged CSP-LHTPV system uses advanced beam-down concentration solar optics that collect the solar radiation and then distribute it to the modules by means of a flux splitter with adjustable mirrors. Each module contains (4) solar absorbers (charging system), (4) PCM crucibles (storage system) and (1) TPV converter (discharging system) in a compact design, which is replicable in order to construct the CSP-LHTPV concept through a bottom-up approach. The system is designed so that only its upper and bottom parts lose any thermal heat to the ambient. The rest of the surfaces re-radiate to each other through surface-to-surface radiation. Four operating modes are identified, two during daytime and two during night-time. **Mode A:** Simultaneous Charge/Discharge (Daytime). Solar radiation is heating through the absorber the crucibles sidewalls (charging), whereas the TPV is patched to the system, producing power simultaneously (discharging). This mode involves additional losses from the solar aperture to the ambient. **Mode B:** Charge-only (Daytime). The system is charged likewise Mode A, but the TPV is dispatched (OFF). As in Mode A, additional losses originate from the solar aperture. A thermal insulation cover is placed on top of the TPV to avoid excess heat losses from the crucible sidewalls towards the hollow area left by the TPV removal. **Mode C:** Discharge-only (Night-time). The heat in the crucibles is being discharged through the TPV, whereas the crucibles are retracted from the solar apertures to avoid re-emission losses. **Mode D:** Storage-only (Night-time). The TPV is OFF and the system acts as a storage system. In this mode, the insulating method plays a key role on how much time the system will sustain its energy.

TABLE I: SUMMARY OF STUDIED CASES (BLUE: DEVIATION FROM ADIABATIC CONDITIONS LESS THAN 10 %)

Insulating Method		Charging			Discharging		Charging-Discharging		Storage
Name	$R_{th, 1200}^{\circ C}$ [m ² K/ W]	t_{charge} [h] / dev	Q_{loss}/Q_{in} [-]	η (%)	$t_{discharge}$ [h] / dev	Q_{loss}/Q_{TPV} [-]	t [h] / dev	Q_{loss}/Q_{in} [-]	$t_{storage}$ [h]
Adiabatic-Ideal	∞	0.89	-	100	-	-	1.35	-	-
Adiabatic	∞	1.20 / 0 %	-	68.54	3.84 / 0 %	0	2.30 / 0 %	-	-
GFM:2 cm	0.092	1.34/ 12 %	0.1	61.37	3.12/ 18.61 %	0.27	3.71/ 61 %	0.102	11.14
GFM:6 cm	0.276	1.27/ 6 %	0.056	64.71	3.38/ 12.07 %	0.15	2.62/ 14 %	0.055	19.84
GFM:10 cm	0.460	1.25 / 4 %	0.048	65.41	3.43 / 10.64 %	0.12	2.59 / 13 %	0.046	24.04
GFM:8 cm-FSB: 2 cm	0.660	1.24 / 3 %	0.043	65.76	3.46 / 9.86 %	0.11	2.47 / 7 %	0.042	27.09
GFM:6 cm-FSB: 4 cm	0.850	1.24/3 %	0.041	65.93	3.48/ 9.34 %	0.10	2.45/ 7 %	0.040	28.81

$t_{charge}/ t_{discharge}$: phase changing time. dev : Deviation from "adiabatic conditions"

$t_{storage}$: time needed before the system loses its stored latent heat (~6.88 MJ) plus a small share of sensible heat ~0.6 MJ

Q_{loss} : LHTES system losses, Q_{in} : Incoming thermal flux to the LHTES system, η : overall efficiency $(Q_{in}-Q_{loss})/Q_{in,ideal}$

III. LHTES SYSTEM THERMAL ASSESSMENT

The CFD model used to simulate the phase changing process has been already validated in [1]. In this method, the PCM (FeSiB alloy) liquid fraction (LFR) varies from 0 (solid) to 1 (liquid) during phase change. Appropriate boundary conditions are set at the crucible (graphite) faces based on the operating mode simulated to consider system losses. In Modes A & B, the domain is sub-cooled 100 °C below the melting point (onset) of FeSiB alloy ($T_0=1122$ °C). In modes C & D, the domain patched 100 °C over the melting point (end point) ($T_0=1349$ °C).

efficiency reduces accordingly. Notably, the incoming power per module is almost equal to ~5 kW per solar aperture, under realistic conditions, meeting one of the desirable KPIs. **Mode C:** Under adiabatic conditions, the KPI of discharging 4 hours is almost met (~3.84 h). Applying a thermal insulation of $R_{th}>0.46$ m²K/W will reduce substantially the induced losses and improve the system discharging time (Fig. 2b). The same applies for **Mode D**, for which for $R_{th}>0.46$ m²K/W the system storage capacity can reach over 24 hours (Table I).

IV. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Fig. 2. a. Charging efficiency and b. Charging/Discharging rates.

Mode A/B: It has been revealed that the losses originating from the solar aperture determine most the system storage efficiency than those in the LHTES upper/bottom part (Fig. 2a). Even under adiabatic conditions (purple line), as the system temperature increases, the storage efficiency decreases drastically from 80% at the beginning of the charging phase (~1122 °C) to less than 60 %, when the PCM is completely melted. As the temperature increases more, the charging

V. CONCLUSIONS

This work has assessed a CSP-LHTES concept, currently being developed within the framework of SUNSON Project. It has been demonstrated that the proposed concept complies with several targeted KPIs, including the operating temperature (~1250 °C), incoming power per module (~5 kW per solar aperture, under realistic conditions), and, predicted charging/ discharging times (~1 h charging and ~ 4 h discharging), when an appropriate insulation method is applied (with a thermal resistance of at least ~0.46 m²K/W). Furthermore, it has been demonstrated that for the specific design and materials selected the insulating method affects more Modes A, C and D. Even still, during Mode A and B the lateral heat losses play a less important role if to be compared with the solar aperture losses.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

SUNSON project has received funding from Horizon Europe Research and Innovation Action programme under Grant Agreement n° 101083827. Funded by the European Union.

REFERENCES

[1] Zeneli, M., et al., Numerical simulation of a silicon-based latent heat thermal energy storage system operating at ultra-high temperatures. Applied Energy, 2019. 242: p. 837-85

Metallic phase change materials for high temperature applications

Paolo Lai Zhong Lo Biundo¹, Wojciech Polkowski¹, Jian Meng Jiao¹, Maria Wallin¹, Merete Tangstad¹

¹ Department of Materials Science and Engineering, Norwegian University of Science and Technology, Alfred Getz vei 2, 7491, Trondheim, Norway

Abstract — The advancement on latent heat thermal energy storage (LHTES) has led to the development of heat-to-electricity converters able to benefit from very high temperatures. Consequently, there is a pressing need to develop phase change materials (PCMs) that are compatible with these demanding operating conditions. This study aims to address this demand by conducting a comprehensive screening of metal-based PCMs with temperatures exceeding 1000°C for LHTES that applicable to concentrated solar power (CSP) plants. The investigation was carried out in two steps, initially leveraging simulations with FactSage to narrow down potential candidates, followed by experimental evaluations to validate their suitability for the intended application. Starting from Fe, Si, Mn, Cr, B, Ti, Ni, V, the candidates were narrowed to the FeSiB, FeSiCr and FeSiMn systems. Of these systems, some compositions were characterized by DSC and other techniques to predict their performance as PCMs.

I. INTRODUCTION

Latent Heat Thermal Energy Storage (LHTES) systems offer a promising solution for providing transient storage to support energy production from intermittent sources. The stability provided by TES solutions could facilitate greater integration of renewables such solar and wind energy into the power grid [1], [2].

The core of LHTES are a phase change material (PCM) that stores the energy in its phase transition and the heat-to-electricity converter. More often than not, the PCM works exploiting the solid-liquid transition.

Different authors have tried to define a set of desired and require properties for a PCM[3], [4], [5], [6]:

- Ensuring melting and freezing points fall within the designated operational temperature range;
- Maximizing latent heat per unit volume to enhance energy density and minimize the energy storage unit's size;
- Facilitating high thermal conductivity to mitigate significant thermal gradients and facilitate efficient heat transfer;
- Maintaining congruent melting or eutectic composition to work in a defined temperature range and prevent segregation during operation, which may result in localized chemical variations;
- Minimizing volume changes during phase transition;
- Achieving low supercooling during freezing, ideally aligning with the thermodynamic freezing point;

- Ensuring chemical stability throughout operational cycles;
- Maintaining low corrosiveness towards the containment vessel;
- Prioritizing availability and affordability;
- Ideally, being non-toxic and non-flammable.

This work will investigate new PCM possibilities focusing on metallic system including Fe, Si, Mn, Cr, B, Ti, Ni, V, aiming to find alloys with working temperature above 1000°C.

II. MATERIALS AND METHOD

A. FactSage simulation

Simulation of binary, ternary and quaternary systems containing Fe, Si, Mn, Cr, B, Ti, Ni, V were done using FactSage 8.2.

The target properties in this initial selection phase are:

- Liquidus above 1000°C
- Difference between solidus and liquidus (ΔT) < 50°C
- Volumetric enthalpy in the working temperature range above 1 MWh/m^3

The third requirement was defined arbitrarily as the heat exchanged in a temperature range of 100°C to take into account the ΔT defined in (ii) and undercooling, resembling a plausible usage thermocycling. This was modeled assuming a constant specific heat for each system, derived from the specific heat of an alloy with equal weight fractions of the components at 1000°C. For example, in the FeSiB system, the C_p value was obtained from the Factsage simulation of 33.3 wt% Fe, 33.3 wt% Si, and 33.4 wt% B at 1000°C. While this approach is a rough approximation, it remains reasonable as long as the sensible heat is significantly smaller than the latent heat.

B. Raw materials and alloy production

The alloys were produced with arc-melter, a small scale production (1 gram per sample) technique that exploits a plasma arc with extremely high temperatures up to 3500 °C to melt and mix the raw materials.

The alloys were produced from 99.99% pure elements provided by Thermo Fisher Scientific using the arc melter under inert (argon) atmosphere.

C. Characterization of the samples

The samples are then crushed and analyzed with differential scanning calorimetry (DSC) to experimentally verify the working temperature and the latent heat. The measurement was carried with a Netsch STA 449 F3 Jupiter under argon atmosphere, using boron nitride (BN) coated alumina crucibles. This method was successfully tested for pure Si [7], [8], [9].

ACKNOWLEDGEMENT

SUNSON project has received funding from Horizon Europe Research and Innovation Action programme under Grant Agreement no 101083827, funded by the European Union. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or CINEA. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

REFERENCES

- [1] I. Sarbu and C. Sebarchievici, "A Comprehensive Review of Thermal Energy Storage," *Sustainability*, vol. 10, no. 1, Art. no. 1, Jan. 2018, doi: 10.3390/su10010191.
- [2] Y. Qin, M. Ghalambaz, M. Sheremet, M. Fteiti, and F. Alresheedi, "A bibliometrics study of phase change materials (PCMs)," *J. Energy Storage*, vol. 73, p. 108987, Dec. 2023, doi: 10.1016/j.est.2023.108987.
- [3] M. Liu, W. Saman, and F. Bruno, "Review on storage materials and thermal performance enhancement techniques for high temperature phase change thermal storage systems," *Renew. Sustain. Energy Rev.*, vol. 16, no. 4, pp. 2118–2132, May 2012, doi: 10.1016/j.rser.2012.01.020.
- [4] M. M. Kenisarin, "High-temperature phase change materials for thermal energy storage," *Renew. Sustain. Energy Rev.*, vol. 14, no. 3, pp. 955–970, Apr. 2010, doi: 10.1016/j.rser.2009.11.011.
- [5] A. Abhat, "Low temperature latent heat thermal energy storage: Heat storage materials," *Sol. Energy*, vol. 30, no. 4, pp. 313–332, Jan. 1983, doi: 10.1016/0038-092X(83)90186-X.
- [6] J. Schröder and K. Gawron, "Latent heat storage," *Int. J. Energy Res.*, vol. 5, no. 2, pp. 103–109, 1981, doi: 10.1002/er.4440050202.
- [7] M. Homa and N. Sobczak, "Measurements of temperature and heat of phase transformation of pure silicon by using differential scanning calorimetry," *J. Therm. Anal. Calorim.*, vol. 138, no. 6, pp. 4215–4221, Dec. 2019, doi: 10.1007/s10973-019-08716-5.
- [8] W. Polkowski, N. Sobczak, A. Polkowska, G. Bruzda, A. Kudyba, and D. Giuranno, "Silicon as a Phase Change Material: Performance of h-BN Ceramic During Multi-Cycle Melting/Solidification of Silicon," *JOM*, vol. 71, no. 4, pp. 1492–1498, Apr. 2019, doi: 10.1007/s11837-019-03364-4.
- [9] W. Polkowski *et al.*, "Wetting Behavior and Reactivity of Molten Silicon with h-BN Substrate at Ultrahigh Temperatures up to 1750 °C," *J. Mater. Eng. Perform.*, vol. 27, no. 10, pp. 5040–5053, Oct. 2018, doi: 10.1007/s11665-017-3114-8.

Competitive Analysis for Silbat’s LDES Technology

Rishabh Golchha and Ignacio Luque-Heredia

Silbat Energy Storage Solutions SL, Av. del Dr. Federico Rubio y Galí, 75, ES28040 Madrid

This paper compares existing storage technologies with the Silbat battery based on the levelized cost of storage (LCOS). The analysis includes charge-discharge cycles per year and storage duration at rated power. The Silbat battery emerges as a dominant technology for applications requiring over 8 hours of duration, outperforming current leaders like Pumped Hydro Storage (PHS) and H2 solutions. A sensitivity analysis of Silbat's parameters shows its leading LCOS position remains unchallenged within informed bounds, reinforcing its suitability for long-duration energy storage applications.

I. INTRODUCTION

IRENA predicts that the global deployment of energy storage will increase by two to three times from 2017 to 2030, with a major part of this increase expected to come from Concentrated Solar Power (CSP) and batteries in Electric Vehicles (EVs) while PHS, the dominant technology so far, will have a slight increase [1]. Most existing storage technologies are geographically limited or expensive, especially for Long Duration Energy Storage (LDES). Hence, there is a need for economic, scalable LDES technology.

To address this need, Silbat has developed a Thermo-Electric Energy Storage System (TEES) based technology which uses Silicon to store energy. When input electricity is provided, it is converted into heat through Joule heating, melting Silicon at its melting point of 1410°C and storing energy in latent heat at a constant temperature. When the battery needs to be discharged, radiation from hot molten Silicon strikes the Thermo-Photovoltaic (TPV) modules, which convert this to electricity. The working principle can be seen in Fig. 1

Fig. 1. A refractory vessel kept at the melting temperature of silicon contains a coalescent mix of solid and liquid Silicon. The battery is fully charged when all the Silicon is molten and turns liquid and fully discharged when all its latent heat of fusion is extracted through the TPV and the Silicon is fully frozen.

The main advantages of the Silbat battery are:

- Extremely cheap (<\$10/kWh)
- 30 years lifetime with low O&M
- Uses abundantly found raw materials.
- High energy density
- Silent operation & quick start

The present paper evaluates the Silbat battery's LCOS and compares it with existing storage technologies.

II. METHODOLOGY

Schmidt et al. [2]-[3] analyzed different energy storage technologies across various storage applications in terms of the LCOS. The four contributing factors for LCOS are:

- $CAPEX = P * CAPEX_p + d * P * CAPEX_E$
- $OPEX = P * OPEX_{fixed} + d * P * OPEX_{var} * (cyc_{pa} * DoD) * (1 - cyc_{deg})^{(n-1)cyc_{pa}} (1 - T_{deg})^{n-1}$
- $Replacement\ Cost = \sum_{r=1}^R \frac{C_{p-r}P}{(1+r)^{T_c+rep*Tr}}$
- The charging cost is given as $\frac{P_{el}}{\eta}$

$$LCOS = \frac{CAPEX + \sum_n \frac{OPEX}{(1+r)^n} + Replacement\ Cost}{\sum_n \frac{Electricity\ Discharged}{(1+r)^n}} + \frac{P_{el}}{\eta}$$

The analysis is done for a storage duration, d , ranging from 0.5 hrs. to 1024 hrs. and the maximum possible cycles/yr. is given by $\frac{8760}{2d}$. For each combination of storage duration and cycles/yr., the LCOS is calculated for each technology, and the minimum LCOS is determined along with the respective technology. For the Silbat battery, input parameters are shown in Table 1.

TABLE I
TECHNOLOGY INPUT PARAMETERS FOR THE SILBAT BATTERY

Technical parameters	Unit	Value
Investment cost - Power	\$/kW	171
Operation cost	\$/MWh	0.36
Round-trip efficiency	%	41%
Self-discharge	%/day	2.4%
Shelf life	years	20*

*Note: This analysis uses a shelf life of 20 years only. The actual expected lifetime for the Silbat battery is 30 years.

III. RESULTS

Fig. 2 shows the analysis results using existing technologies and the Silbat battery in the mix.

Fig. 2: LCOS of the most cost-efficient technology and the most cost-efficient technology for various discharge durations and cycles per year

As can be seen, the Silbat battery is the best technology for storage durations greater than 8 hours. Lithium-ion is a relatively close competitor of the Silbat battery in the region, with a storage duration of around 4-6 hours. Additionally, PHS can be leading in small areas because for long-duration storage, PHS becomes the second-best technology, and there are these small regions where it is still the best technology.

Fig.3: LCOS range across various cycles/yr for the year 2030

To compare the effect of Silbat battery on the LCOS, another analysis was done with existing technologies but without Silbat battery in the technology mix. The LCOS was compared with the previous case wherein Silbat battery was part of the technology mix. The results are shown in Fig. 3. As can be seen, there is a significant reduction in LCOS when the Silbat battery is in the technology mix.

III. SENSITIVITY ANALYSIS

Since the Silbat battery is still under development, the costs used for the analysis are based on projections. So, a sensitivity analysis was performed to analyze the effect of cost or performance variation. Some of the key conclusions of this analysis are:

- CAPEX increased by 25% and 50%: Silbat’s leading position only slightly decreased.
- OPEX increased by 30 and 85 times: The report by LDES council provides an expected range of OPEX for LDES technologies [4]. This range is 30 to 85 times the expected OPEX for Silbat. However, no significant change in Silbat’s dominant position was seen even when the OPEX was increased by 85 times.
- Reducing efficiency to 38% and 35%: The Silbat battery maintains its dominance at both efficiencies.

III. CONCLUSION

The present paper evaluates the range of applications for which storage technologies can be used. The methodology used by Schmidt et al [2]-[3] is adopted for this. Different storage technologies are compared using this methodology by taking a range of storage duration (0.25 hrs to 1024 hrs). For each case, the best technology is determined in terms of LCOS. It is seen that the Silbat battery dominates in the region of long-duration storage, typically for storage duration greater than 10 hours. Therefore, the Silbat battery would have a very favourable business case in various long-duration energy storage applications.

REFERENCES

[1] Global CO2 Emissions In 2019 – Analysis - IEA", IEA, 2019 <<https://www.iea.org/articles/global-co2-emissions-in-2019>> [Accessed 26 August 2021].

[2] Oliver Schmidt and others, "Projecting the Future Levelized Cost of Electricity Storage Technologies", *Joule*, 3.1 (2019), 81-100 <<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.joule.2018.12.008>>.

[3] Oliver Schmidt and Iain Staffell, "Monetizing Energy Storage: a toolkit to assess future cost and value", Oxford, 2023, <DOI: 10.1093/oso/9780192888174.001.0001>

[4] LDES Council, McKinsey & Company, *Net-Zero Power – Long Duration Energy Storage for A Renewable Grid*, 2021 <<https://www.ldescouncil.com/publication>> [Accessed 8 January 2022]

Multiphysics Modelling of an Ultra-High Temperature Storage integrated in the SUNSON-BOX Solar-To-Heat-To-Power system

Alfonso Hernández^{1,*}, Ignacio Fernández-Pacheco¹, Luis Enrique Acevedo¹, Patricia Royo¹

¹ IDENER, Thermodynamics Division, Earle Ovington 8-9, Edificio Aeronautics Suppliers Village, Parque Tecnológico Aeroespacial de Andalucía, La Rinconada, Sevilla, 41300, Spain

*Corresponding author. Email: alfonso.hernandez@idener.ai

Abstract — The design modelled in the present work incorporates concentrated solar power (CSP) into a compact ultra-high temperature latent heat thermal energy storage (UHT-LHTES) system. This Solar-to-Heat-to-Power (S2H2P) system utilizes Phase Change Materials (PCM) as core storage and a solid-state generator based on Thermophotovoltaic (TPV) cells. Operation at ultra-high temperature levels (over 1200°C) enables a significantly more compact compared to traditional CSP storage. This solution aligns with the European strategy's emphasis on the flexibility and dispatchability of renewable energy sources (RES). COMSOL Multiphysics® supports a multiphysics coupling to understand the influence of the key parameters of the system design and materials on the overall performance. The design model is a useful tool to strongly endorse the choice of optimal materials and design configurations. Results revealed the expected thermal cycling periods, temperature mapping, energy and power outputs and system efficiencies. This is the first time that a groundbreaking design of this nature has been simulated using a comprehensive multiphysics model for all the components of a revolutionary S2H2P system.

I. INTRODUCTION

Energy storage facilitates the integration of renewable energy sources (RES), bolsters system flexibility, and guarantees a reliable energy supply, thereby decreasing reliance on gas power plants [1]. The combination of concentrated solar power (CSP) and thermal energy storage (TES) presents a potentially effective resolution to the issue of intermittent RES availability. TES systems have the potential to offer dispatchability in the absence or reduction of sunlight. In addition, the potential electric energy densities achieved through integrating TES with energy converters, such as thermophotovoltaic (TPV) cells, are on par with the highest-quality lithium-ion batteries [2]. Ultra-high temperature latent heat storage (UHT-LHTES) provides enhanced energy densities and improved operational efficiency, implying increased system adaptability and dispatchability [3]. However, its applications remain limited due to significant technological challenges posed by extreme conditions (corrosiveness, scarcity, low availability, thermal expansion, and sustainability implications) that risk its implementation [4].

The innovative design of a Solar-to-Heat-to-Power (S2H2P) system is the SUNSON initiative's foundation [5]. The project proposes the holistic integration of CSP, TPV, and UHT-LHTES with novel phase change materials (PCM) alloys that

operate over 1200°C. Particularly, systems capitalise on the higher melting points of inorganic substances, e.g., silicon, iron, and boron. However, the selection process for PCMs and the design configuration necessitates a detailed assessment of their properties and influence on the overall system performance. The proposed work moves one step beyond the current state-of-the-art simulations by formulating a comprehensive model that considers usually neglected mechanisms such as natural convection and radiative heat transfer [6]. This allows a better comprehension of the complex thermal, material, and electrical system interactions, particularly at high temperatures.

II. SIMULATION MODELLING

The proposed multiphysics model integrates comprehensive computational fluid dynamics (CFD) and accounts for all heat transfer mechanisms (including surface-to-surface radiation) and natural convection inside the liquid phase of the PCM [7]. COMSOL® 6.2 is used to simulate the system's performance, thereby advancing comprehension and progress of the system. The geometry is simplified using a 3D doubly symmetric simulation. Physics interfaces are configured as laminar flow to describe the fluid motion in the PCM domain (while velocity equals zero in the solid state). The solid-to-liquid transition is defined by a mushy zone resembling a porous material [8]. The Boussinesq approximation addresses natural convection inside the PCM domain as an incompressible fluid, simulating flows driven by buoyancy [9]. The model for the electricity generated by the TPV uses conversion efficiency as a function of the emitter temperature [3]. The method and equations are detailed in reference [10].

The system's structure is embedded within a metal container. The space between the components is filled with multiple thermal insulation layers for high-temperature operation, such as graphite fibre mat or fumed silica board. The system's uppermost part contains the CSP absorbers that provide solar input to the PCM. The crucible (made of silicon carbide and graphite) holds the PCM alloy and transfers heat to and from it. The system's TPV device converts thermal energy into electricity, and the crucible is placed near it for efficient thermal transfer. Insulation in the system's outer wall reduces heat loss.

Key S2H2P system indicator		PCM properties	
Solar input power	47 kW	Volume	0.0124 m ³
Solar irradiance at the aperture	1.2 MW/m ²	Density	2976 kg/m ³
Insulation thermal conductivity	0.05 W/(m·K)	Thermal conductivity @ 20°C	100.67 W/(m·K)
Crucible thermal conductivity	1 W/(m·K)	Latent heat capacity	1669 kJ/kg
TPV cells' power density (dependent on temperature)	~1 W _{el} /cm ²	Sensible heat capacity	1.20 kJ/(kg·K)
TPV cells' surface	100 cm ²	Melting point and range	1340 °C and 60 °C

Table 1 shows the main specifications and PCM properties to simulate the system.

III. ANALYSIS OF RESULTS

Fig. 1 shows the PCM melt fraction, temperature distribution, and velocity distribution in three different time steps during the charging cycle. The PCM starts to melt from the side near the heat source. After enough material melts, natural convection causes the PCM to melt from higher to lower layers. Whirls, which indicate natural convection, arise when buoyancy fluctuates due to the change in the material's temperature.

Fig. 1. PCM temperature mapping (right legend, °C), melt fraction (left legend, 0-solid 1-liquid) and velocity field (arrows).

Fig. 2 illustrates the PCM's liberated thermal energy and the electrical energy produced by the TPV cell over time in a discharge cycle. The primary cause of the linear rise in the liberated thermal energy is the latent heat of fusion, which is dominant over the sensible heat contribution. Conversely, the occurrence of the accumulated thermal energy plateau can be attributed to the completion of the PCM's solidification.

Fig. 2. Energy performance of the S2H2P-UHTES system.

IV. CONCLUSIONS AND DISCUSSION

The SUNSON project involves a novel S2H2P system combining UHT-LHTES and CSP as critical technologies to

transition to sustainable energy. The simulation multiphysics model addresses potential design challenges early on, allowing the analysis of behaviour indicators to improve the system performance, focusing on generation efficiencies. The expected results achieved solar-to-thermal conversion efficiencies >45% and thermal-to-electric conversion efficiencies >15%. The simulations showed that the PCM's high operation temperature (1300-1460°C) implies an efficient thermal energy transfer to the TPV generator, increasing electrical output power up to 250 W. Thermal cycle is 0.87 h for charging (with an energy storage capacity of near 20 kWh_{th}) and 3 h for discharging (with an electricity production of around 0.4 kWh_{el}). Thus, the selected PCM (1669 kJ/kg latent storage capacity and melting point at 1340°C) was proven to offer a great performance. Still, further technical and non-technical criteria (non-harmful materials, economic factors) should be considered in system suitability.

REFERENCES

- [1] European Commission – “REPowerEU Plan - EUR-Lex 52022DC0230”, accessed online: abr. 2024. available link, may. 2022.
- [2] T. Burger et al., “Present Efficiencies and Future Opportunities in TPV,” *Joule*, vol.4-8, aug. 2020, doi: 10.1016/J.JOULE.2020.06.021.
- [3] A. Datas et al., “Ultra high temperature latent heat energy storage and thermophotovoltaic energy conversion,” *Energy*, vol. 107, pp. 542–549, Jul. 2016, doi: 10.1016/J.ENERGY.2016.04.048
- [4] P. Royo et al., “High-temperature PCM-based TES for industrial furnaces installed in energy-intensive industries,” *Energy*, vol. 173, pp. 1030–1040, apr. 2019, doi: 10.1016/J.ENERGY.2019.02.118.
- [5] SUNSON Project GA ID: 101083827 “Concentrated Solar energy storage at Ultra-high temperatures aNd Solid-state cONversion”, from Horizon Europe Programme, DOI 10.3030/101083827
- [6] M. Zeneli et al., “Numerical simulation of a silicon-based LHTES system operating at UHT,” *Appl Energy*, vol. 242, pp. 837–853, May 2019, doi: 10.1016/J.APENERGY.2019.03.147.
- [7] COMSOL®, “The Heat Transfer Module User’s Guide,” 2022, Accessed: Sep. 27, 2023. Available Online: www.comsol.com/blogs
- [8] V. R. Voller et al., “A fixed grid numerical methodology for convection-diffusion mushy region problems,” *Int J Heat Mass Transf*, vol. 30- 8, aug. 1987, doi: 10.1016/0017-9310(87)90317-6.
- [9] COMSOL®, “The CFD Module User’s Guide,” 2022, Accessed: Sep. 27, 2023. Available Online: www.comsol.com/blogs.
- [10] A. Hernández et al. ‘Multiphysics Optimisation Model of a UHTES with a Novel S2H2P system. IRES Conf. Proceedings, 2024:

ACKNOWLEDGEMENT

SUNSON project has received funding from Horizon Europe Research and Innovation Action programme under Grant Agreement n° 101083827. Funded by the European Union.

Environmental footprint of a latent heat thermophotovoltaic system for long duration high density electrical and thermal energy storage

Diego Ruiz^a, Guillermo San Miguel^{*a}, Rafael Molinero^b, Alejandro Benito^b, Ignacio Luque-Heredia^b

^aDepartament of Chemical and Environmental Engineering, ETSII, Universidad Politécnica de Madrid, C. de José Gutiérrez Abascal, 2, ES28006 Madrid;

^bSilbat Energy Storage Solutions, SL, Av. del Dr. Federico Rubio y Galí, 75, ES28040 Madrid.
(* g.sanmiguel@upm.es)

Abstract — Electricity storage systems are essential to facilitate the transition to a decarbonized and sustainable economy. Latent heat thermophotovoltaic (LHTPV) storage based on pure silicon is emerging as a low-cost utility-scale technology capable of meeting the needs of an electricity system increasingly reliant on intermittent renewable technologies. This research based on life-cycle analysis (LCA) methodology describes that this technology exhibits a very small environmental footprint when operating in cogeneration mode (involving the recovery of thermal heat), with an estimated 8.2 kg CO₂ eq./MWh in climate change and similarly low impacts in other categories such as ozone depletion, particulate matter formation and depletion of mineral resources. Most of the carbon footprint is attributable to silicon while using this metalloid does not affect other categories, such as depletion of mineral resources due to its abundance. Reusing and recycling materials provide substantial environmental credits.

I. INTRODUCTION

As countries move away from fossil fuels towards a decarbonized energy system, the global electricity demand is projected to grow 125% from 2020 to 2050, most of which (85%) will be sourced from intermittent Renewable Energy (REN) resources, primarily solar and wind. To enable this transition and guarantee future energy markets' flexibility, stability and reliability, global grid-scale stationary battery storage capacity needs to increase from the current 28 GW to 967 GW in 2030 (IEA, 2024).

In this context, a range of novel stationary Electrical Energy Storage (EES) technologies are being designed and tested, varying largely in terms of scale, capacity, investment cost, flexibility, portability, etc. One of the most promising is latent heat thermophotovoltaic (LHTPV) batteries, which rely on the use of phase change materials (PCMs) as storage media and electricity extraction through photovoltaic systems operating in the infrared (IR) spectrum. LHTPV batteries based on pure silicon operate at temperatures above 1400 °C and benefit from this metalloid's extremely high volumetric latent heat (1154 kWh/m³). Techno-economic analyses have reported that these systems would potentially benefit from very low levelized costs

(<0.15€/kWh), particularly in long-duration and cogeneration applications (Datas et al., 2022).

Selecting the most suitable energy storage systems for this energy transition requires considering their technical and economic performance and their environmental implications. Various publications describe marked differences in the environmental footprint of energy storage systems calculated using a life cycle approach, depending on their nature (electrochemical, electrical, mechanical, thermal storage), design, scale, input and output energy form, etc. (Lechón et al., 2023). Thus, carbon footprint values reported for conventional technologies ranged 1-6 kg CO₂ eq/MWh for pumped storage, 77-110 kg CO₂ eq/MWh for lead acid batteries and 20-82 kg CO₂ eq/MWh for lithium-ion batteries. Thermal storage in Concentrated Solar Power (CSP) using sensible and latent heat has been calculated at between 1-30 kg CO₂ eq/MWh (Thaker et al., 2019). This work aims to quantify the environmental footprint of an LHTPV battery based on molten silicon from primary inventories provided by a company dedicated to its design and development.

II. MATERIALS AND METHODS

A. Goal and scope definition

The LCA was carried out according to ISO 14040: 2006 and the Product Category Rule PCR 2007:08 for "Electricity, steam and hot/cold water generation and distribution" put forward by the International EPD® System. The functional unit was 1 MWh, and the life cycle impact assessment methodology was EF 3.1, as endorsed by the European Commission. Due to space limitations, the analysis covered only four environmental categories: climate change - total (CC-T), ozone depletion (OD), particulate matter formation (PM) and Resource use, minerals and metals (RU-M).

The life cycle stages considered included extraction of raw materials, fabrication of battery components, and end-of-life (benefits beyond system boundaries of reuse and recycling). The battery components considered in the inventory included external containers, crucibles, heaters, insulators, MG-Si, TPV Equipment, and TPV Modules.

The LCA assumed the operation of the LHTPV battery in cogeneration mode, where both electricity and heat are recovered according to the efficiencies shown in Table 1. The allocation criteria followed that put forward in PCR 2007:08, considering the harmonized efficiency reference values for heat and power generation for lignite fuel reported in the Commission Delegated Regulation (EU) 2015/ 2402, yielding an allocation factor for electricity of 59.6%.

B. Life cycle inventory

Silbat Energy Storage Solutions SL provided primary inventory data and information about the battery's baseline operating scenario, while secondary background data was sourced from Ecoinvent v.3.9. Table 1 provides additional technical information about the LHTPV system's operating characteristics.

Table 1. Operating characteristics of the LHTPV battery.

Silicon in battery	25,650	kg
Fusion energy Si	0.497	KWh/kg
Battery electrical efficiency	42.5%	%
Battery thermal efficiency	57.5%	%
Electrical energy delivered/cycle	5.418	MWh
Thermal energy delivered/cycle	7.330	MWh
Cycles	84	cycles/year
Lifetime	20	years
Total electrical energy delivered per battery	9,102	MWh
Total thermal energy delivered per battery	12,315	MWh

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

C. Life cycle assessment

Table 2 shows a carbon footprint for the LHTPV battery of 8.2 kg CO₂ eq./MWh, a value significantly lower than that reported for utility-scale batteries based on lead acid or lithium-ion technologies. Figure 1 shows that most of this impact comes from the silicon used as PCM. The contribution of this material is similarly high in the other impact categories except for resource use (minerals and metals), which is dominated by the container (from steel) and TPV module (from use of silver and other critical metals).

Table 2. Environmental impacts per MWh generated by the LHTPV battery operating in cogeneration mode

Impact category	Units	Raw materials and fabrication	End of life (recycling and reuse)	TOTAL
Climate change	kg CO ₂ eq	24.2	-15.9	8.2
Ozone depletion	kg CFC11 eq	1.59E-06	-1.09E-06	4.98E-07
Particulate matter disease inc.		1.10E-06	-4.43E-07	6.53E-07
Resource use, minerals	kg Sb eq	2.16E-03	-4.68E-05	2.11E-03

Figure 1. Contribution of components to the environmental footprint of silicon-based LHTPV battery

The results also evidence notable environmental benefits associated with the reuse of silicon and recycling other materials (mainly steel) employed in the LHTPV battery.

IV. CONCLUSIONS

The carbon footprint of a silicon LHTPV battery operating in cogeneration mode was estimated at 8.2 kg CO₂ eq./MWh, 77.1% of which derives from the silicon. Reuse and recycling of materials are essential to ensure a low environmental footprint of this type of energy storage device.

REFERENCES

- Datas, A., López-Ceballos, A., López, E., Ramos, A., del Cañizo, C., 2022. Latent heat thermophotovoltaic batteries. *Joule* 6, 418–443. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.joule.2022.01.010>
- IEA, 2024. Grid-scale Storage. International Energy Agency (IEA) [WWW Document]. URL <https://www.iea.org/energy-system/electricity/grid-scale-storage> (accessed 4.20.24).
- Lechón, Y., Lago, C., Herrera, I., Gamarra, A.R., Pérula, A., 2023. Carbon benefits of different energy storage alternative end uses. Application to the Spanish case. *Renew. Sustain. Energy Rev.* 171. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.rser.2022.112985>
- Thaker, S., Oni, A.O., Gemechu, E., Kumar, A., 2019. Evaluating energy and greenhouse gas emission footprints of thermal energy storage systems for concentrated solar power applications. *J. Energy Storage* 26, 100992. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.est.2019.100992>

Coupling of Concentrated Solar Power into an Ultra-High Temperature Latent Heat Thermal Energy Storage System

Thorsten Denk, Aurelio González-Pardo, Alfonso Vidal

Ciemat – Plataforma Solar de Almería, Ctra de Senés, km4.5, 04200, Tabernas, Spain

Abstract — The present work shows how to couple concentrated solar power (CSP) into a compact ultra-high temperature latent heat thermal energy storage (UHT-LHTES) system. This Solar-to-Heat-to-Power (S2H2P) system utilizes Phase Change Materials (PCM) as storage and a solid-state electricity generator based on Thermophotovoltaic (TPV) cells. Operation at ultra-high temperature levels (over 1200°C) enables a significantly more compact design compared to traditional CSP storage. Due to the requirements of UHT-LHTES in terms of size and orientation of the recipients (crucibles) for the phase change material (PCM), special optical elements are required to introduce the highly concentrated solar radiation into the storage material. In this work, the basics of CSP are presented, followed by the special solutions needed for coupling with UHT-LHTES / TPV systems.

I. INTRODUCTION

Like any storage system, ultra-high temperature latent heat thermal energy storage (UHT-LHTES) needs a charge and a discharge system. For discharge, thermophotovoltaics (TPV) is an interesting choice, because it avoids the complexity of thermodynamic cycles with all the associated subsystems like pumps, turbines, valves, heat-exchangers, heat transfer fluids, and so on. For charging, an energy source is needed that is free from greenhouse gas emissions. The straightforward solution is electrical heaters powered by conventional photovoltaics and/or wind power. But there exist other possibilities. *Concentrated solar power (CSP)* is able to convert solar radiation directly into heat without the intermediate step of electricity. Therefore, CSP might be an interesting choice for

powering a high temperature heat storage system with TPV. The main problem to be solved there is how to bring the concentrated solar radiation in good contact with the storage medium avoiding excessive thermal and radiative losses.

II. CONCENTRATED SOLAR POWER

On a sunny day, solar radiation hits the ground with a flux density of up to 1000 W/m². This is nice at the beach, but far too low for any thermal application beyond 120°C. Curved mirrors can be used to increase the solar flux. For temperatures up to 400°C, line-concentrating systems (solar troughs) are the commonly used technology. But for applications well beyond, only point concentrating systems are suitable.

A. Small experimental systems

At small scale (from a few up to 100 kW), *parabolic dishes* and *solar furnaces* [1] are the typical technology. They both include as the central component one large, paraboloid-shaped concentrator. In dish systems, this concentrator is mounted on a two-axis tracking system, following directly the sun. In a solar furnace, the concentrator is put fixed on the ground, often within a building. In most cases, the optical axis is oriented horizontally, facing north (on the northern hemisphere). In front of the building, a flat, large, sun-tracking mirror (*heliostat*) is redirecting the solar radiation onto the optical axis of the concentrator. In both cases (dish and furnace), the so-called

Fig. 1. 7 MW Solar Tower System at the Plataforma Solar de Almería for the generation of high-temperature heat.

receiver is located in the focus of the concentrator. The receiver is the component that absorbs the highly concentrated solar radiation and converts it into something more useful, in the majority of the cases heat.

The advantage of the dish systems is the high efficiency due to having only one reflection and because the concentrator is always oriented perpendicular to the direction to the sun (no cosine losses). In contrast, solar furnaces offer a non-moving and non-rotating focus throughout the whole day, as well as easy access to the focal area frequently inside a protective building.

B. Large systems in the megawatt range

When working with high temperature solar power in the megawatt range (from 0.1 MW up to 100 MW and more), *solar tower systems* or *central receiver systems* are used (Fig. 1). In these systems, a large quantity of sun-tracking heliostats (from 100 up to many 1000s) is located north or around a tower forming the heliostat field. Contrary to a solar furnace, the heliostats are slightly curved. Their reflected sunlight reaches the receiver on the top of the central tower, where the sunlight is converted into heat. This heat is usually carried away by a heat transfer fluid (HTF), like water/steam, atmospheric or pressurized air, or molten salt. It's also possible to use the receiver as a reactor for high temperature thermochemistry, e.g. for hydrogen production. A special design, the so-called *beam-down systems*, reflect the solar ray back from the top of the tower to the ground, offering much easier access to the receiver.

III. MODULAR SYSTEMS

When using concentrated solar power for high temperature thermal storage with TPV, some design requirements collide. From the side of the UHT-LHTES, the main constraints are:

1. Vertical orientation of the crucibles to avoid spilling of the liquid phase through the gap between the container and the lid.
2. Rather small size of each crucible in the range of a fraction of a meter, to prevent excessive limitation of the charging speed due to the low thermal conductivity of the PCM in the solid state.

On the other hand, solar concentrators provide a focal spot with dimensions in the order of several meters. To overcome this discrepancy, the receiver with the heat storage system can

be made highly modular. But this requires an additional optical component that has to “funnel” the solar radiation into every single module.

For small systems with a very low number of modules and a small focal spot, beam-splitters can be used for this. For a large number of modules, each module has to be equipped with a small, so-called *secondary concentrator*. These devices resemble a funnel with mirrors at the inside with a specially calculated shape (compound parabolic concentrator, CPC) [3] to maximize the throughput of the concentrated solar radiation. Depending on details of the primary concentrating system, they can provide an additional concentration in the order of 4x – 10x, in the case of beam-down systems even more.

Receivers on the top of a tower are normally inclined downwards to “see” the heliostat field. For UHT-LHTES systems, however, a vertical ray from the top is preferred to avoid the spilling problem. In a solar furnace, this can be provided by a redirection or diagonal mirror close to the focal area. In a tower system, a possible solution is to use the beam-down concept, with the additional advantage that the receiver with the crucibles and the TPV is now located on the ground, providing much easier access for handling and maintenance.

IV. PLANNED EXPERIMENTAL WORK

The *SUNSON project* involves a novel S2H2P system combining UHT-LHTES and CSP as critical technologies to transition to sustainable energy. It will demonstrate the parallel operation at >1200°C of four modules including UHT-LHTES and TPV in a solar furnace with a beam splitter providing four vertical rays.

REFERENCES

- [1] J. Rodriguez, I. Cañadas, E. Zarza, “New PSA high concentration solar furnace SF40”. AIP Conference Proceedings 1734, 070028 (2016); doi: 10.1063/1.4949175
- [2] R. Buck, T. Bräuning, T. Denk, M. Pfänder, P. Schwarzbözl, F. Tellez, “Solar-Hybrid Gas Turbine-Based Power Tower Systems (REFOS)”, J. Solar Energy Engineering, 124, 2-9 2002

ACKNOWLEDGEMENT

SUNSON project has received funding from Horizon Europe Research and Innovation Action programme under Grant Agreement n° 101083827. Funded by the European Union..

Laboratory-Scale Prototype of Thermal Energy Grid Storage (TEGS) System

Kyle Buznitsky, Colin Kelsall, Shomik Verma, Alina LaPotin, Mehdi Pishahang, Asegun Henry

Department of Mechanical Engineering, Massachusetts Institute of Technology

Abstract — The thermal energy grid storage (TEGS) concept has been discussed as a low-cost, high-efficiency thermal energy storage system and involves a graphite sensible heat storage medium, liquid tin heat transfer fluid, and thermophotovoltaic heat engine, all capable of operating up to 2400°C. While each of these subsystems have been demonstrated to some extent in isolation, there exists no system which has combined these disparate components into a prototype. This work aims to fill this gap by constructing and testing a laboratory-scale prototype of the TEGS concept to uncover and solve system integration challenges, as well as match system performance to modeling to give confidence to commercial-scale system predictions.

I. INTRODUCTION

Much advancement has been made towards the individual components making up the thermal energy grid storage (TEGS) concept [1]: namely, the demonstration of high temperature liquid metal pumping [2] and high thermophotovoltaic (TPV) efficiency [3]. However, these developments have occurred in relative isolation and there exists no system containing both of these components interacting with a thermal storage medium to evaluate system-level performance and identify system integration challenges. It is the purpose of this work to design and test a laboratory-scale prototype of the TEGS system, including a molten tin pump and seals; graphite thermal energy storage medium; an actuatable TPV heat engine to extract electrical power from the system; and all accompanying subsystems such as resistance heaters. It is the goal to test such a system up to the desired peak operating temperature of 2400°C to demonstrate system performance, which can then be matched to model predictions and extrapolated to commercial-scale systems.

II. SYSTEM DESIGN

The designed prototype is made entirely of graphite or other carbon-based materials due to materials constraints, except for the tin used as the pumped heat transfer fluid. This design is shown below in Fig. 1:

Fig. 1. A) front, B) isometric, and C) section view rendering of TEGS prototype design CAD assembly.

The subsystems of interest here are the molten tin centrifugal pump and the TPV emitter and associated heat exchanger.

A. Centrifugal Pump

This work builds on past demonstrations of high temperature molten metal pumping. In this case, the pump casing and impeller are made primarily of graphite, which is required due to the high temperatures involved, necessity of no chemical interaction with tin, and cost at scale. However, such a pump is then subject to additional mechanical constraints due to the tendency of graphite to wear quickly and fail under only moderate tensile forces.

One major challenge of this design is sealing pressurized liquid tin in a manner that can be assembled at room temperature and be heated to the peak operating temperature of the system and remain intact throughout operation. This work relied heavily on graphite flake sheets to create seals due to their compressibility. One approach to sealing was using these sheets to make gaskets, allowing for flanged connections between components. This is of limited use at small scale, though, because the added area of the flange is significant relative to the original size of the component. The other sealing approach used was ferrules made from graphite flake sheets. Connections were designed to contain a ferrule that is crushed during assembly, creating a tight seal. These seals saw very limited leaking, and

only so in the connection immediately exiting the pump and thus at the highest pressure.

Another major challenge in this pump design is the thermal expansion of the pump shaft. Due to the large temperature difference between assembly and operation (>2000 K), thermal expansion can cause significant movement during system heating. This was especially challenging for the pump impeller, which was fixed to a shaft that extended ~ 0.5 m vertically to a mounted motor and moved more than 5 mm during heat up. This caused the impeller to press against the bottom of the pump casing, leading to added torque and accelerated wearing. To solve this, the shaft and impeller were redesigned to prevent any axial movement and the pump casing was changed to include a ~ 6 mm gap to account for thermal expansion. When assembled, the shaft is lifted to that the impeller sits against the top surface of the pump casing. As the system warms, the shaft expands and the impeller moves down in the casing accordingly. At 2400°C , the impeller should not reach the bottom of the casing and no significant wear/unnecessary torque should occur.

Fig. 2. Schematic showing pump impeller placement within pump casing A) before and B) after heating-caused thermal expansion.

B. TPV Emitter

To prevent carbon sublimation from depositing on the TPV cells, a tungsten tube will be used as the emitter. However, tin must be able to bring heat from the graphite storage medium to the emitter, so a surrounding graphite heat exchanger is used to connect the tin loop to the tungsten tube, as seen in Fig. 3:

Fig. 3. A) Isometric, B) cross-sectional, and C) co-sectional views of TPV emitter and heat exchanger.

To reduce machining costs, the minimum number of tin channels required for relative temperature uniformity is found by modeling the heat transfer through the graphite and tungsten cross-sections in a 2D COMSOL Multiphysics model. This resulted in a design with 12 grooves, which should result in a negligible (<5 K) variation in temperature angularly around the emitter, assuming uniform heat flux to the TPV cells. This model was extended to 3D to determine the flowrate required for axial temperature uniformity, which was found to be ~ 4 L/min.

III. EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS

The system has been constructed and tested up to 1000°C , demonstrating pumping across several cycles. Discharge cycles starting at the same temperature and using the same pump rotation rate show identical emitter temperature decay. A comparison of this temperature decay when the pump is on versus off is shown in Fig. 4. As would be predicted, the TPV cavity remains hotter for longer when pumping brings heat from the storage to the emitter than when the pump is off. However, this effect is small, which can be explained by the fact that the block temperature does not differ much between the pumping and no pumping cases. This is due to a contact resistance between the tin loop and the storage medium, which will decrease at higher temperatures due to increased radiation.

Fig. 4. Plot of temperature decay of TPV emitter cavity and storage block during discharge cycles with pump at 1500 RPM and 0 RPM.

REFERENCES

- [1] C. Amy et al., "Thermal energy grid storage using multi-junction photovoltaics", *Energy & Environmental Science*, vol. 12, pp 334-343, abr. 2019, doi: 10.1039/C8EE02341G
- [2] C. Amy et al., "Pumping liquid metal at high temperatures up to 1,673 kelvin", *Nature*, vol. 550, n.o 7675, abr. 2017, doi: 10.1038/nature24054
- [3] A. LaPotin et al., "Thermophotovoltaic efficiency of 40%", *Nature*, vol. 604, n.o 7905, Art. n.o 7905, abr. 2022, doi: 10.1038/s41586-022-04473-y.

Horizon Europe project BLAZETEC

Novel high-temperature solid-state converters under development

Daniele M. Trucchi¹ and the BLAZETEC consortium^{2,3,4,5,6,7}

¹Consiglio Nazionale delle Ricerche – Istituto di Struttura della Materia, Italy; ²Universidad Politecnica de Madrid – Instituto de Energia Solar, Spain; ³RGS Development, The Netherlands; ⁴Ionvac Process, Italy; ⁵The Cyprus Institute, Cyprus; ⁶Centre Suisse d'Electronique et de Microtechnique, Switzerland; ⁷Thermophoton, Spain

Abstract — The Horizon Europe project BLAZETEC - *Breakthroughs in Thermal Batteries Through Zero-Emission High-Temperature Static Thermal-to-Electric Converters* aims to pioneer ultra-high-temperature thermal batteries, operating from 1200 to 1600 °C, offering groundbreaking and efficient solutions for long-duration energy storage and conversion.

IONVAC is a SME specialized in developing vacuum components and systems, whereas CYI is a top research center for solar concentrating systems. CSEM will contribute to apply microelectronic techniques to the development of devices, whereas the spin-off TPH will help in establishing the suitable future market for thermal batteries.

I. INTRODUCTION

BLAZETEC focuses the efforts on two pivotal pilot demonstrators:

- 1) an electric thermal battery capable of converting surplus electricity into heat and then back into electricity;
- 2) a solar thermal battery designed to store concentrated sunlight and provide electric power on-demand.

Both of these systems integrate cutting-edge solid-state energy converters, including thermionics (TIG), thermoelectrics (TEG), and thermophotovoltaics (TPV). Standard thermal engines cannot support such high operating temperatures, therefore solid-state converters are now essential for effectively integrating efficient thermal batteries in renewable energy sources. BLAZETEC advances standalone TIG, TEG, and TPV technologies by introducing innovations with higher conversion efficiency with respect to the state-of-the-art like vacuum micro-gap TIG, multi-module TEG, and multijunction TPV systems. Through hybridization of these solutions, the project introduces TITEG (TIG-TEG hybrid) and TIPV (TIG-TPV hybrid), with a targeted efficiency of over 30% and a power density higher than 5 W/cm², all backed by more than 500 hours of reliability.

The integration of these technologies is facilitated by innovative vacuum encapsulation and the "dispatchable power wall" concept, which enables on-demand power generation by efficiently routing heat through the converters. The project's outcomes result in the development of five advanced energy conversion devices, an inventive system for dispatchable electricity generation, and the successful pilot testing of two kinds of thermal batteries (exploiting latent heat and sensible heat), ultimately achieving TRL 5 according to the scheme shown on the right. The BLAZETEC consortium (Table I) is highly multinational and is composed of Europe's top specialists in TIG (CNR), TEG (RGS), and TPV (UPM)

II. TECHNOLOGIES UNDER DEVELOPMENT

Hybrid thermionic-based conversion technologies are used for different applications: TIPV for latent heat thermal batteries and TITEG for sensible heat thermal batteries.

Thermionic-Thermophotovoltaic (TIPV) converters

The concept relies on the simultaneous emission of photons and electrons from a hot emitter towards a closely spaced (micrometer scale) TPV cell. The thermionic electrons are injected in the TPV cell, and finally extracted to produce useful energy before they are re-injected in the emitter (see Figure 1). In this way, the collected thermionic electrons get additional energy from the photons that offset the thermalization losses in the anode of conventional TIG. Moreover, thermal radiation is harvested and both photons and electrons contribute to electric power generation, partially eliminating the radiative heat losses of conventional TIG. Additionally, the wireless transparent contact in the front side of the cell avoids the use of front metal electrodes, and thus, eliminates the ohmic losses of conventional TPV devices. Two and three terminals TIPV converters have been demonstrated by CNR and UPM as proof-of-concepts [1-3] and they will be discussed in detail.

Thermionic-Thermoelectric generators (TITEG)

TITEG derive from the CNR proprietary concept and fabrication procedure for solar energy conversion [Patent n. EP2893549]. From the preliminary attempts demonstrating the first ever prototype, achieving a solar- and thermal-to-electric efficiency of 0.5% and 6% [4], respectively, the materials and engineering are still under a continuous updating process. The introduction of TEG thermally in series with TIG is justified if the anode temperature is limited to temperatures inducing negligible anodic counter-emission, where the resulting

TABLE I
THE BLAZETEC CONSORTIUM.

Partner	Acronym	Nation
Consiglio Nazionale delle Ricerche (Coordinator) https://www.cnr.en/	CNR	Italy
Universidad Politecnica de Madrid https://www.upm.es/internacional	UPM	Spain
RGS Development https://www.rgsdevelopment.nl/	RGS	The Netherlands
Ionvac Process https://www.ionvacprocess.com/	IONVAC	Italy
The Cyprus Institute https://www.cyi.ac.cy/	CYI	Cyprus
Centre Suisse d'Electronique et de Microtechnique https://www.csem.ch/en/	CSEM	Switzerland
Thermophoton Development https://www.thermophoton.com/	TPH	Spain

efficiency is almost independent from the anode temperature. By considering electrodes' work-functions of 1.7 and 1.0 eV, simulations reveal that a conversion efficiency of 37.6% can be achieved at 1030 °C under a solar power density of 100 W cm⁻² with realistic TEG materials (average ZT=1.0).

III. LATENT HEAT AND SENSIBLE HEAT THERMAL BATTERIES

BLAZETEC will develop Latent heat and sensible heat thermal batteries as demonstrators for TIPV and TITEG technologies, respectively. Since 2012 latent heat thermal batteries incorporating static energy converters are under development primarily at UPM in Spain. The system stores electricity in the form of latent heat by melting a phase change material (PCM) and converts the heat back on electricity on demand using thermophotovoltaics. The first lab-scale battery prototype was developed in the frame of the AMADEUS project (ended in 2019) and was used by UPM to conduct a proof-of-concept experiment (TRL 3) [5]. The system had 0.36 litres of PCM capacity (able to store 500 Wh of thermal energy in FeSiB) and was tested with three kinds of PCMs (Cu, FeSi and FeSiB) and two kinds of TPV cells (InGaAs and GaSb). This prototype enabled the demonstration of latent heat energy storage at record high temperatures (over 1200 °C), a relatively high-power generation from the TPV cells (> 0.5 W/cm²), an effective cooling of the TPV cells, which were kept at temperatures below 35 °C when located in the proximities of an incandescent crucible, and the corroboration of the crucibles' resilience after several melt/solidification cycles. This prototype also served to identify several practical issues, the most important one being related to the integration of TPV within the system (e.g., small amounts of PCM evaporated and condensed on the TPV cells, which darken and stop producing electricity). This and other issues precluded the realization of experiments over long periods.

In recent years, several startups have emerged, focusing on developing solutions to store excess electricity in the form of sensible heat at extremely high temperatures (>1200 °C). They have integrated static thermal-to-electric energy converters into their systems. Both companies employ graphite blocks as the

storage material, with the static energy converter featuring a thermophotovoltaic generator. Despite these companies have advertised very large investments (e.g., over 80 M\$ for Antora) to the best of our knowledge, a fully functional prototype incorporating these elements has not yet been produced, and the challenge of seamlessly integrating TPV technology into these

advanced thermal batteries remains uncharted territory.

Fig. 1. TIPV proof-of-concept (left) and structure (right).

REFERENCES

- [1] A. Bellucci et al., "Photovoltaic Anodes for Enhanced Thermionic Energy Conversion," ACS Energy Letters, vol. 5, no. 5, pp. 1364-1370, 2020, doi: 10.1021/acseenergylett.0c00022.
- [2] A. Bellucci, P. G. Linares, J. Villa, A. Martí, A. Datas, and D. M. Trucchi, "Hybrid thermionic-photovoltaic converter with an In_{0.53}Ga_{0.47}As anode," Solar Energy Materials and Solar Cells, vol. 238, 2022, doi: 10.1016/j.solmat.2022.111588.
- [3] A. Bellucci, P. García - Linares, A. Martí, D. M. Trucchi, and A. Datas, "A Three - Terminal Hybrid Thermionic - Photovoltaic Energy Converter," Advanced Energy Materials, vol. 12, no. 20, 2022, doi: 10.1002/aenm.202200357.
- [4] D. M. Trucchi et al., "Solar Thermionic-Thermoelectric Generator (ST2G): Concept, Materials Engineering, and Prototype Demonstration," Advanced Energy Materials, vol. 8, no. 32, 2018, doi: 10.1002/aenm.201802310.
- [5] A. Datas, A. López-Ceballos, E. López, A. Ramos, and C. del Cañizo, "Latent heat thermophotovoltaic batteries," Joule, vol. 6, no. 2, pp. 418-443, 2022, doi: 10.1016/j.joule.2022.01.010.

Theoretical and experimental study of zero-gap thermophotovoltaic system

Yonghui Liu^{ab}, Yili Tang^{ab}, Jiapeng Li^{ab}, Xiaoyu Lv^{ab}, Yuan Yuan^{ab}, Liangliang Tang^{abc*}, Jianxiong Shao^{abc*}

^a MOE Frontiers Science Center for Rare Isotopes, Lanzhou University, Lanzhou 730000, China;

^b School of Nuclear Science and Technology, Lanzhou University, Lanzhou 730000, China;

^c Institute of National Nuclear Industry, Lanzhou University, Lanzhou 730000, China

Graphical abstract:

Abstract:

Thermophotovoltaic system has attract much interest recently in commerce, military, and aerospace industries, among others. For traditional far-field TPV system, the relatively large distance between the emitter and cells, typically several centimeters, results in a limited view

factor. Consequently, the conversion efficiency would be limited by two factors: I. The radiant energy loss between the emitter and cells, and II. Heat loss due to heat conduction and convection between the emitter and the external environment. To address this issue, a widely adopted approach internationally is the implementation of near-field TPV system. Nevertheless, narrowing the gap distance between the emitter and cells to the micron-nanometer scale presents several problems. For instance, elevated cell temperature resulting from nanogaps, which can diminish the performance of TPV cells, would result in energy loss through heat conduction. Consequently, near-field TPV systems employ smaller-sized cells, thereby limiting the total power emitted.

This research developed a zero-gap thermophotovoltaic system by incorporating an infrared transmitting layer between the emitter and the cell, thereby enabling maintenance of far-field distance for achieving super-Planckian radiation effects. The translucent layer of GaAs material exhibits a radiation energy approximately 100 times that of a black body in vacuum at 1200 °C, while for quartz glass, the radiation energy is about 10 times that of a black body in vacuum.

Keywords: Far-field; Thermophotovoltaic system; Super-Planckian radiant spectrum;

Modeling thermophotovoltaics and combustion heat sources for portable power generation

S.V. Karnani, W. R. Allmon, H. Hier, N.C. Das, and C. Mike Waits

U.S. Army Combat Capabilities Development Command, Army Research Laboratory,
Adelphi, MD 20783, USA

Abstract

Thermophotovoltaics for quiet power generation is a promising, but elusive, technology to mature. The range of available system sub-components and a limited understanding of their interactions with one another helps explain why. This paper attempts to provide structure to the design space by accounting for combustion kinetics, heat transfer, the cavity between emitter and receiver, and photovoltaic response to illustrate the tradeoffs between component technologies for a thermophotovoltaic portable power generator. The impact of emitter type, recuperator effectiveness, cavity endcap reflectivity, and photovoltaic back surface reflectivity on system performance are considered over a range of flow rates for InGaAs lattice matched to InP to estimate a practical upper limit of what can be achieved in the near-term with respect to efficiency.

Introduction

Research on using thermophotovoltaics to generate portable power tends to focus on the performance of individual components, independent of other subsystems. This leaves a gap in our understanding as to why experimentally measured system efficiencies – on the order of 1-5% – lag predictions based on the performance of individual subcomponents.

To aid in answering this question, this paper describes the function and results of two numerical tools – ROCR (Reduced Order Chemical Reactor) [1] and ECT (Emitter, Cavity, TPV) – that describe the dominant physics of the burner, emitter, cavity, and receiver to evaluate each major sub-system and their coupled behaviors on TPV performance. The presented work will describe two numerical tools that describe the dominant physics of the burner, emitter, cavity, and receiver to evaluate each major sub-system and their coupled behavior on TPV performance. Evaluating the near-term design space helps illustrate the relative benefits of different emitters, cavity features, back surface reflectors, and PV materials to help focus research efforts.

Accounting for heat release in a counterflowing chemical reactor and the impact of the cavity on combustion temperatures as part of evaluating system performance distinguishes this effort from previous modeling studies.

Results

A cylindrical and highly emissive SiC gray body emitter in a concentric array of InGaAs photocells (0.74 eV bandgap at room temperature), equipped with back surface reflectors and gold endcap mirrors represents a baseline case (Fig. 1). Burner geometry [2], recuperator effectiveness [3], and photocell performance [4] are provided by the literature. Losses due to arraying are not accounted for. From the baseline conditions evaluated, approximately 55.1% of the input chemical power is emitted as radiation ($\eta_{thermal}$), 9% of the radiation is converted to electricity (η_{ECT}); the product of both translates to a 4.9% gross system efficiency (η_{sys}).

Figure 1: Practical TPV embodiment consisting of a cylindrical counterflowing heat exchanger combustor, cavity, and PV receiver.

Improvements in emitter, cavity, and TPV receiver can be realized by increasing the photoactive area (A_{active}) of the outer receiving cylinder or through boosting the reflectivity of the array's inactive regions ($R_{inactive}$). When considering the burner, emitter, and recuperator, candidates for improvement include advancements in exhaust heat scavenging (η_{eff}) and drawing a vacuum in the cavity region to eliminate unnecessary heat loss from the emitter (q_{cond}).

As a function of input power, thermal efficiency, $\eta_{thermal}$, peaks at a chemical input power, $P_{chem} = 500W$ and declines despite rising emitter temperatures. Insufficient convective heat transfer to the emitter wall

Figure 2: System efficiency as a function of input chemical power. ●: Baseline. ▼: $A_{active} = 0.88$, $R_{inactive} = 0.95$; ■: $A_{active} = 0.61$, $R_{inactive} = 0.95$; ▲: $\eta_{eff} = 0.8$, ►: $q_{cond} = 0$, ◄: $A_{active} = 0.61$, $R_{inactive} = 0.95$, $\eta_{eff} = 0.8$, and $q_{cond} = 0$

drives the behavior. ECT efficiency, η_{ECT} , improves with chemical input power as temperatures have an influence on emitted flux and the fraction of radiation convertible by the photo receiver. When taken together, gross system efficiency gradually improves with input power peaking just below 5% (Fig. 2).

In the cases evaluated, the modifications aimed at improving η_{ECT} have a negative impact on $\eta_{thermal}$. Increasing A_{active} , for example, reduces effective emissivity, hampering radiative heat transfer (i.e., $\eta_{thermal}$). Fortunately, the net result is a near doubling of optical and system efficiencies, η_{ECT} and η_{sys} . Given that a fully populated cylindrical receiver design might be impractical, an alternative path to achieve comparable

Figure 3: System efficiency as a function of emitter material choice. ●: SiC. ■: $\epsilon_{in}:\epsilon_{out} :: 0.86:0.30$. ▼: Kanthal Super ER (oxidized). ▲: NiO-doped MgO. Solid lines refer to baseline conditions. Dot-dash lines reflect the following improvements: $A_{active} = 0.61$, $R_{inactive} = 0.95$, $\eta_{eff} = 0.8$, and $q_{cond} = 0$

improvements in performance without modifying A_{active} could be reached by coating inactive areas on the array with a highly reflective gold coating. Finally, when combined with an improved recuperator and a vacuum

between the emitter and receiver, a gross system efficiency $>10\%$ becomes feasible.

Baseline system performance and the conditions that enable 10% gross system efficiency are compared against different emitters in Figure 3. For the power conditions tested, and without cavity reflectivity and recuperator improvements, NiO-doped MgO [5] outperforms SiC, and the generic selective emitter [6] (Fig 3). Spectral selectivity explains why. NiO-doped MgO behaves like a bandpass filter centered above the InGaAs bandgap, which limits thermalization losses, and is absorptive in the mid to long IR. The combination still results in the lowest thermal efficiency of the three, but the boost in η_{ECT} makes up for the loss. If the multiple suggested improvements impacting cavity reflectivity, recuperator effectiveness, and a vacuum gap are implemented (see Figure 2), SiC in a cavity where reflectivity is maximized emerges as the technology capable of peak TPV performance.

Conclusion

The coupling of two numerical tools, which, in sum, capture the dominant physics of a combustion-based TPV portable power generator allow us to quickly assess the design space by rapidly varying operating conditions to identify what combination of components can maximize performance. A highly emissive gray body exhibits the greatest benefit from a back surface reflector, in terms of reducing unnecessary radiative heat loss and increasing temperature. When a selective emitter is employed, a back surface reflector has a limited impact due to the diminished sub-bandgap emissivity/absorptivity of the emitter. In sub-optimal cavity conditions (baseline), NiO-doped MgO emerges as a top performing emitter for a lattice-matched InGaAs cell.

References

- [1] S.V. Karnani, W.R. Allmon, and C.M. Waits. Reduced-order modeling for mesoscale reactor design. *Combustion Science and Technology*, 2018.
- [2] W.E. Horne, M.D. Morgan, V.S. Sundaram, and T. Butcher. 500 Watt diesel fueled TPV portable power supply. AIP Conference Proceedings, 653(91), 2003.
- [3] L.M. Fraas, J.E. Avery, L. Minkin, and H. She. Light weight fuel-fired TPV battery replacement. International Photovoltaic Science Engineering Conference, DOI:10.13140/RG.2.2.31044.01922, 2016.
- [4] Z. Omair, G. Scranton, L.M. Pazos-Out' on, T.P. Xiao, M.A. Steiner, V. Ganapati, P.F. Peterson, J. Holzrichter, H. Atwater, and E. Yablonovitch. Ultraefficient thermophotovoltaic power conversion by band-edge spectral filtering. Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences, 116(31):15356–15361, 2019.

- [5] L.G. Ferguson and F. Dogan. A highly efficient NiO-doped MgO matched emitter for thermophotovoltaic energy conversion. *Materials Science and Engineering: B*, 83(1-3):35–41, 2001.
- [6] R. Sakakibara, V. Stelmakh, W.R. Chan, M. Ghebrebrhan, J.D. Joannopoulos, M. Soljačić, and I. Celanovic. Practical emitters for thermophotovoltaics: a review. *Journal of Photonics for Energy*, 9(3), 2019.

Effective Emissivity: How cavity reflectivity affects emitter operating point?

S. Karnani, H. Hier, W. Allmon, N. Das, and C. Mike Waits

U.S. Army Combat Capabilities Development Command, Army Research Laboratory,
Adelphi, MD 20783, US

Abstract

Achievements in InGaAs cell performance (>30-40%) [1,2] suggest key technological hurdles to commercial TPV applications are being overcome. The laboratory conditions enabling this feat (i.e., highly emissive gray body emitters coupled to photocells equipped with rear reflectors) provide high spectral selectivity, with limited substrate heating. The impact of this strategy on net heat loss from the emitter, however, which is a key determinant defining thermal efficiency for portable power generation, is less obvious. This paper reports on the impact of cavity reflectivity on emitter temperature using electrically heated, emulated components, in a cylindrical configuration, over a range of input power conditions. Data includes experimental measurements using emulated components to characterize changes in emitter temperature with cavity reflectivity, photovoltaic (PV) measurements using a partially populated array, along with modeling support.

Introduction

As a spectral control strategy, a highly emissive gray body coupled to a back surface reflector is the preferred approach when demonstrating record thermophotovoltaic (TPV) conversion efficiencies with limited substrate heating [1,2]. Translating laboratory experiments with isolated components to a practical system implementation, however, is not straightforward as the conversion process to produce the thermal energy to begin with is not accounted for, as well as the non-idealities of the cavity and its associated view factor. Because a photovoltaic (PV) will convert photons of an energy above the cell bandgap to electrons, heating strategy, emitting surface, and the cavity separating the emitter and receiver must be carefully selected to maximize system-wide energy conversion efficiency. To assess the role of cavity on net radiative emission, components meant to emulate the emitter and photovoltaic cell array (PCA) receiver are instrumented and arranged to geometrically resemble a portable power generator, and measurements are taken to assess heat transfer at multiple input power conditions and cavity configurations. The goal of this effort is to evaluate whether simplistic optical models are sufficient when developing an understanding of view factor and net heat transfer for a TPV portable

power generator that achieves spectral selectivity using a reflector-based strategy.

Results and Discussion

The emitter emulator consists of an electrically heated SiN element mounted on a SALI base and surrounded by a cylindrical Si-SiC emitter from MHI International. The PCA is emulated using 18 rectangular elements of flexible double-sided copper clad with an insulating phenolic assembled to create a faceted cylinder, concentric with the emitter (Fig. 1). Different materials can be affixed to the rectangular elements creating uniquely reflective environments. Four cavity configurations are evaluated: Au on Si (98% reflectivity, $\lambda > 2$ microns), Ge (37% reflectivity, $\lambda > 2$ microns), InGaAs on InP with Au rear reflector (90% reflectivity, $2 \text{ microns} < \lambda < 5 \text{ microns}$), and Au on Si with one facet replaced with an array of InGaAs, lattice matched to InP, cells operated individually. Approximately 14% of each facet remains uncovered with an average optical reflectivity of 21.6%.

Figure 1: Overhead images of emulated components assembled to resemble a TPV portable power generator, with and without a SALI endcap.

Thermocouples are affixed to the SiN heating element and the inner wall of the Si-SiC emitter. An optical pyrometer measures the temperature on the outer wall before and after every tested cavity condition to monitor the Si-SiC for signs of degradation and calibrate inner wall thermocouple temperatures when the cavity is in place. The electrical power supplied to

the SiN is measured and used as an input to a numerical model [3]. The model simulates propane combustion as a heat source. Modifications, including, limiting sensible enthalpy losses via the exhaust, and eliminating convective heat transfer within the emitter are sufficient for the model to resemble electrically heated experiments. Relying on gas chemistry to provide heat does limit the simulation to conditions where combustion can be sustained. Using a combustion-based model will ease comparisons with future fuel-fired experiments.

Emitter temperature for a given configuration is solved by, first, computing effective emissivity of the emitter and cavity configuration as a function of emitter temperature. Effective emissivity is net radiance after accounting for multiple cavity reflections between the emitting/absorbing inner cylinder, SALI end cap reflectors [4], and the spectrally reflective/absorbing outer faceted cylinder, normalized to the radiance from a black body at the same temperature (Eq. 1) [5,6].

$$\epsilon_{eff} = \int_0^{10\mu m} \epsilon(\lambda) \frac{2\pi hc^2}{\lambda^5} \frac{1}{e^{hc/(\lambda k_b T)} - 1} d\lambda / \sigma T^4 \quad (1)$$

Literature [7,8] and in-house FTIR measurements provide reflectivity data. The resulting function is used to describe the emitter's heat loss boundary condition.

Figure 2. Experimental emitter temperature measurements compared to simulations as a function of input power and cavity configuration.

Figure 2 compares experimental estimates of the emitter outer wall to simulations at the same conditions. There is good agreement over the range of power and cavity conditions evaluated. At temperatures below 600C, the simulation is unable to sustain combustion. Simulations overpredict experimentally measured temperatures by approximately 5%, and 10% in the worst case. The results demonstrate that as a cavity becomes more reflective, effective emissivity goes down, leading to

Figure 3. Thermal efficiency of a SiC emitter in different cavity configurations as a function of effective emissivity, at a fixed 206W of input power.

higher emitter temperatures for a fixed power condition. Higher temperatures improve spectral selectivity, improving energy conversion at the cell, but at the cost of thermal efficiency (Figure 3), defined as the ratio of power radiatively emitted normalized to reactor input power.

Finally, in the Au on Si mirrored facet configuration, one of the elements is replaced with a 1x6 array of lattice matched InGaAs cells purchased from Antora Energy, Inc. Only one cell, positioned at the same height where temperatures were measured was wired for interrogation. Experiments are compared to results from a single diode model populated using parameters extracted from the cell after being characterized under various lighting conditions [9]. The model includes the impact of bandgap narrowing [10] and dark current [11]. Modeling data suggests cell temperatures are approximately 20C higher than temperatures measured at the base of the receiver's heat sink. In the 116W and 146W cases, simulated open circuit voltages agree within 2% of experimentally measured values (0.417 vs 0.411 and 0.4438 vs 0.451, respectively). Experimentally measured short circuit currents are approximately 66% greater than simulations (23.29mA vs 14.16mA, and 110.7mA vs 67.84mA, respectively). Bandgap narrowing plays a partial role in the increased current, but the remaining discrepancy suggests that view factor should be modified to reflect the radiation incident on an individual cell.

Conclusion

Components designed to emulate an emitter and receiver in a TPV portable power generator were evaluated to characterize how a reflective cavity as a spectral control strategy impacts net heat radiative transfer from the emitter. Good agreement is observed over the conditions evaluated (Figure 2). Results

provide insight to the model's limitations when simulating system performance. Emitter temperature and thermal efficiency trend inversely with radiant heat extraction, illustrating the conflict between reactor efficiency and potential system efficiency. The measurements give us a preliminary understanding of electricity generated in a relevant environment as a function of incident flux and cell temperature. Substituting real components enables the tracking of tangible operational outputs, like electricity generated in a thermally relevant environment to inform practical TPV conversion efficiency when considering non-ideal reflective cavities and TPV arrays.

References

- [1] A. LaPotin, *et al. Nature* **604**, 287–291 (2022).
- [2] Z. Omair, et al. Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences, 116(31):15356–15361, 2019.
- [3] S.V. Karnani, et al. *Combustion Science and Technology*, 2018.
- [4] A. Sergeev and C.M. Waits. *Journal of Photonics for Energy*, 10(3), 2020.
- [5] R.B. Bird, W.E. Stewart, and E.N. Lightfoot. *Transport Phenomena*. John Wiley & Sons, 1960.
- [6] Howard, Siegel, and Menguc. *Thermal radiation heat transfer*. URL <http://www.thermalradiation.net/sectionc/C-92.html>
- [7] S. Babar and J. H. Weaver. *Appl. Opt.* **54**, 477-481 (2015)
- [8] T. Amotchkina, et al., *Appl. Opt.* **59**, A40-A47 (2020)
- [9] E. Meyer. *International Journal of Photoenergy*, <https://doi.org/10.1155/2017/8479487>, 2017.
- [10] H. Zielinski, et al. *Journal of Applied Physics*, 59(6), 1986.
- [11] S. Wojtczuk. *AIP Conference Proceedings*, 358:387–393, 1996.

Experiment assessing the use of GaSb array with filters for waste heat recovery in the cement, steel, and glass Industries

Graham Buckley, C. M. Iftexhar Hussain, Brian Norton.

Technological University Dublin, graham.buckley@tudublin.ie
Grangegorman, Dublin 7, Ireland

Abstract –Cement, steel, and glass industries combined emitted approximately 5080MTonnes of CO₂ in 2022. This accounts for about 13.8% of all CO₂ output by human activity. These three industrial sectors have become as efficient as practically possible, to increase profitability and reduce the impact on the environment. TPV, as a technology, lends itself particularly well to these industries as they all produce a large quantity of high temperature waste heat. Approximately 10 to 25% of the heat losses are due to emission of photons which, so far, are not captured, recycled, or used in the process. A TPV system can convert their radiated heat into electrical power to partially meet their plant's electricity requirements. A linear TPV array of 19 cells was tested in a float glass plant for 50 minutes at 1250°C and a cement plant for 2.5 hours at 1050°C. Fluctuations in light intensity were seen as passing materials vary. The expected power density of this prototype in the cement scenario was approximately 0.06W/cm² to 0.2W/cm². This prototype measured an MPP between 0.025W/cm² to 0.05W/cm².

Key words: TPV system, GaSb, spectral filters, high-temperature, waste heat, cement, glass.

Storage-integrated solar thermophotovoltaics: model and experiments

Maxime Giteau

CNRS, Laboratoire PROcédés, Matériaux et Energie Solaire (PROMES), UPR 8521, Odeillo, France

Abstract — Photovoltaics (PV) is currently the main solution to harvest solar power but does not provide much-needed energy storage capacity. Concentrated solar power (CSP) inherently offers thermal storage but remains expensive and restricted to large-scale power plants. Here, we discuss the development of an alternative solar thermal technology called storage-integrated solar thermophotovoltaics (SISTPV), which combines solar energy harvesting, high-density thermal energy storage, and high-performance electricity production using thermophotovoltaics (TPV). In this presentation, I will first overview the progress and challenges towards the development of SISTPV technology. I will then present numerical results as well as preliminary experimental results towards the development of a 6kW prototype.

I. INTRODUCTION

Immediate coordinated action is required to secure a livable and sustainable future, as humanity must achieve carbon neutrality by 2050 to limit global warming below 1.5°C. Solar cells, which directly generate electricity from sunlight through the photovoltaic (PV) effect (Fig. 1(a)), hold a central place in this plan. However, the transition towards an energy mix dominated by renewable sources implies intermittent energy production with little dispatchability, resulting in colossal energy storage capacities requirements.

An alternative solar technology, known as concentrated solar power (CSP), harvests sunlight directly as thermal energy, offering one crucial advantage compared to PV conversion: the integrated ability to store energy as heat at low cost to produce electricity on-demand. However, the levelized cost of electricity is much lower for PV. This is partly because the modularity of PV makes it deployable at all scales, while CSP is only viable at utility scale. As a result, PV has recently overtaken most of the solar energy market.

To improve the prospects of solar thermal technologies, their operation temperature should be drastically enhanced, from ~500°C to well over 1000°C. While solar tower systems can achieve sufficiently high concentration to reach temperatures well above 1000°C, the temperature limitation is rather dictated by material and engineering constraints on the solar receiver, storage medium, and heat engine.

A promising way to enable high-temperature energy conversion is to replace the steam turbine of CSP systems by thermophotovoltaic (TPV) cells, which use the PV effect to convert the thermal radiation from any hot source into electric power [1]. Unlike dynamic engines, the performance of TPV devices is independent of scale, and they offer better reliability and lower maintenance costs thanks to the absence

of moving parts or working fluids. TPV has been an increasingly active research field in the past decade, owing to developments in material science and devices [2], leading to impressive experimental results [3] and several startups. **However, all these systems rely on thermal batteries which are heated electrically rather than with sunlight.**

Solar TPV (STPV), where an absorber heats up by collecting concentrated sunlight on one side and emits photons towards a TPV cell on the other side, has long been suggested for its potential to approach the 85% solar efficiency limit [4]. The first experimental efficiency was reported in 2013 [5]. Since then, despite significant progress, the efficiency record remains around 8.4% [6]. **Additionally, all STPV experiments have so far considered direct solar-to-electricity energy conversion, neglecting thermal storage.** Not only does this removes the key advantage of solar thermal technologies, adding storage would allow decoupling solar input from production, reducing the need for large TPV production area.

The object of this presentation is a system that combines sunlight absorption, thermal storage, and TPV electricity generation, called **storage-integrated solar TPV (SISTPV)**. First suggested in 2013 [7], inspired by an earlier work [8], a SISTPV system can fundamentally be decomposed into three parts (**Fig. 1**). Sunlight is concentrated onto a surface with high absorptivity in the solar spectrum, generating heat. This heat is transferred to a material in which it can be stored. To produce electricity, the heat is radiated by a surface with high emissivity in the infrared towards a low-bandgap TPV cell which converts this thermal radiation into electricity.

Fig. 1. Sketch of a general SISTPV system.

II. RESEARCH

On the theoretical front, I am currently developing a **comprehensive model that couples sunlight absorption, thermal storage and TPV conversion**. For solar absorption, I will introduce various strategies to maximize absorption while minimizing radiative losses, leveraging spectral and spatial engineering techniques [9]. Regarding thermal storage, I will present simulations of the heat transfer that goes through the storage material, with a focus on phase-change materials (**Fig. 2**). For TPV conversion, I will apply thermodynamic balance models to determine the efficiency and power density [10]. Finally, I will show how coupling these models allows to find optimal operation conditions, taking into account experimental constraints.

Fig. 2. Stored energy as sensible and latent heat, as a function of time, for a cycle consisting in 10 min charge followed by 20 min discharge. The dashed lines indicate the maximum energy that can be stored as sensible heat in the solid phase and as latent heat.

On the experimental side, a prototype for sunlight absorption and storage (at this stage without a TPV cell) is under construction, to be installed under a 6 kW solar concentration apparatus (see **Fig. 3**). The prototype is almost complete, and **first experiments will be conducted this summer**.

Sunlight enters through a hemispherical glass window. Light is absorbed at the surface of the thermal storage unit, a cylinder of 62 mm diameter and 105 mm height surrounded by a thick insulation to minimize heat dissipation through conduction. The temperature evolution during operation will be measured using 15 thermocouples located around the thermal storage unit. The system is sealed to enable operation under a neutral (Ar) low-pressure atmosphere in order to prevent undesirable chemical reactions as well as evaporation onto the front window.

The first objective is to demonstrate efficient solar absorption and storage. Thermal storage will initially be

achieved using sensible heat with a graphite block, followed by investigations into latent heat storage in metallic alloys (FeAl) as well as fluorines (MgF₂). The system has been designed to be modular, allowing for modifications and updates. In particular, the ceramic block below the thermal storage unit will be **replaced by a TPV cell to demonstrate electrical power production**.

Fig. 3. Schematic of the SISTPV system under fabrication.

REFERENCES

- [1] A. Datas and R. Vaillon, Chapter 11 - Thermophotovoltaic Energy Conversion, in *Ultra-High Temperature Thermal Energy Storage, Transfer and Conversion*, edited by A. Datas (Woodhead Publishing, 2021), pp. 285–308.
- [2] A. Datas, M. Francoeur, M. Shimizu, and R. Vaillon, Advances in Thermophotovoltaics: Materials, Devices, and Systems, *Solar Energy Materials and Solar Cells* **240**, 111711 (2022).
- [3] M. Giteau, M. F. Picardi, and G. T. Papadakis, Thermodynamic Figure of Merit for Thermophotovoltaics, *Journal of Photonics for Energy* **14**, 042402 (2024).
- [4] N.-P. Harder and P. W. Würfel, Theoretical Limits of Thermophotovoltaic Solar Energy Conversion, *Semicond. Sci. Technol.* **18**, S151 (2003).
- [5] A. Datas and C. Algora, Development and Experimental Evaluation of a Complete Solar Thermophotovoltaic System, *Progress in Photovoltaics: Research and Applications* **21**, 1025 (2013).
- [6] R. Bhatt, I. Kravchenko, and M. Gupta, High-Efficiency Solar Thermophotovoltaic System Using a Nanostructure-Based Selective Emitter, *Solar Energy* **197**, 538 (2020).
- [7] A. Datas, D. L. Chubb, and A. Veeraragavan, Steady State Analysis of a Storage Integrated Solar Thermophotovoltaic (SISTPV) System, *Solar Energy* **96**, 33 (2013).
- [8] D. L. Chubb, B. S. Good, and R. A. Lowe, Solar Thermophotovoltaic (STPV) System with Thermal Energy Storage, *AIP Conference Proceedings* **358**, 181 (1996).
- [9] Sarkar, M., Giteau, M., Enders, M. T. & Papadakis, G. T., Lithography-free directional control of thermal emission, *Nanophotonics* **13**, 763–771 (2024).
- [10] Giteau, M., Picardi, M. F. & Papadakis, G. T., Thermodynamic performance bounds for radiative heat engines, *Phys. Rev. Appl.* **20**, L061003 (2023).

Design of Optical Cavity for Thermophotovoltaics Considering Thermal Conditions in Cells

Haolin Wang, Makoto Shimizu, Hiroo Yugami

Department of Mechanical Systems Engineering, Graduate School of Engineering, Tohoku University, Aoba 6-6-01 Aramaki, Aoba-ku, Sendai 980-8579, Japan

Abstract — Thermophotovoltaics (TPVs) offer a promising avenue for efficient heat-to-electricity conversion, particularly with recent advancements in photon-recycling techniques. However, the effective implementation of photon recycling requires a well-designed optical cavity, an area where existing literature falls short. Addressing this gap, our study explores the intricate design aspects of TPV systems and investigates the combined impact of photon recycling and cell temperature dependence on system performance. Through ray-trace simulations and experimental validation utilizing GaSb cells, we analyze the factors influencing TPV system efficiency and establish design guidelines for optimizing optical cavities. Our findings emphasize the importance of achieving high cooling performance alongside efficient photon recycling to maximize system efficiency. This research advances the understanding of TPV system design and lays a foundational framework facilitating future research and practical applications in the field.

I. INTRODUCTION

Thermophotovoltaics (TPVs) offer a promising way for efficient heat-to-electricity conversion through photons, especially with recent advancements in photon-recycling techniques. Significant progress has been made in optimizing these strategies, leading to record-breaking efficiencies in TPV systems. For instance, Omair et al. [1] achieved a TPV efficiency of $29.1 \pm 0.4\%$ at an emitter temperature of $1207\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ by employing a highly reflective mirror at the rear of the PV cell to maximize radiation extraction. Fan et al. [2] integrated an air bridge layer within a thin-film $\text{In}_{0.53}\text{Ga}_{0.47}\text{As}$ cell, creating a near-perfect mirror with nearly 99% out-of-band reflectance, achieving remarkable conversion efficiency exceeding 30%. However, the effective implementation of photon recycling, particularly with cells possessing high out-of-band reflectance, necessitates a well-designed optical cavity. While several innovative TPV optical-cavity designs have been proposed [3], existing studies often compare these designs with traditional concentric cylinder TPV systems without delving into specific geometric factors influencing optical efficiency or providing guidelines for achieving optimal cavity designs. Addressing this gap, our study aims to explore the intricate design aspects of TPV systems. Our primary objectives are twofold: firstly, to establish design guidelines aimed at optimizing the optical cavity for TPV systems, and secondly, to investigate the combined impact of photon recycling and the temperature dependence of the cell on system performance.

II. METHODS

This study constructed a model (Fig. 1) comprising an emitter, optical cavity, and PV cells to analyze TPV system performance. Ray-trace simulations were employed to investigate the impact of various design parameters on optical efficiency, including cavity shape, emitter-to-cell distance, cavity wall reflectance, cavity length, and area ratios between cells and emitters. Experimental setups utilizing GaSb cells were employed to explore the thermal behavior of the cells and compare them with theoretically calculated temperature coefficients. System efficiency was determined by dividing the electrical output power, calculated using a detailed balance model adjusted for temperature dependence based on experimentally obtained temperature coefficients, by the net input power, which accounts for the total input power minus the power reflected back to the emitter.

Fig. 1. Schematic figure for TPV system model in this study.

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

A. Ray-trace simulation results

Ray-trace simulations provided crucial insights into the factors influencing TPV system efficiency. Notably, the straight cavity design emerged as optimal due to its simplicity and comparable optical efficiencies, particularly at shorter emitter-cell distances. Higher cavity wall reflectance correlates with increased optical efficiency and reduced loss rates. The length of the PV cell array ceased to affect optical efficiency and loss rate beyond a certain value. The area ratio is an important factor, with an optimal value of 1 when the cell temperature is kept constant at 300 K.

B. Experimental results

Experimental findings validated theoretical predictions, emphasizing the importance of considering thermal behavior of TPV cells. The short-circuit current showed a slight increase with temperature, attributed to a minor reduction in the bandgap and enhanced external quantum efficiency. Conversely, the open-circuit voltage exhibited a consistent linear decrease with temperature. Although the fill factor decreased with rising cell temperature, its relationship showed less linearity. Despite some disparities between calculated and experimental results, largely due to challenges in parameter acquisition, the overall alignment underscored the validity of the analytical approach. A margin of approximately 10% was acceptable for evaluating the thermal behavior of TPV cells.

C. Calculated system efficiency considering temperature dependence of TPV cells

To address the temperature dependence of TPV cells and obtain system efficiency under real operating conditions, calculations incorporated varying cell temperatures instead of assuming a constant value. Thus, we set heat sinks with different heat-transfer coefficients. The maximum system efficiency at the optimal area ratio under different conditions is shown in Fig. 2. Notably, even with advanced technology, which is high-reflectance cell, significant improvements in system efficiency could not be achieved without enhancing heat transfer rates. The system efficiency of high-reflectance cell with low cooling performance is even lower than low-reflectance cell with high cooling performance when emitter temperature is high. High-reflectance cells coupled with high heat-transfer rates yielded optimal performance, surpassing state-of-the-art GaSb cells [7]. Additionally, varying emitter temperatures influenced system efficiency, with lower temperatures proving advantageous under low heat transfer rates and higher temperatures under high heat transfer rates. The optimized emitter temperature was approximately 1700 K for high-reflectance cells with high heat-transfer rates, with marginal differences observed between emitter temperatures ranging from 1500 K to 1900 K.

Fig. 2. Maximum system efficiency at optimal area ratio for varying emitter temperatures, with low (1000 W/(m²K)) and high (10000 W/(m²K)) heat transfer coefficients, low and high reflectance.

D. The significance of the work for the field

This study contributes to the advancement of optical cavity design for TPV systems by meticulously analyzing the influence of each parameter on optical efficiency and loss rate. By considering the absorption loss in cavity walls during photon recycling, this research takes a step towards practical application. Moreover, by integrating photon recycling and accounting for cell temperature dependence of the cell, our study provides invaluable insights into optimizing TPV system efficiency. We emphasize the importance of achieving high cooling performance alongside efficient photon recycling to further enhance system efficiency. While our primary focus is on GaSb cells, the foundational framework established by our findings extends to other cell materials, facilitating future research and practical applications in TPV system design.

IV. CONCLUSIONS

In summary, our study focused on optimizing optical cavities for cylindrical TPV systems, uncovering key insights through ray-trace simulations while considering cell thermal dynamics. We found that a straight cavity design offers simplicity and competitive optical efficiencies, especially at shorter emitter-to-cell distances. The cavity wall reflectance playing a critical role in reducing losses. Minimizing the distance between emitter and cell is essential, alongside an optimal area ratio of 1 under constant cell temperature conditions. Moreover, our investigation into TPV cell thermal behavior, validated through experiments, highlighted the importance of robust parameter evaluation, despite minor theoretical-experimental disparities. By integrating cell temperature coefficients into our simulations, we showcased the potential of efficient photon recycling with high-reflectance cells and enhanced heat dissipation to achieve system efficiencies surpassing 40%, even in practical TPV setups. To further boost TPV performance, future efforts should prioritize improving cooling performance alongside increasing the photon-recycling effect.

REFERENCES

- [1] Z. Omair et al., Ultraefficient thermophotovoltaic power conversion by band-edge spectral filtering, *Proc. Natl. Acad. Sci.* 116 (2019) 15356–15361. <https://doi.org/10.1073/pnas.1903001116>.
- [2] D. Fan et al., Near-perfect photon utilization in an air-bridge thermophotovoltaic cell, *Nature* 586 (2020) 237–241. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41586-020-2717-7>.
- [3] P. Sansoni et al., Evaluation of elliptical optical cavity for a combustion thermophotovoltaic system, *Sol. Energy Mater. Sol. Cells* 171 (2017) 282–292. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1016/j.solmat.2017.07.001>.

Enhancing the Capabilities in Thermophotovoltaic Systems by Harnessing Multiple Heat Sources

Shahriar Homaei¹, Nima Talebzadeh¹, Paul G. O'Brien¹

¹Department of Mechanical Engineering, York University, Toronto, Ontario, M3J 1P3, Canada

Abstract — Thermophotovoltaics (TPV) is a versatile thermal-to-power conversion technology with numerous applications. TPV is traditionally powered by a single heat source; however, integration of multiple heat sources significantly enhances flexibility, reliability, and performance. In this study, numerical and experimental methods are employed to assess and compare the performance of TPV systems powered by individual and combined heat sources. The findings demonstrate the output power from a TPV system is increased by 42% when powered by two sources providing 50 W/cm², as compared to the total power produced when two separate TPV systems are both powered by 50 W/cm² sources. Integration of multiple heat sources marks a critical step towards expanding applications of TPV systems.

I. INTRODUCTION

Thermophotovoltaics (TPV) stands out as a versatile technology for converting heat into electricity, finding application in uninterrupted power supplies, combined heat and power systems, self-powered heating devices, and industrial waste heat recovery. Recent advancements have pushed TPV efficiency beyond 40%, with projections indicating potential further gains of up to 50% [1]. TPV systems demonstrate adaptability to various heat sources including biomass and hydrogen combustion, concentrated solar power, waste heat recovery, and chemical and nuclear reactions making them suitable for diverse energy contexts. Notably, TPV's solid-state design has no moving parts, which enhances reliability and durability. Incorporating multiple heat sources in TPV configurations can have many advantages including increased system reliability and flexibility, optimized use of available heat, heat source matching, broader adaptability, customizable outputs, cost-effective operations, and scalable designs.

II. BACKGROUND, RESEARCH GAP & OBJECTIVES

Despite its numerous advantages, multisource TPV integration remains mostly underexplored. Davis et al. developed a hybrid solar/natural gas TPV system with objectives including 25% efficiency in solar-to-electric and 20% efficiency in gas-to-electric conversion, along with doubling energy density [2]. They utilized solar absorbers and emitters to harness both solar irradiance and gas for power generation. Challenges such as vacuum seal malfunctions and material compatibility issues are noted for future refinement.

Hussain et al. demonstrated a hybrid solar-biomass power plant, emphasizing the heat-injected emitter design for

simplicity and versatility [3]. They proposed integrating parabolic dish solar collectors with TPV cells and fuel burners. However, research gaps include the lack of experimental and numerical analysis, system design parameters, and efficiency assessments, suggesting future investigations to enhance practical applicability and efficiency. The focus of this work is on the numerical and experimental analysis of powering a TPV system using multiple heat sources. The primary objective is to evaluate the performance of a TPV system incorporating a secondary heat source. The initial step involves a theoretical assessment to determine the viability of a multi-source TPV structure. Analytical evaluation aims to understand the potential benefits associated with adding an auxiliary source. Additionally, monitoring output variations between single-source and multi-source operations is crucial. Subsequently, experimental methods are employed to validate the findings from theoretical analysis, ensuring the practical applicability of the proposed multi-source TPV system.

III. METHODS

In the numerical approach, the emitting source is assumed to be a blackbody emitter with high thermal conductivity such as graphite. This emitter is powered by two heat sources both ranging from 0 to 100 W/cm². The output power is calculated based on the individual input sources and when they are integrated to determine individual and combined effects on output power. The increase in output power due to an increase in input power from a secondary source is also assessed. The output power calculations are based on the equations used in [4-5] for a GaSb PV cell.

In the experiments, a ceramic resistive heater serves as the first source, while a high-wattage Tungsten light, concentrated

Fig. 1 Experimental setup of the multi-source TPV system.

Fig. 2. (a) the sum of the output power from a TPV system when it is powered by two sources individually ($P_{out(1)} + P_{out(2)}$) (b) the output power from a TPV system when it is simultaneously powered by two sources ($P_{out(1+2)}$). (c) the power enhancement ($P_{out(1+2)}/(P_{out(1)} + P_{out(2)})$) is achieved by powering the TPV system with two power sources simultaneously as compared to the power generated when the power sources are used individually.

by an elliptical concentrator, acts as the second power source. The setup, operated under vacuum conditions, monitors the emitter temperature and output power as a function of the input from two power sources. The output power from the TPV system is first measured when the ceramic heater and light bulb are used as power sources individually. Subsequently, the output power from the TPV system is measured when the power sources are used simultaneously. Figure 1 shows the experimental setup for studying the multi-source TPV system.

IV. RESULTS

Fig. 2.a depicts the output power of the GaSb PV cell as functions of the primary and secondary heat source ranging from 0 to 100 W/cm² (emitter surface) when the input sources are applied separately and the output powers due to each source are summed ($P_{out(1)} + P_{out(2)}$). Fig. 2b shows the output electric power as functions of the primary and secondary sources when they are applied simultaneously ($P_{out(1+2)}$). For example, the summation of the output power from the TPV system when it is powered with 50 W/cm² from the primary source and when it is powered with 50 W/cm² from the secondary source is $P_{out(1)} + P_{out(2)} = 13.7$ W/cm². In comparison, the output power from the TPV system when it is powered by 50 W/cm² from the primary source and 50 W/cm² from the secondary source simultaneously is $P_{out(1+2)} = 19.5$ W/cm². This result shows a 42% increase in the power output when sources 1 and 2 are used simultaneously. Fig. 1.c shows the power enhancement ratio ($P_{out(1+2)}/(P_{out(1)} + P_{out(2)})$) achieved by powering the TPV system with the two power sources simultaneously as compared to when the two power sources are used separately. Experimental results were obtained where the TPV system is separately powered by sources 1 and 2 ($P_{out(1)} + P_{out(2)}$) and then powered in the multi-source configuration ($P_{out(1+2)}$). The results show that the difference between the single-source and multi-source output increases rapidly by increasing the input sources. For example, comparing the output when the input sources power the emitter independently and simultaneously at their middle rate and highest rate, the output changes from $P_{out(1)} + P_{out(1)} =$

0.012, 0.495 μ W to $P_{out(1+2)} = 0.4644, 6.386$ μ W correspondingly.

V. CONCLUSION

The integration of multiple heat sources to power a TPV system to significantly enhance system output and efficiency is demonstrated. Through both numerical and experimental analysis, this study confirmed that simultaneous operation of dual heat sources leads to a notable increase in output power—up to 42% more compared to single-source operations when both sources are $P_m = 50$ W/cm². This enhancement is particularly pronounced at lower input power levels, highlighting the potential for substantial efficiency gains in low-temperature applications. The ability to harness and effectively manage multiple heat sources not only broadens the applicability of TPV systems across various thermal sources but also paves the way for more cost-effective and scalable energy solutions. Future research should focus on optimizing the integration process and exploring various heat sources such as incident radiation for aerospace applications to elevate TPV systems' performance and adaptability.

REFERENCES

- [1] Alina LaPotin et al. "Thermophotovoltaic efficiency of 40%". In: Nature 604.7905 (2022), pp. 287–291.
- [2] Gray Davis. Hybrid thermophotovoltaic power systems. Tech. rep. Technical report P500-02-048F, California Energy Commission, 2002.
- [3] CM Iftekhar Hussain et al. "Hybrid Solar Thermophotovoltaic-Biomass/Gas Power Generation System with a Spectrally Matched Emitter for Lower Operating Temperatures". In: 12th conference on sustainable development of energy, water and environment systems, Dubrovnik, October 4–8. 2017.
- [4] Hao Wang et al. "Performance analysis of solar thermophotovoltaic conversion enhanced by selective metamaterial absorbers and emitters". In: International Journal of Heat and Mass Transfer 98 (2016), pp. 788–798.
- [5] Yimin Xuan, Xue Chen, and Yuge Han. "Design and analysis of solar thermophoto-voltaic systems". In: Renewable Energy 36.1 (2011), pp. 374–38

Development and experimental characterization of highly packed Ge thermophotovoltaic mini-modules.

J. Villa^a, P. García-Linares^a, I. Izquierdo^{a,b}, A. M. Medrano^a, E. López^a, and A. Datas^a

^a Instituto de Energía Solar, Universidad Politécnica de Madrid, Av. Complutense s/n, 28040, Madrid, Spain.

^b Termophoton, Calle Chile, 10, 28290, Las Rozas de Madrid, Spain

Abstract — Germanium (Ge) is a low-cost alternative to III-V semiconductors for the development of thermophotovoltaic (TPV) devices. Despite several works that have reported the development of Ge TPV cells, very few reported the integration of Ge TPV cells into modules. This step is key for the development of final applications and to accomplish scale up system demonstrations. This study presents a scalable procedure for assembling highly packed mini-modules using Ge TPV cells that are soldered onto direct bonding copper (DBC) substrates. Each mini-module comprises 10 1-cm²-sized Ge cells and produces a short-circuit current of 10 A at 75 suns-reference illumination conditions. In addition, a Ge bypass diode is assembled in the mini-module to mitigate losses under non uniform irradiance conditions, which may be expected during operation in the final application. We demonstrate minimal diode leakage losses by parasitic illumination of 0.03 A at 75 suns. Furthermore, *I-V* characteristic of the Ge bypass diode exhibits a direct forward current of 20 A at 0.7 V forward bias, and a breakdown voltage of approximately -4.5 V. Thermal cycling tests reveal no degradation in the mini-modules. Thermal and mechanical characterization of the mini-modules, which includes the inspection of voids in the soldering process, will be shown in the final presentation. It is expected that these highly packed Ge-based mini-modules will produce a short-circuit current of 15 A when irradiated by a graphite emitter at 1300 °C.

I. INTRODUCTION

Ge represents a cost-efficient alternative to III-V semiconductors for the manufacture of TPV devices [1]. Several works have reported the development of Ge TPV cells with relatively high efficiency (>10%) and power density generation (>1 W/cm²) [2]. However, very few works have reported the development of compact Ge-based TPV modules [3]. The assembly of TPV modules may lead to several issues, including resistance losses due to cell interconnection, current mismatch due to non-homogeneous irradiance conditions, or cell overheating due to poor thermal dissipation, among others. In this work, we present a scalable procedure for assembling highly packed Ge mini-modules, which are designed to deliver high current densities. Additionally, a bypass diode is inserted to mitigate losses when multiple mini-modules are interconnected into a large system. In Section II, we describe the design, the components, and the experimental procedure for the assembly of the mini-modules. In Section III, we show the experimental results from the characterization, in particular, the Ge bypass diode *I-V* curve and the electrical performance of the mini-modules in comparison with individual Ge cells. Finally, in Section V, we summarize the main conclusion and future pending work.

II. METHODOLOGY

The highly packed Ge-based mini-module comprises 10 Ge TPV cells (10x10 mm sized), manufactured by CESI, and one homemade Ge bypass diode soldered into a Curamik™ direct bonded copper (DBC) substrate. A bypass diode is inserted to prevent current losses. Mini-modules are intended to be integrated into a larger TPV power converter and they will be electrically interconnected among them. The Ge bypass diodes are manufactured by means of standard photolithography process, wet chemical etching and thermal evaporation making use of n/p epitaxial structures, which were manufactured by the Fraunhofer-ISE on high-doping Ge-wafer.

The assembly process for developing highly packed Ge-based mini-modules involves several key steps. First, Ge devices are soldered onto the DBC substrate using SAC-305 preforms, which are 10 mm x 10 mm metal sheets comprising an alloy of Sn, Cu, and Ag, in a reflow oven. Forming gas is utilized in this process to eliminate surface oxides and it enhances the wettability of the soldering preforms to both the metal Ge TPV cell and DBC surfaces. Second, the front contacts of the Ge cells are interconnected by soldering tabbing ribbon to the front bus bar of each individual cell. Lastly, external wiring is established through Ni-plated platen with parallel gap welding.

III. EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS

Fig. 1 displays an image of one of the assembled highly packed Ge-based mini-modules. Our developed process has proven to be functional. The constituent elements of the mini-modules are clearly discernible in the image.

Fig. 1. Real picture of one of the highly packed Ge-based mini-modules assembled.

A. Ge bypass diode electrical characterization

Fig. 2 shows the dark current-voltage characteristics for a Ge bypass diode. An inset is included to depict the *I-V* curve in logarithmic scale. Three points are highlighted in the main

curve, which represents: (1) breakdown voltage for the diode at around -4.8 V; (2) working point for a current when the diode is biased at -0.6 V, this current is -3 mA; and (3) working point for 20 A flowing through the diode being 0.70 V; and . In addition, Ge bypass diode produces a short-circuit current of 0.03 A under 75 suns-reference illumination condition.

Fig. 2. Dark IV measurement of the Ge bypass diode. The inset depicts the IV characteristics in logarithmic scale.

B. Ge Cell-to-module characterization

The dark IV response of the mini-module is shown in the Fig. 3 (a). This graph depicts the dark I - V characteristics of the mini-module with the Ge bypass diode (black curve), the IV of the mini-module without the bypass diode (green curve) and an individual Ge TPV cell (blue curve).

Fig. 3. Dark IV (a) and light IV (b) measurements of the Ge-based mini-module with Ge bypass diode (black curve), without diode (green curve), and an individual Ge TPV cell.

Fig. 3 (b) shows the I - V curve of the mini-module under 75 suns illumination with and without the bypass diode (black and green curves, respectively), and that of the individual Ge TPV cell (blue curve). The small leakage current and the high breakdown voltage of the bypass diode ensures small power

losses during normal operation. For instance, when irradiated by a graphite emitter at 1300 °C, the mini-module is expected to produce around 9 W (15 A and 0.6 V). Under this conditions, the diode consumes only 1.8 mW (3 mA and 0.6 V). When a large number of mini-modules is connected to integrate a TPV system and it is illuminated with non-uniform irradiance condition, the presence of bypass diodes ensures proper the operation of the full system, as it is expected, thanks to the fact that the bypass diode can withstand up to 20 A and working voltage of 0.70 V without showing degradation.

V. CONCLUSIONS

This study presents the development of highly packed Ge-based TPV mini-modules and outlines the assembly procedure. Through thorough characterization, including the assessment of mini-module functionality and performance, our findings demonstrate promising results, producing 10 A under 75 suns. The integration of the bypass diode within the mini-module ensures a reduction in losses under non-uniform irradiance conditions, which may be expected during operation in the final application. In the final presentation of this work, we will present the interconnection between minimodules measured under high irradiance and non-uniform conditions, where the bypass diodes will play a crucial role. Also, we will show the mechanical characterization of back-side-soldered cells, focusing on comparing void ratios between the metallic surfaces of the Ge cells and the DBC substrate, along with the thermal characteristics of the mini-modules.

ACKNOWLEDGMENT

This work has been partially funded by the project GETPV (PID2020-115719RB-C22) and the project THERMOBAT, which has received funds from European Commission under grant agreement 10105754. The sole responsibility for the content of this publication lies with the authors. It does not necessarily reflect the opinion of the European Union. Neither the REA nor the European Commission is responsible for any use that may be made of the information contained therein. The authors acknowledge Dr. David Lackner and Dr. Frank Dimroth, from Fraunhofer-ISE, for the development of the epitaxial structures that were used to manufacture the Ge bypass diodes. Ignacio Izquierdo acknowledges the Comunidad de Madrid for financial support through the program of Industrial Doctorates (IND2022/AMB-23530).

REFERENCES

- [1] J. van der Heide et al., "Cost-efficient thermophotovoltaic cells based on germanium substrates", *Solar Energy Materials and Solar Cells*, vol. 93, issue 10, oct. 2009, doi: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.solmat.2009.06.017>.
- [2] J. Fernandez, «Development of Crystalline Germanium for Thermophotovoltaics and High-Efficiency Multi-Junction Solar Cells».
- [3] A. Datas et al., "Development and experimental evaluation of a complete solar thermophotovoltaic system", *Progress in Photovoltaics: Research and Applications*, vol 21, issue 5, apr. 2012, doi: <https://doi.org/10.1002/pip.2201>.

Experimental Investigation of Improving Thermophotovoltaic Energy Conversion via Photon Recycling with Ellipsoidal Optical Cavities

Nima Talebzadeha, Shahryar Homaei, Keshav Ramparsad, and Paul G. O'Brien

Department of Mechanical Engineering, York University, Toronto, Ontario, M3J 1P3, Canada.

Abstract — Thermophotovoltaic (TPV) systems convert thermal energy into electricity through the interaction of photons with a photovoltaic (PV) cell. Understanding the fate of photons is crucial for optimizing the system's efficiency and overall performance. In this study a parametric analysis about the effect of photon fates in a GaSb-based TPV system is carried out and subsequently the experimental results prove the importance of photon fate analysis and using ellipsoidal optical cavities to significantly control the photon fates and enhance the system performance. In the experiments, different radial sizes of silver-coated glass plates are used to analyze different photon fates and show the effect of recycling factors. Results show that there is an optimum value for the maximum useful power delivered to PV cell which can be achieved by using a well-designed optical cavity. The experiments show that by increasing the radial size ratio of the silver coated glass from $\omega/a = 0$ to 0.8, the maximum output power and system efficiency increases by 270 times (from 0.113 mW to 3.27 mW). In conclusion, a well-designed optical cavity in advanced TPV systems can bring their performance closer to the high theoretical efficiencies they are capable of.

I. INTRODUCTION

Thermophotovoltaic (TPV) technology offers a promising route for direct conversion of radiant heat into electricity using photovoltaic (PV) cells. Recent advancements have yielded TPV systems achieving a record power conversion efficiency of 40% [1]. This achievement involved optimizing two-junction tandem III-V PV cells with bandgap energies (1.2 eV and 1.4 eV) that were strategically aligned with the emission spectra from an emitter operating in the temperature range of 1900-2400 °C. Motivated by the significant gap between current efficiencies and theoretical limits, intense research and development efforts are underway to push TPV systems towards achieving 50% efficiency [2]. Realizing this ambitious goal holds immense potential for TPV technology.

The main components in a TPV system are the emitter and the PV cell (Fig. 1). Photons from the thermal emitter are converted to electric power within the PV cell. However, only photons absorbed by the PV cell can be converted to electric power. Further, the energy of the photons absorbed by the PV cell must be greater than its band-gap. When the energy of photons absorbed by the PV cell is greater than its bandgap the excess energy is converted to thermal energy, which heats the PV cell and reduces its efficiency. Moreover, not all emitted photons are absorbed by the PV cell. In this regard, understanding and managing the fate of photons in a TPV system is crucial for optimizing the system's performance. The

process by which photons are managed within a TPV system involves several key stages, from their generation to their eventual conversion into electrical energy or loss mechanisms. Photon fate analysis guides advancements in material selection, emitter design, and spectral filtering, ultimately leading to higher power conversion efficiencies and realizing the full potential of TPV technology. Although optical cavities are powerful tools for controlling photon fate and significantly increasing system capabilities, they have been rarely studied [3]. Our recent research demonstrated that spheroidal structures as optical cavities significantly enhance the control of the photon behavior, thereby offering substantial improvements to the performance of TPV systems [4-6].

Fig. 1 illustrates the typical photon fates in a TPV system. It includes F_{elc} : The portion of photons captured and converted by

Fig. 1. An overview of the typical photon fates in a TPV system.

the PV cell into electricity; F_{recy} : The portion of photons reflected back to the emitter (referred as recycled); F_{vf} : The emitted photons lost due to non-unity view factor; and F_{th} : The portion of emitted photon energy absorbed by the PV cell but lost through thermalization. In this paper a numerical analysis on the probable photon fates in a TPV system is parametrically studied and subsequently experiments are carried out to show the effect of photon recycling and controlling the photon fates using a semi-ellipsoidal specular optical cavity.

II. METHODS TO INVESTIGATE THE EFFECT OF PHOTON FATES

The ultimate goal of a TPV system is to maximize the number of photons absorbed by the PV cell that have optimal energy, which is slightly greater than the bandgap of the PV cell (here is $E_g = 1.7 \mu\text{m}$ for GaSb TPV cell). The target is to 1) Increase F_{recy} to increase the temperature of the emitter and the number

of photons with energy greater than the bandgap of the PV cell (referred to as in-band photons); 2) Increase the view factor between the emitter and PV cell, which decreases view factor losses (F_{VF}) and increases output electricity (F_{elc}). For example, according to the energy balance shown in (1), by increasing the recycling factor (F_{recy}) the temperature of the emitter increases (T^*) and more in-band photons are generated which can result in an increase in F_{elc} . However, increasing F_{recy} decreases the total portion of the photons delivered to the PV cell ($F_{elc} + F_{th}$).

$$P_{in} = \int_0^{\infty} \varepsilon_0 (1 - F_{rec}(\lambda)) E_{b\lambda}(\lambda, T^*) d\lambda \quad (1)$$

where, P_{in} is the input power emitted from the emitter, ε_0 is the emissivity of the emitter, $E_{b\lambda}$ is the blackbody spectral emissive power at elevated temperature of T^* due to photon recycling.

In the experiment, a hemi-ellipsoidal specular reflector optical cavity (Optiforms[®]) is used to concentrate the emitted light from a Zirconia micro heater (IST[®]) placed at its focal point. A GaSb PV cell (JX-Crystal[®]) is placed on the minor axis and a silver-coated glass with an aperture is placed on the PV cell. Fig. 2a shows the concept of the test setup and Fig. 2b shows the experimental setup.

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Fig. 2. a) The concept of a semi-ellipsoidal optical cavity to study the photon fate in the TPV system, b) Experimental setup.

Fig. 3 shows results from the parametric numerical analysis for the in-band (useful) power delivered to the GaSb PV cell for three blackbody thermal emission input powers of $P_{in} = 1, 5,$ and 10 W/cm^2 as a function of the photon recycling factor range $0 < F_{rec} < 0.99$. In this case the view factor loss is assumed to be constant at $F_{VF} = 0.01$. As shown in this figure, the maximum in-band power delivered to the PV cell has an optimum value when the photon recycling factor is $F_{rec} = 0.976, 0.966,$ and 0.958 for $P_{in} = 1, 5,$ and 10 W/cm^2 , respectively.

Table 1 shows the experimental results for the GaSb PV cell for different aperture sizes (different values of ω/a in Fig. 2a). As the size of the aperture decreases (corresponding to an increase in ω/a) the degree of photon recycling increases, which in turn increases the efficiency of the TPV system. Thus, the ellipsoidal optical cavity and aperture can be used to control the fate of photons from the emitter, and the performance of the TPV system.

Fig. 3. In-band power delivered to the PV cell as a function of F_{rec} when $F_{VF} = 0.01$, for three input powers.

TABLE I

SUMMARY OF THE EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS

Case	Reference ($\omega/a = 0$)	1 ($\omega/a = 0.2$)	2 ($\omega/a = 0.4$)	3 ($\omega/a = 0.6$)	4 ($\omega/a = 0.8$)
I_{sc} (mA)	4.2	4.46	5.9	10.75	23
V_{oc} (mV)	26.9	29.2	38	69	142
Efficiency enhancement (%)	0	15.3	98.4	556.5	2791

IV. CONCLUSION

This study demonstrated the significant role that ellipsoidal optical cavities play in enhancing the control of photon fates within TPV systems. Through detailed parametric analysis and experimental validation, we have demonstrated that employing semi-ellipsoidal specular optical cavities can markedly improve the efficiency and performance of TPV systems. Experimental results confirm that by manipulating the photon recycling factor and optimizing the geometry of optical cavities, it is possible to substantially increase the in-band power delivered to GaSb PV cells. Furthermore, our findings underscore the potential of advanced optical cavity designs in TPV, which could lead to more robust and higher-performing systems. These advancements hold promise for scaling TPV applications, making them more viable for diverse energy needs.

REFERENCES

- [1] A. LaPotin et al., "Thermophotovoltaic efficiency of 40%", *Nature*, vol. 604, n.o 7905, Art. n.o 7905, abr. 2022, doi: 10.1038/s41586-022-04473-y.
- [2] T. Burger et al "Present efficiencies and future opportunities in thermophotovoltaics", *Joule*. 2020 Aug 19;4(8):1660-80.
- [3] L. Weinstein et al., "Optical cavity for improved performance of solar receivers in solar-thermal systems," *Sol. Energy*, 69-79 (2014).
- [4] N. Talebzadeh et al., "Ellipsoidal optical cavities for enhanced thermophotovoltaics." *IEEE J. Photovolt.* 12.1 (2021): 353-363.
- [5] N. Talebzadeh et al., "Spheroid-based optical cavities for tunable photon recycling and emitter temperature control in robust solar thermophotovoltaic systems." *Journal of Photonics for Energy*. 2023 Jan 1;13(1):018501-.
- [6] N. Talebzadeh et al., "The effect of optical cavities on thermophotovoltaic systems." In AIP Conference Proceedings, vol. 2841, no. 1. AIP Publishing, 2023.

Evaluation of TPV devices in different irradiation environments

Naresh Das, Harry Hier, William Allmon, Sunny Karnani, and C. Mike Waits

U.S. Army Combat Capabilities Development Command, Army Research Laboratory, Adelphi, MD 20783, USA

Abstract: We report on the performance degradation of InGaAs-based TPV devices as a function of cell temperature when exposed to, either AM 1.5 Solar or a resistively heated gray-body irradiation source. The performance degradation is influenced by the irradiation source temperature due to bandgap narrowing, and dark current, which varies with substrate temperature. The spectral nature of the irradiation source must be considered when optimizing system output power and when evaluating the relative benefits of cooling cells to improve performance against allowing cells to operate at a higher temperature with a degraded output. Finally, we report the power degradation versus cell temperature for gray body emitters at different temperatures (thus different spectrums) typically found in highly reflective spectral control TPV systems which will aid system optimization efforts.

I. INTRODUCTION

There exists a great need for fuel agnostic compact power generation for many defense and commercial applications. Thermophotovoltaic (TPV) based devices represent a potential solid-state compact power generation strategy that functions on externally provided heat. Among various semiconducting materials, InGaAs-based TPV devices have superior conversion efficiency and a broad range of spectral absorption characteristics compared to other materials. For example, Narayan T.C. et al, recently reported record high TPV efficiencies greater than 30% [1]. When evaluated in a laboratory environment, thermophotovoltaic cell testing typically involves a concentrated optical source designed to mimic the Solar spectrum. Despite the difference in spectral character and incident flux, device performance when irradiated with different sources can be assumed approximately equivalent when short circuit currents, I_{sc} , are matched. However, we have done extensive evaluation of InGaAs TPV devices illuminated under various irradiation conditions. The TPV electrical output will degrade with substrate temperature, the result of a competition between an increase in short circuit

current due to bandgap narrowing and a drop in open circuit voltage due to temperature's influence on dark current [2].

II. RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

Antora Energy, Inc. supplied InGaAs lattice-matched to InP TPV devices (device area: 0.64 cm², Active Area: 0.56 cm²) are evaluated using two irradiation sources: a solar simulator (Oriol SOL3A 4X4 450W with AM 1.5 filter) and a resistively heated, highly emissive, SiN gray body emitter (characterized in-house, $\epsilon \approx 0.99$ between 0.5-5.5 μm). A Fresnel lens concentrates the solar irradiation to mimic fluxes relevant to TPV applications ($> 2 \text{ W/cm}^2$). TPV device operating temperatures are measured using a thermocouple, mounted between an alumina substrate and the TPV device. The three-component stack is mounted onto a temperature-controlled stage and current-voltage characteristics are measured using a Keysight 1501A curve tracer and Keithley 4460 source meter for currents below and above 1A, respectively.

The impact of substrate temperature (varied between 20°C and 50°C) on device response at different irradiation conditions (1.9 - 3.9 W/cm² of concentrated Solar and 1.6 - 4.2 W/cm² using the resistively heated SiN) is provided in Table 1 and Figure 1. Open circuit Voltages (V_{oc}) and Fill Factors (FF) decrease (negative values) with increasing substrate temperatures. Short circuit currents (I_{sc}), increase (positive difference values), but more so when exposed to a thermal source relative to Solar. Power degradation occurs in all the irradiation cases with increasing substrate temperature. The impact is most pronounced with the AM 1.5 Solar source (about 10%) relative to the resistively heated SiN source (3-4%). The degradation at 1200 C (Table 1) is less than 1100 C and it may be due to experimental error.

TABLE 1:
Change of device parameters from 20°C to 50°C under different irradiations conditions

Irradiation Source	V_{oc} change (-%)	I_{sc} change (+%)	FF change (-%)	Power change (-%)
Solar (1.9 W/cm ²)	8.0	0.8	3.65	11.8
Solar (3.9 W/cm ²)	7.7	3.92	5.2	9.1
SiN (1000°C)	8.0	11.3	4.5	2.2
SiN (1100°C)	7.7	9.43	5.6	4.65
SiN (1200°C)	7.4	9.25	4.3	3.2

Figure 1. Normalized power degradation versus substrate temperature.

Figure 2. Comparison of experimental short circuit current changes with temperature with single diode model data.

Experimental measurements are compared to a single diode model using parameters extracted from the cell, characterized in-house using various illumination conditions [3]. A J0P parameter is defined to estimate changes in dark current as a function of temperature and bandgap [4].

$$J_0 = J_0P * T^3 \exp\left(-\frac{E_g}{kT}\right) \quad (1)$$

A bandgap narrowing term from [5] is considered and quantum efficiency is adjusted by shifting the 0.74eV band edge accordingly. Short circuit current is determined by the in-band emission spectra and cell quantum efficiency. Figure 2 compares the change in I_{sc} with device operating temperature for experimental results with data from single diode modeling results. The alignment between experimental and numerical results suggests two key factors determine the degradation in electrical power output as a function of substrate temperature: Reverse saturation current (J_0) increases exponentially with temperature, negatively impacting open circuit voltage [4] and a narrowing bandgap with temperature that increases short circuit current as a larger portion of the emitter's emission

spectrum becomes available for conversion. The increase in current doesn't overcome the impact of reverse saturation current on voltage and so, on net, power degrades. The degradation in power is more pronounced when illuminated by a Solar spectrum as the marginal increase in energy available for conversion is smaller than the SiN thermal source, where peak emission is near the absorption band of the photocell. Similar results can be observed with the SiN emitter: at higher temperatures, degradation is greater as a function of substrate temperature. One can visualize this behavior by comparing the peak emission wavelength from Wein's law to the bandgap of the cell. The AM1.5 spectrum peak (~550 nm) is well below the lattice matched InGaAs band edge (1.67 μm). This difference in peak absorption may result in excess carrier generation due to solar irradiation (high energy photons) shifting further from the band edge which does not contribute to photo current and may further degrade the device performance.

Notwithstanding the discrepancy at higher SiN emitter temperatures (1200°C), there is good agreement between the experiments and single diode model in tracking the increase in short circuit current with device temperature (Figure 2). We suspect subtle changes in quantum efficiency as a function emitter temperature may be lost when extrapolating changes using a simple band edge shift play a role given the gradual change in spectrum intensity and emission peak over the SiN temperature range studied (1000°C-1200°C).

III. CONCLUSIONS

From Solar AM1.5 and thermal irradiation experiments and modeling, we find that TPV cell power degradation as a function of substrate temperature is strongly influenced by emitter temperature. The degradation due to solar irradiation is higher than the resistively heated gray-body irradiation (Table 1) for similar power generation level. Hence, we cannot simply extrapolate solar irradiation results for thermal irradiation TPV performance. Two primary factors determine the degradation rate: dark current, which degrades open circuit voltage, and bandgap narrowing, which increases short circuit current. Dark current wins out in the conditions evaluated, however, the rate is lowest at lower emitter temperatures. At a 1000°C emitter temperature, degradation rate is approximately 0.1%/°C. Our results show the irradiation spectrum should be considered when assessing the power lost due to high cell operating temperature versus the power lost and potential size and weight added to cool the cells.

REFERENCES:

- [1] Narayan T.C. et al, World record demonstration of >30% thermophotovoltaic conversion efficiency, IEEE PVSC conference proceedings, p. 1792, 2020
- [2] R. S. Tuleya and R. J. Nicholas, Band gap dependent thermophotovoltaic device performance using the InGaAs and InGaAsP material system, Journal of Applied Physics, 108, 084516, 2010.
- [3] E. Meyer. Extraction of saturation current and ideality factor from measuring Voc and Isc of photovoltaic modules. International Journal of Photoenergy, page <https://doi.org/10.1155/2017/8479487>, 2017.
- [4] Wojtczuk, S., InxGa1-xAs TPV experiment-based performance models. AIP Conference Proceedings, 358:387–393, 1996.
- [5] E. Zeilinski et al, Excitonic transition and exciton damping processes in InGaAs/InP, J. of Applied Physics, 59, 2196, 1986

Design strategies for very low bandgap InAs/InAsSb thermophotovoltaic cells

Basile Roux,^a Jean-Philippe Perez,^a Frédéric Martinez,^a Stéphanie Parola,^a Leire Del Campo,^b Lionel Cosson,^b Olivier Rozenbaum,^b Philippe Christol,^a Rodolphe Vaillon,^c

^aIES, Univ Montpellier, CNRS, Montpellier, France

^bCNRS-CEMHTI, UPR 3079, 1D Avenue de la Recherche Scientifique, Cedex 2, Orléans, France

^cLAAS-CNRS, Université de Toulouse, CNRS, Toulouse, France

Abstract — Ideally, very low bandgap (0.2 – 0.4 eV) thermophotovoltaic cells should be used to maximize electrical power, in particular for emitter temperatures below 1500°C. However, because of large recombination rates, this pathway is extremely difficult, in particular for the cells to operate at room temperature. In this work, we are exploring various design strategies for very low bandgap thermophotovoltaic cells using an InAs/InAsSb type II superlattice as the absorber layer. Design, fabrication and characterization of cells with various (barrier or p-i-n) structures and sizes, allow to extract pros and cons of the various strategies.

I. INTRODUCTION

Spectral selectivity is proven to be effective for maximizing conversion efficiency of thermophotovoltaic (TPV) devices. To achieve this, the two main approaches for minimizing the out-of-band net radiation power absorbed by the cell are to use a reflector at the back of the TPV cell or to minimize the out-of-band emissivity of the emitter. Another factor to be considered is the in-band thermalization loss caused by high-energy photons. The main strategy to minimize this thermalization loss is to use wide bandgap cells. The downside is that the electrical power density is far from optimum [1] (figure 1).

One solution is to operate with higher temperature emitters, with increasing difficulty in ensuring spectral selectivity and dissipating the heat generated in the TPV cell. The opposite solution, selected in this work, is to explore the feasibility of a very low bandgap (0.2 – 0.4 eV) TPV cell under the illumination of a lower temperature emitter (700-1000°C). However, the main challenge is to operate the cells at room temperature because of larger recombination losses.

Little work has been done on very low bandgaps TPV cells (cf. [2] and figure 1), compared with InGaAs (~0.73 eV) or GaSb (0.67 eV) cells. This could be explained in part by the fact that cells with very low bandgaps generate low voltages and high currents, leading to large series resistance losses. Carrier diffusion lengths are short if the cell is not cooled down to cryogenic temperatures. To address these problems, a solution was proposed by Huang et al. [3] based on interband cascade structures with an absorbing layer made of an InAs/GaSb type II superlattice (T2SL). Although some expected benefits of the

interband cascade structure were demonstrated, the presence of Ga-native defects was still limiting the diffusion length of the carriers. In this context, we are developing cells with an absorbing layer made of a similar - but Ga-free - InAs/InAsSb T2SL.

Fig. 1. Power output (p_{out}) colormap for a TPV device in the detailed balance limit, as a function of (blackbody) emitter temperature and cell bandgap. (E_g, T_e) points from ~30 experimental data from the literature are represented, but their position on the colormap does not reflect the real power output which was measured. Figure from [1].

II. CELL DESIGN, FABRICATION AND CHARACTERIZATION

A. InAs/InAsSb Type II superlattice

The T2SL is composed of successive periods of InAs and InAsSb strained-compensated layers. Minibands for electrons and holes are thus formed, along with an artificial bandgap (250 meV in our case) depending on the chosen period. The local separation between holes and electrons characteristic of the type II heterostructure InAs/InAsSb (cf. figure 2) helps to increase the carrier's lifetime, especially the Auger one, which is the limiting recombination factor at room temperature [4].

Fig. 2. Schematic band diagram of a few periods of the InAs/InAsSb superlattice absorber.

B. Barrier and PIN cell structures

Two cell structures were chosen in this work: a classical p-i-n junction, and a barrier structure (cf. figure 3) inspired by what is done in the infrared photodetector community [5]. The barrier structure already enabled to increase the operating temperature of the photodetectors thanks to the confinement of the electric field in the AlAsSb barrier layer and its supposedly auto-passivation properties, advantages that could also be beneficial for a TPV cell.

Fig. 3. Simulated band diagram (under 0.1 V) of a barrier structure and the corresponding stacking of layers.

Several configurations were considered for the barrier cell structure: different top contact layers (InAs/InAsSb SL or p-doped GaSb) having an impact on charge separation, and two sizes (photodetector-type circular micrometric cells or square centimetric cells with appropriate contact grid), having an impact on the proportion of surface recombination at the edges. Several batches for these various cells were fabricated using multiple clean room processing steps, including standard photolithography, metallization and mesa etching.

C. Electrical characterization

The cells were characterized in a Linkam stage by making 4-point-probe $I(V)$ measurements in the dark and under illumination, with cell temperature varying from 77 to 300 K. A $2 \times 2 \text{ cm}^2$ planar emitter has been specifically developed

using a patented industrial process. The coating of this emitter has an emissivity close to that of a blackbody (cf. figure 4) from 700°C to $\sim 1000^\circ\text{C}$ and over a wide spectral range. The distance between the cell and the emitter was adjusted to control the incident power density.

Fig. 4. Emissivity of the emitter used to characterize the cells as a function of temperature.

III. CONCLUSION

The possibility to develop very low bandgap InAs/InAsSb-superlattice based TPV cells is currently explored. In our work, several design strategies have been investigated: two structures (barrier and p-i-n), micrometer and centimeter sized cells, and various contact layers for the barrier cell structure. The results exhibit the advantages and disadvantages of the different designs, with in particular the observation of strong recombination currents in the micrometer-sized cells.

ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

The authors would like to thank Gérard Duneau from ITECH SYSTEM (Veuzain sur Loire, France) for designing and supplying the infrared emitters.

REFERENCES

- [1] B. Roux et al., "Main performance metrics of thermophotovoltaic devices: analyzing the state of the art", *Journal of Photonics for Energy*, vol. 14, n.o 4, article n.o 042403, 2024.
- [2] R.Q. Yang et al., "Narrow bandgap photovoltaic cells", *Solar Energy Materials and Solar Cells*, vol. 238, article n.o 111636, 2022.
- [3] W. Huang, "Enhanced collection efficiencies and performance of interband cascade structures for narrow bandgap semiconductor thermophotovoltaic devices", *Journal of Applied Physics*, vol. 124, n.o 2, article n.o 023101, 2018.
- [4] B.V. Olson et al., "Intensity-and-Temperature-Dependent Carrier Recombination in InAs/InAsSb type II Superlattices", *Physical Review Applied*, vol. 3, n.o 4, article n.o 044010, 2015.
- [5] P.C. Klipstein, "Perspective on III-V barrier detectors", *Applied Physics Letters*, vol. 120, n.o 6, article n.o 060502, 2022.

All-coupled evaluation for the thermophotovoltaic cell with selective emitter

Hongyu Pan, Xue Chen, Xinlin Xia*

School of Energy Science and Engineering, Harbin Institute of Technology, 92, West Dazhi Street, Harbin 150001, PR China

Abstract — Thermophotovoltaic (TPV) cells are highly sensitive to its thermal characteristics. A multi-field coupled model is used to evaluate the selective emitter performance from optical and thermal perspectives of TPV cells. Taking the typical GaSb TPV cell as example, with 1200 K blackbody emitter, there is a 4.6% error of the maximum output power. Where, the average cell temperature can reach 312.3 K at optimal voltage. Then, the TPV system with different emitter temperature are calculated and analyzed quantifiably. The error rises rapidly from 1.2% to 96.3% with 1000 K~ 2000 K emitter temperature. Finally, the effects of selectivity of emitters on the TPV performance are discussed and evaluated quantifiably. When the bandwidth of unity emissivity is 300 nm, the efficiency reaches a peak of 16.63%. Compared with the uncoupled model, the peak performs a striking decrease and blueshift from 900 nm to 1000 nm.

I. INTRODUCTION

As a static power generation technology revived in recent years, thermophotovoltaic (TPV) technology has once again set off a research boom for high-efficiency thermal radiation generations [1, 2]. Recently, advances in nanofabrication technology have given new vitality to TPVs. Benefiting from this, research works progressively emerge on high-efficiency selective emitters and novel TPV cells [3, 4]. Whereas, the expensive experimental cost is a practical challenge, which can be coped with the precise guidance protocol. Theoretically speaking, there is a process of mutual conversion and transportation of light, electricity, and heat within the TPV system where these energies are tightly coupled [5]. Considering the balance between computational cost and research objectives, various reported research efforts simplify the energy flow in the TPV cell according to their targets [6-8].

In principle, the study on the opto-electrical conversion in TPV cells originated from that on solar cells. In recent decades, the thermal effects in photovoltaic cells attracted the attention of researchers. Li and his team proposed an opto-electrical-thermal model for the solar cell based on the carrier dynamic theory and supplemented the thermal analysis [9, 10]. By analogy, TPV cells face more severe thermal effects has been noticed by some researchers. Vaillon et al. [11] presented the opto-electrical analysis for the self-developed InSb TPV cell considering the temperature influence. Subsequently, they analyzed the thermal behavior of the GaSb TPV cell from a thermodynamic view by their energy loss model based on the semi-experimental diode theory [12]. The results revealed the internal temperature characteristics of the cell and an external

improvement of radiative cooling was proposed to weaken the temperature influence. Differing from solar cells, the more severe thermal effects in TPV cells mean that the changed cell temperature characteristics will lead to larger simulation errors with the isothermal model.

In this paper, a coupled opto-electro-thermal model is used to analyze the thermal and opto-electrical characteristics of the typical GaSb TPV cell. The improvement of ideal selective emitter is evaluated from different optical, electrical and thermal views respectively.

II. PHYSICAL AND MATHEMATICAL MODEL

A pn junction GaSb TPV cell is adopted in this paper as shown in follows. The radiation source is assumed as ideal blackbody emitter of 1200 K. A pn junction GaSb TPV cell is adopted as shown as follows. The reflection at cell surface is considered, and the absorption is simplified as exponential attenuation along the cell thickness according to the Beer law.

Fig. 1. Graphs of (a) physical model and (b) various heat generations in the TPV cell.

The drift-diffusion-Poisson equation and Fourier's conduction equation are used as the control equation of this coupled simulation where various heat generations are considered as the internal heat source.

$$\begin{cases}
 G(x) = \int_0^{\lambda_{0s}} g(x, \lambda) d\lambda = \int_0^{\lambda_{0s}} \alpha(\lambda)(1-R(\lambda))I_0(\lambda) \frac{hc}{\lambda} e^{-\alpha(\lambda)x} d\lambda & (1) \\
 \nabla \cdot [D_p \nabla p(x) + p(x)D_{p,T} \nabla T(x) + p(x)\mu_p(\phi + \chi + E_g - \frac{k_B T(x)}{q} \ln(N_v))] + G_p(x) - U_p(x) = 0 \\
 \nabla \cdot [-D_n \nabla n(x) - n(x)D_{n,T} \nabla T(x) + n(x)\mu_n(\phi + \chi + \frac{k_B T(x)}{q} \ln(N_c))] + G_n(x) - U_n(x) = 0 \\
 \nabla^2 \phi(x) = -\frac{\rho(x)}{\epsilon_0 \epsilon_r} = -\frac{q[n(x) - p(x) + N_D - N_A]}{\epsilon_0 \epsilon_r} \\
 \nabla \cdot [\lambda_c \nabla T(x)] - P_{H, total}(x) = 0 \\
 P_{H, total}(x) = P_{Th}(x) + P_{Pel}(x) + P_{sol}(x) + P_{sur} + P_{Aug}(x) + P_{SRH}(x) + P_{rad}(x)
 \end{cases}$$

In the domain, charge contacts of the cell are assumed, which are assumed as ohmic one. The natural air cooling is settled on top surface of the cell, and there is forced water cooling of 300

W/(m²·K) on the bottom surface. The thicknesses of different junctions are $L_A=0.4 \mu\text{m}$ and $L_D=10 \mu\text{m}$, and the doping concentrations of the cell are $N_A = 1 \times 10^{18} \text{ cm}^{-3}$, $N_D = 1 \times 10^{17} \text{ cm}^{-3}$. The other parameters are the relative dielectric constant $\epsilon = 15.7$, the band gap $E_g = 0.726 \text{ eV}$ and the electron affinity $\chi = 4.06 \text{ eV}$. The initial cell temperature is 300 K.

III. RESULT AND DISCUSSION

The temperature distribution along the voltage and the depth in the cell is shown in Fig. 2(a). The minimum temperature occurs at the voltage corresponding to the maximum output power ($P_{m,\text{out}}$, V_{op}) and the temperature monotonically drops with depth. Detailly, in Fig. 2(b), it can be seen that the average temperature (T_{ave}) exhibits a minimum of 312.3 K along the voltage. The decline rate of T_{ave} remains almost constant before V_{op} and then T_{ave} spikes to 316.3 K. At three typical voltages of 0 V, $V_{\text{op}}=0.3 \text{ V}$, $V_{\text{OC}}=0.37 \text{ V}$, the temperature variation along with the depth in the cell is illustrated in Fig. 2(b).

Fig. 2. Diagram of cell temperature along the voltage and thickness.

In the prototype case ($T_e=1200 \text{ K}$), $P_{m,\text{out}}$ increases from 1460.7 W/m^2 to 1530.7 W/m^2 ($\sim 4.6\%$), accompanied by an decrease in V_{op} from 0.315 V to 0.3 V . As the emitter temperature (T_e) rises from 1000 K to 2000 K , it can be seen that the difference rises rapidly from 1.2% to 96.3% . In addition, the average cell temperature (T_{ave}) exponentially rises from 301.2 K to 788.8 K while the temperature difference presents a logarithmic increase.

Fig. 3. (a) The difference of $P_{m,\text{out}}$ with rising T_e , and (b) the average temperature and difference in the TPV cell.

Fig. 4. Illustration of $P_{m,\text{out}}$ and T_{ave} with different selective emitters.

Then, the ideal selective emitter with unity emissivity in band of specific width ($\Delta\lambda$) from bandgap. With the increase of $\Delta\lambda$, the output power rises. When the bandwidth of unity emissivity exceeds 600 nm , the output power almost keeps at similar level. While, the efficiency presents a peak at $\Delta\lambda=1000 \text{ nm}$. Compared with the uncoupled model, the peak performs a striking decrease and blueshift (from 900 nm to 1000 nm).

IV. CONCLUSION

In the prototype case where the emitter is 1200 K , there is a 4.6% error between the coupled case and the isothermal cell case (300 K). The reason is that various thermal effects heat the cell to above 312.3 K . With rising emitter temperature ($1000 \text{ K} \sim 2000 \text{ K}$), the error increases from 1.2% to 96.3% . In addition, the cell temperature exponentially rises from 301.2 K to 788.8 K . When the bandwidth of unity emissivity is 1000 nm , the efficiency reaches a peak of 16.63% .

REFERENCES

- [1] D.M. Bierman, et al., "Enhanced photovoltaic energy conversion using thermally based spectral shaping", *Nature Energy*, vol. 1, n.o 16068, Art.n.o 16068, may 2016, doi: 10.1038/nenergy.2016.68.
- [2] A. LaPotin et al., "Thermophotovoltaic efficiency of 40%", *Nature*, vol. 604, n.o 7905, Art. n.o 7905, abr. 2022, doi: 10.1038/s41586-022-04473-y.
- [3] T.J. Coutts, "A review of progress in thermophotovoltaic generation of electricity", *Renewable & Sustainable Energy Reviews*, vol. 3, may. 2000, doi: 10.1016/S1364-0321(98)00021-5
- [4] A. Datas, et al., "Development and experimental evaluation of a complete solar thermophotovoltaic system", *Progress in Photovoltaics: Research and Applications*, vol. 5, n.o 21, apr. 2013, doi: 10.1002/pp.2201
- [5] C. Ungaro, et al., "Solar thermophotovoltaic system using nanostructures", *Optics Express*, vol. 23, n.o 19, aug. 2015, doi: 10.1364/OE.23.0A1149.
- [6] N.A. Pfister, et al. "Selective emitters for thermophotovoltaic applications", *Physica Status Solidi (a)*, vol. 214, n.o 214, nov. 2017, doi: 10.1002/pssa.201600410.
- [7] W. Shockley, et al., "Detailed balance limit of efficiency of p-n junction solar cells", *Journal of Applied Physics*, vol. 32, n.o 3, may. 1961, doi: 10.1063/1.1736034.
- [8] A. Datas, et al., "Detailed balance analysis of solar thermophotovoltaic systems made up of single junction photovoltaic cells and broadband thermal emitters". *Solar Energy Materials and Solar Cells*, vol. 94, n.o 12, jul. 2010, doi: 10.1016/j.solmat.2010.06.042.
- [9] A. Shang, et al., "Photovoltaic Devices: Opto - Electro - Thermal Physics and Modeling", *Advanced Materials*, vol. 29, n.o 8, Art. n.o 1603492, dec. 2017, doi: 10.1002/adma.201603492.
- [10] Y. An, et al., "Heterojunction perovskite solar cells: opto-electro-thermal physics, modeling, and experiment", *ACS Nano*, vol. 14, n.o 4, apr. 2020, doi: 10.1021/acsnano.0c01392.
- [11] E. Blandre, et al., "New insights into the thermal behavior and management of thermophotovoltaic systems", *Optics Express*, vol. 27, n.o 25, nov. 2019, doi: 10.1364/OE.27.036340.
- [12] O. Dupré, et al., "A full thermal model for photovoltaic devices", *Solar Energy*, vol. 140, nov. 2016, doi: 10.1016/j.solener.2016.10.033.

Interdigitated Back Contacted c-Ge thermophotovoltaic devices

M. Gamel^a, G. Rivera^a, G. López^b, M. Garín^c, I. Martín^a

^a Departament d'Enginyeria Electrònica, Universitat Politècnica de Catalunya, C/Jordi Girona 1-3, Mòdul C4, 08034, Barcelona, Spain.

^b Departament d'Enginyeria Gràfica i de Disseny, Universitat Politècnica de Catalunya, Av. Diagonal 647 edifici H, 08028, Barcelona, Spain.

^c GR-MECAMAT, Department of Engineering, Universitat de Vic – Universitat Central de Catalunya, C/de la Laura 13, 08500, Vic, Spain.

Abstract — Interdigitated Back Contacted (IBC) c-Ge cells are a cost-effective approach to thermophotovoltaic devices. Our research group has developed electron (n-type nanocrystalline silicon layers) and hole (laser processed Al₂O₃/SiC film stack) selective contacts that can be applied to IBC structures. Due to the complexity of the architecture, in this abstract we show 3-D simulation results that explore the effect of the different contact geometries which enables efficiencies in the range of 12-13 %. The optimized geometry will be used in fabricated devices whose performance will be hopefully reported in the conference.

I. INTRODUCTION

It is well known that the cost per watt (€/W) in thermophotovoltaics is the most important limitation to make this technology industrially appealing. To reduce it, two main strategies can be followed: the reduction of fabrication cost per device area (€/cm²) and the increase of the extracted electrical power density (W/cm²).

In this work, we focus on Interdigitated Back Contacted (IBC) thermophotovoltaic devices based on crystalline germanium (c-Ge) substrates which combine both approaches. On the one hand, c-Ge is a low bandgap material which is a cost-effective alternative to the typical III-V semiconductors [1]. Additionally, the proposed technology to fabricate these devices avoids the use of epitaxial growth which also helps in device cost reduction. On the other hand, the IBC architecture has several advantages to increase the power density. The absence of front metallization maximizes the photons introduced in the device increasing the extracted current. Moreover, the flat front surface paves the way to near-field solutions where the thermal emitter is located over the device at distances shorter than the emitted wavelengths (typically well below 1 μm) [2]. Finally, IBC structure enables a dense compaction of the cells in the thermophotovoltaic module. As the contacts are at the rear surface, the connection between cells can be done through the rear backsheet leaving negligible space between them. Notice that this photovoltaic inactive space can be a strong limitation in module power density.

In this abstract, we show 3-D simulations results using Silvaco ATLAS in order to understand the key parameters of the architecture and determine potential efficiencies of the forecasted devices. Based on these results, in the next months we plan to fabricate IBC c-Ge thermophotovoltaic devices whose results will be hopefully presented at the conference.

II. DESCRIPTION OF THE SIMULATION MODEL

In figure 1, we show the structure of the simulated device based on technologies developed by our research group on p-type c-Ge substrates. In particular, in the simulations we use two different acceptor densities $2.5 \cdot 10^{15}$ and $2.5 \cdot 10^{16}$ cm⁻³ (corresponding to resistivities of about 1.2 and 0.13 Ω·cm, respectively) which are the substrates used to develop the technology supporting the simulations. Moreover, they cover a doping range with relatively low free carrier absorption, improving the recycling of out-of-band photons [3].

As we can see, most of both surfaces are covered by a dielectric passivation based on Al₂O₃/SiC stack where the selective contacts are defined. This dielectric passivation has demonstrated a surface recombination velocities of 9 and 40 cm/s in 1.2 and 0.13 Ω·cm substrates, respectively [4]. This excellent passivation has been introduced into the simulations.

Fig. 1. Simulated structure.

Focusing on their geometry, the electron selective contacts are defined as lines opened onto the dielectric where a n-type nano-crystalline silicon layer is deposited and capped by aluminum fingers that fully cover them. The electrical quality of this contact shows a saturation current density of density of $1.45 \mu\text{A}/\text{cm}^2$ (corresponding to an open-circuit voltage at AM1.5g 1 sun-illumination of about 265 mV) and a contact resistivity of $10^{-4} \Omega\text{cm}^2$ [5]. On the other hand, the hole selective contacts are point-like contacts defined as $10 \mu\text{m}$ side squares resembling the contacts obtained through laser processing the Al₂O₃/SiC films where a contact recombination velocity of 1700 cm/s and a contact resistivity of $5.7 \cdot 10^{-5} \Omega\text{cm}^2$ are experimentally determined [4]. These contacts are interconnected by $20 \mu\text{m}$ wide aluminum fingers. As thermal emitter, we use a black body at 1473 K with a view factor of

0.2, leading to 5.32 W/cm² power impinging on device surface. The photogeneration in the c-Ge is calculated by raytracing module provided by Silvaco ATLAS. Finally, we include the resistance related to a grid of 11 μm thick aluminum film where a triangular current distribution along the fingers is considered.

III. SIMULATION RESULTS

As a first approach, we explore the effect of the width of the electron selective contact (W_{ESC}). The electrical (P_{el}) is shown in figure 2.(a). Additionally, we experimentally measured the reflectance and transmittance in the range of $\lambda = 0.3-15 \mu\text{m}$ for the three film configurations that can be found at the rear surface. With this information, we can calculate the reflected (P_{ref}) and transmitted (P_{trans}) power of the simulated devices, whose results are shown in figure 2.(b), by applying the percentage of the rear surface covered by every configuration. Finally, with this information a preliminar efficiency can be calculated, which is shown in figure 2.(c).

Fig. 2. Effect of the width of the electron selective contact on (a) electrical power; (b) reflected and transmitted power; (c) efficiency.

As we can see, the wider the ESC, the less electrical power extracted. This is mainly linked to the decrease in V_{oc} and FF which is attributed to a higher surface recombination (part of the excellent dielectric passivation is replaced by a selective contact) and a longer horizontal hole current path, i.e. higher parasitic series resistance, to find the hole selective contacts whose periodicity increases. Regarding transmitted and reflected powers, longer W_{ESC} leads to better rear reflectance and, more importantly, less percentage of area without metal, i.e. less transmitted power. Consequently, efficiency shows a maximum in the range of $W_{ESC} = 50-100 \mu\text{m}$, with higher values for the 1.2 Ωcm material due to higher P_{ref} .

In figure 3, we show the impact of the distance between HSC (laser pitch, p_L) along the fingers maintaining W_{ESC} to 20 μm.

Fig. 3. Effect on the laser pitch of the hole selective contacts on (a) the electrical power and (b) efficiency.

Focusing on the P_{el} , an optimum pitch in the range of 100-150 μm is observed for the 1.2 Ωcm material due to the trade-off between V_{oc} , which increases due to the reduction of carrier recombination, and FF , which decreases due to a higher parasitic series resistance. On the other hand, the 0.13 Ωcm material reduces P_{el} with longer pitches because the increase in V_{oc} is not enough to compensate the loss in FF . In this case, the reflected power does not depend on the laser pitch (same metal grid) and the P_{el} trend is transferred to efficiency with higher values for the 1.2 Ωcm due to higher reflected power.

These simulations point out to feasible geometries of the IBC cells that will be applied to the fabricated devices whose performance will be hopefully presented in the conference.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

This work is part of projects PID2020-115719RB-C21 (GETPV) and TED2021-131778B (TROPIC) by MCIN/AEI/10.13039/5011000110033. Project TED2021-131778B (TROPIC) is also funded by European Union “NextGenerationEU”/PRTR.

REFERENCES

- [1] J. van der Heide et al. “Cost-efficient thermophotovoltaic cells based on germanium substrates” *Solar Energy Materials and Solar Cells* 93, 1810–1816 (2009).
- [2] Fiorino, A. et al. “Nanogap near-field thermophotovoltaics”, *Nature Nanotech* 13, 806–811 (2018).
- [3] H.B. Briggs, R.C. Fletcher, “Absorption of infrared light by free-carriers in germanium”, *Phys. Rev.* 91, 1342–1346 (1953).
- [4] M. Gamel et al. “Highly reflective and passivated ohmic contacts in p-Ge by laser processing of aSiC_x:H(i)/Al₂O₃/aSiC films for thermophotovoltaic applications” *Solar Energy Materials and Solar Cells* 265, 112622 (2024).
- [5] M. Gamel et al., accepted in 41st European Photovoltaic Solar Energy Conference and Exhibition, to be held in Vienna, Sept. 2024.

IR laser-fired contacts for rear surface of c-Ge TPV devices

G. Rivera^{1a)}, M. Gamel¹, G. López², M. Garín³ and I. Martín¹

¹Departament d'Enginyeria Electrònica, Universitat Politècnica de Catalunya, Barcelona, Spain.

² Departament d'Enginyeria Gràfica i de Disseny, Universitat Politècnica de Catalunya, Av. Diagonal 647 edifici H, 08028, Barcelona, Spain

³Department of Engineering, Universitat de Vic. Universitat Central de Catalunya (UVIC-UCC), Vic, Spain

^{a)} E-mail for correspondence: gerard.rivera@upc.edu

Abstract — This work explores the creation of laser-fired contacts (LFC) on p-type c-Ge substrates by applying an IR laser onto aluminum film which is point-like fired through a dielectric passivating film stack. The electrical performance of the contacts is characterized, leading to surface recombination velocity at the contact of 1075 cm/s and contact resistivity of $7.2 \cdot 10^{-5} \Omega\text{cm}^2$ with an average area of $2000 \mu\text{m}^2$, pointing out to the creation of p^+ regions in the germanium substrate with negligible damage. The resulting partially contacted surface has the potential to have simultaneously low surface recombination velocity and contact resistance. Moreover, the metal/dielectric/c-Ge stack is an excellent mirror for the out-of-band photons at the rear surface of the TPV device which is key for high efficiencies. We are currently fabricating TPV c-Ge devices, including this rear surface configuration whose performance will be reported in the conference.

I. INTRODUCTION

The recent advances in c-Ge dielectric passivation using aluminum oxide (Al_2O_3) films have opened the perspective for high-performance c-Ge TPV cells using partially contacted surfaces. In such configuration, the surface is excellently passivated by the dielectric film which is periodically opened to create contacts. Typically, a partially contacted structure can be achieved either by photolithography or laser process. While the former approach can produce contacts with minimal surface damage compared to the latter, the feasibility of the laser method and its ability to skip the photolithography processing steps makes it cost-effective and attractive for large-scale production, such as in PERC commercial c-Si solar cells [1]. Obviously, the choice of a laser source and optimization of process parameters is essential in implementing this approach.

In a previous work, our group targeted the creation of hole-selective contacts in p-type c-Ge by laser-processing a dielectric stack consisting of a-Si:H/ Al_2O_3 /a-SiC_x film stack using a UV 355nm laser source. Remarkable results were obtained, albeit limited by the shallowness of the p^+ regions that were obtained from the aluminum content of the Al_2O_3 films [2]. Shifting to longer laser wavelengths has the potential to penetrate deeper into the c-Ge substrate, which together with longer laser pulse durations can enable stronger and deeper p^+ regions, enabling low-resistivity and highly selective contacts.

In this study, we optimize the laser processing approach by using an IR laser emitting at 1064 nm. An aluminum buffer layer is deposited on top of the dielectric which allows to fine-tune the energy transferred to the material and acts as a source of dopant (laser-fired contact approach). **Figure 1** shows a

schematic representation of the process. Up to now, we have carried out morphological characterization of laser spots, confirming the Al dopant diffusion inside the contacted surface. Additionally, analytical models are used to characterize the electrical performance of the contacts in terms of their specific contact resistivity and surface recombination velocity.

Figure 1. Sketch of the laser-firing process applied to the rear surface of a TPV device.

II. EXPERIMENTAL

The wafers used in this work are 4-inch (100) p-type c-Ge, with a resistivity of $1.3 \Omega\text{cm}$ and a thickness of $175 \mu\text{m}$. The passivation is based on a a-Si:H/ Al_2O_3 /a-SiC_x stack, whose details can be found in reference [2]. PECVD (13.56 MHz, ElettoRava S.p.A) was used for the a-Si:H and a-SiC_x layers; while for the Al_2O_3 we used ALD (Savannah S200). Finally, the aluminum buffer layer was thermally evaporated. The laser used to create the p^+ regions is a Nd:YAG (StarMark SMP 100II Rofin-Baasel) working at 1064nm in pulsed mode. Laser frequency and pulse duration were fixed at 4 kHz and 400 ns, respectively. Effective lifetime measurements were made using the Sinton WCT-120 lifetime tester tool. The morphology and size of the contacts were examined using an optical microscope.

III. RESULTS

Different laser powers were tested under two aluminum thickness to delimit the range of reasonable contact areas with minimal substrate damage. SIMS and TEM measurements were performed inside one of the contacts to explore the Al diffusion and the crystal damage, respectively. **Figure 2** shows the SIMS Al signal profile exhibiting atom diffusion deep into the c-Ge substrate, while the TEM image comparison in **Figure 3** shows that the Ge crystallinity is greatly preserved in the process.

Figure 2. Aluminum signal in SIMS analysis performed inside a contact as a function of the contact depth for three different laser powers: 1240mW, 1340 mW and 1420 mW, respectively.

Figure 3. TEM images of the passivated surface before and after the laser-firing process. Image b) is taken inside a contact. The inset images show the Fourier transform of the crystal image and are used as a mean to assess the degree of crystallinity quality.

The specific contact resistance ρ_c was characterized by using the test structure of **Figure 4a**, where the resistance of square matrices with different number of contacts was linearly fitted to find the resistance of a single contact. Then, ρ_c was extracted from the Cox and Strack approximation [3]. The surface recombination velocity at the contact (S_{cont}) was characterized using the structure of **Figure 4b**, where the aluminum buffer layer is etched in order to obtain an asymmetrical surface passivation (i.e. the front surface has a higher recombination velocity by the contact contribution). The degradation of the passivation as a function of the contact pitch was fitted using Fischer's model [4], where S_{cont} is the only free parameter. The results of the optimization process can be seen in **Table 1**. Additionally, the data obtained for the case of laser processing the dielectric stack with the UV laser is also included. As we can see, despite the fact that the IR laser leads to bigger contact areas, we obtain similar ρ_c and lower S_{cont} compared to the UV laser, probably related to deeper p^+ regions.

Figure 4. Test structures used for the determination of the contact resistivity (a) and contact surface recombination velocity (b).

Table 1. Comparison of the electrical performance of the contacts between the UV laser source and the IR laser source after the optimization of the laser parameters.

	UV (355 nm)	IR (1064 nm)
Contact area (μm^2)	~60	~2000
ρ_c ($\Omega\cdot\text{cm}^2$)	$0.54 \cdot 10^{-4}$	$0.72 \cdot 10^{-4}$
S_{cont} (cm/s)	1700	1075

As reported in ref. [2], the combination of the dielectric stack with the aluminum film leads to reflectance in the range of 95% for the out-of-band photons. Given the excellent electrical and optical properties, we are currently fabricating TPV c-Ge devices with the rear surface scheme proposed hereby whose performance will be reported in the conference.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

This work is part of projects PID2020-115719RB-C21 (GETPV) and TED2021-131778B (TROPIC) by MCIN/AEI/10.13039/5011000110033. Project TED2021-131778B (TROPIC) is also funded by European Union "NextGenerationEU"/PRTR.

IV. REFERENCES

- [1] A. Blakers, "Development of the PERC Solar Cell," *IEEE J Photovolt*, vol. 9, no. 3, pp. 629–635, 2019.
- [2] M. Gamel *et al.*, "Highly reflective and passivated ohmic contacts in p-Ge by laser processing of aSiC_x:H(i)/Al₂O₃/aSiC films for thermophotovoltaic applications," *Solar Energy Materials and Solar Cells*, vol. 265, p. 112622, Jan. 2024.
- [3] R. H. Cox and H. Strack, "Ohmic contacts for GaAs devices," *Solid State Electron*, vol. 10, no. 12, pp. 1213–1218, Dec. 1967.
- [4] B. Fischer, "Loss Analysis of Crystalline Silicon Solar Cells Using Photoconductance and Quantum Efficiency Measurements [Thesis]." *Universität Konstanz*, 2003.

Electrical and Optical Performance of Epitaxial-free Low-doped Germanium Thermophotovoltaic Devices

M. Gamel¹, G. Rivera¹, A. M. Medrano², J. Villa², G. López³, P. García-Linares², A. Datas², M. Garín⁴ and I. Martín¹

¹ Departament d'Enginyeria Electrònica, Universitat Politècnica de Catalunya, Barcelona, Spain.

² Instituto de Energía Solar, Universidad Politécnica de Madrid, Madrid, Spain.

³ Departament d'Enginyeria Gràfica i de Disseny, Universitat Politècnica de Catalunya, Barcelona, Spain.

⁴ GR-MECAMAT, Department of Engineering, Universitat de Vic – Universitat Central de Catalunya, Vic, Spain.

Abstract — In this work, we explore the use of p-type low-doped crystalline germanium substrates, with acceptor densities of 2×10^{15} (LD) and $2 \times 10^{16} \text{ cm}^{-3}$ (HD), in epitaxial-free TPV devices. Front contact is based on a nc-Si(n) layer deposited by PECVD, while rear contact is created by direct evaporation of aluminium film on the c-Ge surface. Our characterization includes high-intensity flash $J-V$ measurements, suns- V_{oc} analysis, and FTIR reflectance. From the obtained results we can conclude that HD devices produce 5 times lower series resistance than LD ones, mostly related to the rear contact resistivity. Additionally, the IR reflectance of LD devices is $\sim 5\%$ higher than the HD counterparts, which is attributed to a lower free carrier absorption. Finally, the suns- V_{oc} analysis suggests that both types of devices are limited by poor passivation at the rear side. Currently, we are fabricating devices with a passivated rear surface combined with point-like contacts based on laser processing. This rear surface configuration will improve electrical and optical properties and their characterization will be reported in the conference.

I. INTRODUCTION

Crystalline germanium (c-Ge) has been regarded as a promising material for thermophotovoltaic (TPV) cells due to its cost-effectiveness compared to III-V materials like InGaAs or GaSb [1]. The best-performance c-Ge cells to date have predominantly employed epitaxial growth techniques. For instance, incorporating gallium arsenide or indium gallium phosphide has proven effective in creating high-performance electron-selective contact (ESC) [1]. Thus, developing Ge TPV cells using cost-effective methods remains a crucial effort in current research endeavors.

Our research focuses on utilizing free epitaxial fabrication techniques that can be implemented in industrial processes. This study emphasizes the utilization of a double-side-contacted c-Ge(p) TPV cell that features phosphine-doped nanocrystalline silicon (nc-Si(n)) as ESC developed by plasma enhanced chemical vapor deposition (PECVD). As a first approach, the rear contact is defined using an evaporated Al film directly contacting the c-Ge. The study will investigate the optical and electrical performance of two doping c-Ge(p) wafers, 2×10^{15} and $2 \times 10^{16} \text{ cm}^{-3}$.

II. EXPERIMENTAL

This study utilizes two p-type c-Ge(100) wafers with a resistivity, doping, and thickness of 1.2 and $0.13 \Omega\cdot\text{cm}$, 2×10^{15} and $2 \times 10^{16} \text{ cm}^{-3}$, and 155 and 175 μm , respectively. Initially,

the front side of the c-Ge wafer is cleaned by dipping them into diluted hydrofluoric acid (HF, 1%) for one minute, followed by a 30-second dip in DI water and a 3-minute dip in hydrochloric HCl:H₂O water at 1:1 ratio. PECVD is used to deposit $\sim 20 \text{ nm}$ nc-Si(n). Subsequently, the rear side of the wafer undergoes cleaning before being loaded into a homemade evaporator for the deposition of a $\sim 1 \mu\text{m}$ Al metal contact. After that, a thin ($\sim 15 \text{ nm}$) Indium Tin Oxide (ITO) is deposited by RF magnetron sputtering on the top of nc-Si(n), followed by the 2200 nm silver (Ag) metal grid, with a grid pitch of 75 μm . Fig.1(a) shows the developed structure.

Fig. 1. Ge cell Schematic in:(a). this work, and (b). future work.

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

A. Electrical performance

Fig. 2 shows the $J-V$ characteristics of the two devices. As we can see the maximum power produced by the c-Ge cell with a doping level of $2 \times 10^{16} \text{ cm}^{-3}$ is higher than that of $2 \times 10^{15} \text{ cm}^{-3}$. This is related to the low series resistance (R_s), which is ~ 5 times lower in the case of the $2 \times 10^{16} \text{ cm}^{-3}$. Since the front surface is the same, the most likely explanation for this difference is related to the rear Al/c-Ge(p) contact, which produces better contact resistance as doping increases.

Suns- V_{oc} measurements are conducted to further understand the current mechanisms in the devices. With this characterization technique, a dark pseudo $J-V$ characteristic can be obtained (assuming a linear relation between light intensity and short-circuit current density), where the R_s does not affect the measurement, enabling a wide voltage range where the exponential current mechanism is visible. This measurement is conducted at temperatures from 25 to 65 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ with 10 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ steps. The experimental data are fitted to an exponential trend described by the equation pseudo $J = J_o(T)[\exp(A(T) \cdot V_{oc}) - 1]$,

where $J_0(T)$ is the saturation current density, and $A(T)$ is the exponential factor. The Arrhenius plots of these parameters in Fig 3a and 3b reveal that $A(T)$ linearly increases with $1/k_B T$ with constant ideality factors of 1.019 and 1.021 and activation energies of 0.738 and 0.682 eV for the c-Ge(p) doping concentration of 2×10^{15} and 2×10^{16} cm^{-3} , respectively. This indicates that the current mechanism is dominated by recombination at the quasi-neutral region of c-Ge, which is attributed to the high rear surface recombination velocity at the Al/c-Ge(p) contact.

B. Optical performance

The optical properties of the Al back surface reflectance on the c-Ge cells, with different doping concentrations, are characterized using Fourier transform infrared (FTIR) spectroscopy, whose results are shown in Fig.4. The reflectance of the substrate doped at 2×10^{15} cm^{-3} is $\sim 5\%$ higher than that of the substrate doped at 2×10^{16} cm^{-3} . This difference may be attributed to free carrier absorption, which increases with higher doping concentrations [2].

Fig. 2. The JV characteristics of the investigated c-Ge TPV cells, representing the sun flash measurements at 55 and 70 suns for c-Ge doping of 2×10^{15} and 2×10^{16} cm^{-3} , respectively. The current densities are equated to the TPV radiation temperature of 1473 K based on the device *EQE*'s. Table summarizes the cell performances based on one-diode model. Inset shows the completed c-Ge cells.

From the presented results, we can conclude that device performance is limited by the simple rear contact of Al/c-Ge(p). Further improvements in the electrical and optical performance can be achieved through the integration of $\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3/\text{SiC}$ passivation with laser-processed hole selective contacts at the rear surface (see Fig. 1.(b)), as demonstrated in our prior studies [3]. For example, the reflectance is anticipated to improve to a range of 95% due to a better rear mirror. Furthermore, laser processing of the same dielectric stack will produce local hole-selective contact with lower recombination and R_s . The devices incorporating these advancements are presently undergoing refinement and will be showcased at the upcoming conference. Such structure will emphasize free epitaxial cost-effective

methods (via PECVD and laser) to achieve high-performance TPV cells with a high probability of large-scale production.

Fig. 3. Arrhenius plot of the saturation current density (J_0) and the prefactor of the exponent (A) for c-Ge devices with doping concentrations of (a) 2×10^{15} cm^{-3} and (b) 2×10^{16} cm^{-3} .

Fig. 4. Reflectance of sub-bandgap photons of the investigated c-Ge TPV cells measured by FTIR spectroscopy for doping of 2×10^{15} and 2×10^{16} cm^{-3} . The measurement is conducted without the front metal grid to reduce the scattering of photons.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

This work funded by the projects PID2020-115719RB-C21 and PID2020-115719RB-C22 (GETPV) and TED2021-131778B (TROPIC) by MCIN/AEI/10.13039/5011000110033. Project TED2021-131778B (TROPIC) is also funded by European Union "NextGenerationEU"/PRTR.

REFERENCES

- [1] Y. Kim et al., "Highly efficient epitaxial Ge solar cells grown on GaAs (001) substrates by MOCVD using isobutylgermane," *Sol. Energy Mater. Sol. Cells*, vol. 166, pp. 127–131, 2017.
- [2] H.B. Briggs, R.C. Fletcher, "Absorption of infrared light by free-carriers in germanium", *Phys. Rev.* 91, 1342–1346 (1953).
- [3] M. Gamel et al., "Highly reflective and passivated ohmic contacts in p-Ge by laser processing of aSiCx:H(i)/Al2O3/aSiC films for thermophotovoltaic applications," *Sol. Energy Mater. Sol. Cells*, vol. 265, 2024.

Revisiting the Role of Auger Recombination in Germanium Thermophotovoltaic Converters

Pablo Martín, Víctor Orejuela, Aitana Cano, Iván García, Ignacio Rey-Stolle

Instituto de Energía Solar, ETSI de Telecomunicación, Universidad Politécnica de Madrid, Madrid, Spain

Abstract — Germanium thermophotovoltaic converters (TPV) can be a cost-effective alternative for the introduction of the technology in the commercial market. However, the impact of Auger recombination is usually considered an unavoidable efficiency limiting factor at high irradiances for indirect band-gap semiconductors. In this work, we summarize the literature about Auger recombination in Ge and analyze its impact on a common highly doped ($3 \cdot 10^{17} \text{ cm}^{-3}$) p-type Ge TPV converter under high irradiance conditions ($J_{sc} \sim 5 \text{ A/cm}^2$). The recombination currents related to each mechanism under study (radiative, Shockley-Read-Hall, Auger and effective surface recombination) were simulated using SILVACO TCAD. The analysis shows that, although the impact of Auger recombination heavily depends on the value of the Auger coefficients used, the impact of this intrinsic recombination process seems to be secondary in current Ge devices.

I. INTRODUCTION

The interest in thermophotovoltaic (TPV) systems have been renewed during the last years as several new TPV applications have been proposed. Most of the state-of-the-art TPV converters have been based on III-V semiconductors. However, the elevated cost of this type of materials hampers their short-term commercial implementation. In this context, germanium-based TPV converters could offer a cost-effective alternative for the integration of the technology in the market, as it is a moderately priced and widely available material, and Ge wafers are already being used in other PV technologies, like space PV and concentration PV.

However, despite the economic attractiveness of Germanium for TPV, the impact of Auger recombination in limiting the achievable performance of these devices is often argued as an unsurmountable drawback. Of course, it is well reported that the V_{oc} (i.e. recombination losses) of silicon concentrator cells is limited by Auger losses [1]. As it will be shown in following sections, Auger recombination, being a three-particle process, increases as the cube of carrier concentration, and thus should become performance-limiting at the high current densities (i.e. carrier injection rates) expected in TPV applications. Even more so, this limitation should be more pronounced for indirect band gap semiconductors, as Ge, where radiative recombination plays a limited role and device thickness needs to be large to achieve full absorption.

However, the fact of the matter is that the literature available on the role of Auger recombination in germanium is far less abundant than that of silicon. The goal of this work is to revisit

the reported studies about Auger recombination in Ge and conclude whether it plays a significant role in TPV converters.

II. RECOMBINATION PROCESSES AND COEFFICIENTS IN GERMANIUM

The main recombination mechanisms in the bulk of a semiconductor can be divided in radiative, Shockley-Read-Hall (SRH) and Auger. In this work we will describe in some detail Auger recombination, whereas will only mention expressions to quantify all other mechanisms.

A. Auger recombination

The Auger recombination rate is obtained as follows [2]:

$$R_{Aug} = C_n(pn^2 - nn_i^2) + C_p(np^2 - pn_i^2) \quad (1)$$

where C_n and C_p are the auger coefficients for electrons and holes, and n_i is the intrinsic carrier concentration. The exact values of C_n and C_p in germanium are not clear, as Auger recombination can only be measured at high excitation levels, where it becomes a nonlinear process. Moreover, due to the steep excitation profiles in germanium the domain of excited carriers becomes a system of distributed parameters with nonlinear recombination and inhomogeneous injection. As a result, several authors have proposed different Auger coefficients for germanium. The most relevant ones found in literature are summarized in Table I.

Author	C_n [cm^6/s]	C_p [cm^6/s]
Y. P. Varshini [3]	$8.0 \cdot 10^{-32}$	$2.8 \cdot 10^{-31}$
R. Conradt et al. [4]	$1.0 \cdot 10^{-31}$	$1.0 \cdot 10^{-31}$
A. Vossier et al. [5]	$2.2 \cdot 10^{-30}$	$2.4 \cdot 10^{-31}$

TABLE I. Summary of the most relevant Auger coefficients reported for germanium.

To analyze the impact that this variation may have, we have selected for the simulations the minimum and maximum values reported for the Auger coefficient in Table I.

It is important to note that Auger recombination is greatly enhanced by the Coulomb interaction between electrons and holes, as electron density is significantly higher in the vicinity of holes, which accordingly increases the Auger recombination in the semiconductor and its corresponding coefficients [6]. However, the impact that this effect has at high injection levels is reduced, as the number of electron and holes become

comparable, resulting in a strong screening of the Coulomb forces between them [7]. Thus, in this work this effect is not taken into account.

B. Radiative recombination coefficients and SRH coefficients

For the sake of conciseness, the formulas used for to calculate the radiative recombination rate and SRH lifetimes are omitted in this abstract, but they could be found in [8] and [9], respectively. The complete formulas and the correspondent description will be included in the final paper, if accepted.

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The recombination current densities at the maximum power point ($J_{Rec,mpp}$) corresponding to each recombination mechanisms under study (including surface recombination) were simulated using SILVACO TCAD for a Ge TPV converter with a 140 μm thick, highly doped ($3 \cdot 10^{17} \text{ cm}^{-3}$) p-type base, and a 200 nm thick gallium-doped n-type emitter. In order to reproduce typical injection conditions, irradiance was adjusted to get a $J_{SC} \sim 5 \text{ A/cm}^2$. Simulations were carried out as a function of the front and rear effective surface recombination rates.

Fig. 1 and Fig. 2 show respectively the recombination current components for the minimum and maximum Auger coefficients presented in Table I as a function of the effective front surface recombination rate (S_{Front}). In both cases a constant effective rear recombination rate (S_{Rear}) of 10^4 cm/s was considered.

As expected, the value selected for the Auger coefficient heavily affects the impact of the Auger recombination, as its corresponding current doubles when using its maximum reported values. Nevertheless, in both figures the intrinsic recombination –i.e., the sum of Auger and radiative components– does not seem to be dominant, as SRH recombination currents are up to four times greater. Thus, we may conclude that the role of Auger recombination in Ge is secondary, even when considering high dopant concentrations and high injection levels.

Fig. 1. Recombination current components for $S_{Rear}=10^4 \text{ cm/s}$, $C_n=1.0 \cdot 10^{-31} \text{ cm}^6/\text{s}$, and $C_p=1.0 \cdot 10^{-31} \text{ cm}^6/\text{s}$ as a function of S_{Front} .

Fig. 2. Recombination current components for $S_{Rear}=10^4 \text{ cm/s}$, $C_n=2.2 \cdot 10^{-30} \text{ cm}^6/\text{s}$, and $C_p=2.4 \cdot 10^{-31} \text{ cm}^6/\text{s}$ as a function of S_{Front} .

Further data about the structure and characteristics of the Ge TPV converter under study, as well as further and more detailed simulation results and analysis will be included in the final paper, if accepted.

REFERENCES

- [1] M. J. Kerr, A. Cuevas, and P. Campbell, "Limiting efficiency of crystalline silicon solar cells due to Coulomb-enhanced Auger recombination," *Progress in Photovoltaics: Research and Applications*, vol. 11, no. 2, pp. 97–104, Mar. 2003, doi: 10.1002/pip.464.
- [2] J. Dziewior and W. Schmid, "Auger coefficients for highly doped and highly excited silicon," *Appl Phys Lett*, vol. 31, no. 5, pp. 346–348, 1977, doi: 10.1063/1.89694.
- [3] Y. P. Varshini, "Band-to-Band Radiative Recombination in Groups IV, VI and III-V Semiconductors (I) and (II)," *Phys. Stat. Sol.*, vol. 19, pp. 459–514, 1967.
- [4] R. Conradt and J. Aengenheister, "Minority Carrier Lifetime in Highly Doped Ge," *Solid State Commun*, vol. 10, pp. 321–323, 1972, doi: 10.1016/0038-1098(72)90016-6.
- [5] A. Vossier, B. Hirsch, and J. M. Gordon, "Is Auger recombination the ultimate performance limiter in concentrator solar cells?," *Appl Phys Lett*, vol. 97, no. 19, Nov. 2010, doi: 10.1063/1.3510474.
- [6] A. Hangleiter and R. Hacker, "Enhancement of Band-to-Band Auger Recombination by Electron-Hole Correlations," *Phys Rev Lett*, vol. 65, no. 2, 1990.
- [7] V. K. Khanna, "Physical Understanding and Technological Control of Carrier Lifetimes in Semiconductor Materials and Devices: A Critique of Conceptual Development, State of the Art and Applications," *Prog Quantum Electron*, vol. 29, pp. 59–163, 2005, doi: 10.1016/J.PQUANTELEC.2005.01.002.
- [8] D. K. Schroder, *Semiconductor material and device characterization*. IEEE Press, 2006.
- [9] E. Gaubas, J. Vanhellefont, E. Simoen, I. Romandic, W. Geens, and P. Clauws, "Carrier lifetime dependence on doping, metal implants and excitation density in Ge and Si," *Physica B Condens Matter*, vol. 401–402, pp. 222–225, Dec. 2007, doi: 10.1016/j.physb.2007.08.151.

Experimental Efficiency of 11.2 % in Germanium Thermophotovoltaic Devices

A. M. Medrano ^a, E. López ^a, Pablo García-Linares ^a, J. Villa ^a, G. Rivera ^b, M. Gamel ^b, G. López ^c, M. Garín ^d, I. Martín ^b, C. Cañizo ^a, A. Datas ^a

^a Instituto de Energía Solar, Universidad Politécnica de Madrid, Av. Complutense s/n, 28040, Madrid, Spain.

^b Departament d'Enginyeria Electrònica, Universitat Politècnica de Catalunya, C/Jordi Girona 1-3, Mòdul C4, 08034, Barcelona, Spain.

^c Departament d'Enginyeria Gràfica i de Disseny, Universitat Politècnica de Catalunya, Av. Diagonal 647 edifici H, 08028, Barcelona, Spain.

^d GR-MECAMAT, Department of Engineering, Universitat de Vic – Universitat Central de Catalunya, C/de la Laura 13, 08500, Vic, Spain.

Abstract — Germanium is a low cost alternative to the highly expensive III-V semiconductors commonly used on thermophotovoltaic (TPV) devices. Despite efficiencies up to 16.5 % have been theorized in previous works, no experimental efficiencies have been reported so far for germanium-based devices. In this work, we present the first TPV germanium efficiency measured in a high view factor calorimetry set up. Efficiencies and power densities up to 11.2 % and 1.43 W/cm² have been obtained using a graphite emitter heated at 1544 °C.

I. INTRODUCTION

The state of the art in TPV has pushed forward mainly in III-V materials, where efficiencies have been experimentally demonstrated to reach values slightly over 40 % [1]. Our approach aims to promote a more economically viable material, such as germanium (Ge). However, Ge presents important challenges, including surface passivation caused by its highly reactive surface, and its indirect bandgap which results in lower open circuit voltage vs. energy gap ratio compared to other materials. To address this, we have developed a PERC (Passivated Emitter Rear Contact) TPV cell structure integrating laser firing processing to simultaneously achieve low contact resistivity and surface recombination velocity on the rear surface, as well as a dielectric/metal back mirror to recycle unabsorbed radiation. Previous work has theorized a possible efficiency of 16.5 % by applying this approach [2].

In this work, we report a PERC Ge-based TPV cell with an efficiency and power density up to 11.2 % and 1.43 W/cm² when irradiated by a graphite emitter heated at 1544 °C. This result represents the first direct measurement of the efficiency of a Ge TPV [3].

II. METHODOLOGY

In this study, we initiated with 4-inch p-type crystalline Germanium (c-Ge) wafers oriented along the (100) plane with different doping concentrations (Sample 1 with $N_A=4\cdot 10^{17}$ cm⁻³ and sample 2 with $N_A=4\cdot 10^{16}$ cm⁻³). Sample 1 was used to develop a conventional Ge TPV cell that will be used as the baseline, whereas sample 2 was employed to develop an advanced PERC configuration. A cross-section of the fabricated devices can be seen in Fig. 1. Both samples underwent epitaxial growth of n-type GaAs/GaInP layers at Fraunhofer Institute for Solar Energy using metalorganic vapor phase epitaxy (MOVPE). The rear side of sample 2 was

passivated with a dielectric stack consisting of 2 nm of amorphous silicon carbide (aSiC_x:H) grown by plasma-enhanced chemical vapor deposition (PECVD) at 400 °C, followed by 50 nm of aluminum oxide (Al₂O₃) deposited via atomic layer deposition (ALD), and an additional layer of 45 nm thick amorphous silicon carbide (aSiC) at 370 °C. This stack enhances rear passivation while utilizing the Al₂O₃ layer as a dopant source for generating Laser Fired Contacts (LFC) [4]. This technique injects aluminum dopant into the substrate, forming a back surface field (BSF) of p+ germanium, providing low resistivity and highly reflective contacts. For this process, a Talon 355-6 Nd:YVO₄ laser emitting pulsed ultraviolet light at a wavelength of 355 nm has been used. The laser conditions are set at a frequency of 20 kHz and a diode intensity of 4 A, resulting in pulses of 9 ns. The emitting power fixed at 11 mW generated pulses with a fluence of 0.9 J/cm². The spot laser pattern, determined through previous electrical analysis, targeted a pitch of 60 μm separation with one pulse per spot.

Fig. 1. Device structures measured in the TPV setup. The gold electrodes incorporate evaporated AuGe/Ni/Au layers (85/25/100 nm) plus electroplated gold. The conventional device has an unpolished rear side, while the PERC device has both sides polished. The image is out of scale to simplify the view.

Finally, a metallization of 5 nm thick chromium layer for adhesion and a 200 nm thick gold layer of the entire rear surface was performed to interconnect all formed contacts and finalize the back surface reflector. For creating the front contacts to n-type GaAs, we deposited a metal stack of AuGe/Ni/Au layers, with thicknesses of 85 nm, 25 nm, and 100 nm, respectively, followed by electroplating to achieve a total metal thickness of

5 μm . Subsequently, mesa etching was performed to isolate the device. In the case of sample 2 a rapid thermal annealing (RTA) at 350 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ for 60 seconds was conducted to reduce contact resistivity and improve the electrical conductivity of the electroplated gold. The manufacturing of sample 1 could not incorporate this RTA step due to the very thin GaAs front contact layer that could not prevent shunting during the annealing. Finally, the GaAs contact layer was selectively removed in the PERC device (see fig.1 b) to enhance absorption in the in-band region of the device.

III. EXPERIMENTAL RESULT AND CONCLUSIONS

Both TPV cells are measured in the TPV set up described elsewhere [3] and the results are presented in Fig. 2. It is worth noting that the TPV cell efficiency shown in panel A is defined as $\eta_{TPV} = P_{el}/(P_{el} + Q)$, being P_{el} the electrical power density (panel B) and Q the heat dissipated in the cell (panel C).

Fig. 2 In this figure, all the experimental results obtained in the TPV set up are shown in comparison with the data available in green in [2].

The results (panel A) demonstrate significantly higher efficiency with the PERC structure compared to a conventional device. The higher efficiency of the PERC device is attributed to the higher output power (panel B) and the lower dissipated heat (panel C). The lower power of the conventional cell is attributed to the higher series resistance (R_s) with fitted values of 138.6 $\text{m}\Omega\text{cm}^2$, whereas the PERC design has 11.8 $\text{m}\Omega\text{cm}^2$. This can be seen as well in a decrease in fill factor (FF) at higher emitter temperature or, equivalently, high short circuit densities (J_{sc}), as depicted in panel E. The main reason for this higher resistance of the conventional cell is related to the incapability to conduct an RTA to improve the front contact, as explained in the methodology section. The lower heat

dissipation in the PERC design is due to the increased reflectivity, which is attributed to two factors: 1) lower substrate doping concentration, leading to reduced free carrier absorption, and 2) enhanced back surface reflector facilitated by the dielectric stack in combination with metallization. Additionally, this dielectric stack enhances the open circuit voltage (V_{oc}) to values comparable to the higher doping substrates by improving rear surface passivation [4] (panel D). The comparison with V_{oc} data from Jara et al [2], who used substrates with doping density in the range of 10^{17} cm^{-3} , suggests the potential for higher V_{oc} if rear passivation were implemented in our highly doped substrates. Panel F illustrates the J - V curve of both devices measured at an emitter temperature of 1390 $^{\circ}\text{C}$, revealing a low FF attributable to R_s .

The fabricated devices demonstrate the potential of the proposed PERC technology. A first loss analysis points out that the improvement of their efficiency would require the thinning of the substrate to minimize free carrier absorption and enhance the reflectance in this case. Future work will address the implementation of improved mirror designs and wafer thinning techniques applied to the PERC design with different wafer doping concentrations, with the final goal to boost the cell conversion efficiency beyond 20 % [5].

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

The THERMOBAT project received funds from European Commission under grant agreement 10105754. The sole responsibility for the content of this publication lies with the authors. It does not necessarily reflect the opinion of the European Union. Neither the REA nor the European Commission is responsible for any use that may be made of the information contained therein. The Spanish Research State Agency MCIN/AEI/10.13039/ 501100011033 is acknowledged for financial support through the projects PID2020-113533RB-C31 (GREASE), PID2020-115719RB-C21 (GETPV), PID2020-115719RB-C22 (GETPV) and TED2021-131778B (TROPIC). Project TED2021-131778B (TROPIC) is also funded by European Union "NextGenerationEU"/PRTR. The authors acknowledge Dr. David Lackner and Dr. Frank Dimroth, from Fraunhofer-ISE, for the development of the epitaxial structures that were used to manufacture the TPV cells.

References

- [1] A. LaPotin *et al.*, «Thermophotovoltaic efficiency of 40%», *Nature*, vol. 604, n.º 7905, pp. 287-291, abr. 2022, doi: 10.1038/s41586-022-04473-y
- [2] J. Fernandez, «Development of Crystalline Germanium for Thermophotovoltaics and High-Efficiency Multi-Junction Solar Cells».
- [3] E. López *et al.* «Thermophotovoltaic conversion efficiency measurement at high view factors», *Sol. Energy Mater. Sol. Cells*, vol. 250, p. 112069, ene. 2023, doi: 10.1016/j.solmat.2022.112069.
- [4] M. Gamel *et al.*, «Highly reflective and passivated ohmic contacts in p-Ge by laser processing of aSiC_x:H(i)/Al₂O₃/aSiC films for thermophotovoltaic applications», *Sol. Energy Mater. Sol. Cells*, vol. 265, p. 112622, ene. 2024, doi: 10.1016/j.solmat.2023.112622.
- [5] P. Martín *et al.*, «Device Architectures for Germanium TPV Cells with Efficiencies over 30%», en *2023 14th Spanish Conference on Electron Devices (CDE)*, Valencia, Spain: IEEE, jun. 2023, pp. 1-4. doi: 10.1109/CDE58627.2023.10339503.

GeSn Mid-Infrared Thermophotovoltaic Cells Monolithically Integrated on Silicon for Power Beaming and Heat Conversion

Grard Daligou¹, Richard Soref², Patrick Del Vecchio¹, Anis Attiaoui¹, Mahmoud R. M. Atalla¹ and Oussama Moutanabbir¹

¹Department of Engineering Physics, Ecole Polytechnique de Montral, Montral, Qubec, Canada

²Department of Engineering, University of Massachusetts Boston, Boston, MA 02125, USA

Abstract — An emerging family of semiconductors for mid-infrared thermophotovoltaic (TPV) is presented. To study the properties of TPV devices based on these materials, a theoretical framework based on the generalized transfer matrix method and the self-consistent resolution of the Poisson-current equation is developed to investigate the performance of GeSn-based TPV cells. Using this framework, power conversion efficiencies of up to 9% are predicted for $\text{Ge}_{0.83}\text{Sn}_{0.17}$ TPV cells under black-body radiation at temperatures in the 500-1500 K range. Preliminary experimental results will also be presented.

I. INTRODUCTION

Narrow bandgap thermophotovoltaic (TPV) cells have been the subject of extensive investigations motivated by their strategic importance in harvesting infrared radiations for heat waste conversion, portable devices, power beaming, and space applications [1], [2]. Recently, considerable endeavors have been dedicated to the advancement of mid-infrared TPV cells to leverage their several technological advantages such as the potential to exploit the atmospheric transparency windows for eye-safer energy beaming and the ability to generate energy from the substantial heat wasted by major industries. In fact, vital manufacturing sectors such as iron, steel, cement, glass, and metallurgy suffer large energy footprints exacerbated by heat losses at temperatures below 2000 K. An efficient absorption and conversion of black-body radiations emitted in this range requires semiconductors with a bandgap energy (E_g) smaller than ~ 0.7 eV. Compound semiconductors have been explored to implement both far-field and near-field sub-2000 K TPV cells reporting a measured efficiency in the 1-11% range, while theory hints to higher values reaching 24% [2]–[4]. However, the high cost associated with these technologies limits their broad adoption. A cost-effective and scalable alternative to compound semiconductor mid-infrared TPV materials would be the silicon-compatible narrow bandgap $\text{Ge}_{1-y}\text{Sn}_y$ semiconductors [5]. These group IV alloys are grown on large-diameter silicon wafers and can cover the entire mid-infrared range by increasing the Sn content. Indeed, the recent progress in their epitaxial growth led to the demonstration of a variety of monolithic mid-infrared emitters and detectors. Building on these achievements, herein we introduce $\text{Ge}_{1-y}\text{Sn}_y$ alloys to design silicon-integrated mid-infrared TPV cells and discuss their performance and its evolution as a function of the basic material properties.

II. DEVICE STRUCTURE AND THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

The proposed all-group IV mid-infrared TPV cells consist of a GeSn p-i-n heterostructure grown on a silicon wafer using a germanium interlayer - commonly known as virtual substrate. Fig. 1 shows a schematic illustration of the device structure. Note that the effects of the parasitic resistances are neglected in evaluating the device performance.

Furthermore, the adoption of the one-dimensional treatment is justified since the device dimensions are considered to be significantly larger than its total thickness. Consequently, the

Fig. 1. Schematic illustration of the proposed GeSn TPV cell

evaluation of the TPV cell's performance and electrical characteristics is achieved through the self-consistent solution of the steady-state coupled Poisson drift-diffusion equations. In the simulations of the optical behavior of the cell, with the calculation of parameters such as the generation rate $G(x)$ and the absorbance $A(x)$, the complete stack of layers is considered to describe both the front and back-side illumination. In this study, the light propagation through the different layers of the $\text{Ge}_{1-y}\text{Sn}_y$ TPV cells is investigated using the generalized transfer matrix method (GTMM) [6] thereby accounting for the incoherency of light in the structure, induced by the $500 \mu\text{m}$ Silicon substrate. Once both $G(x)$ and $A(x)$ are obtained, as first approximation, the simulations of the electrical characteristics of the device are restricted to the set of active layers, namely the p-i-n junction, and the metallic contacts (Fig. 1).

In photovoltaic devices with wide-bandgap materials, and especially Si solar cells, the impact of the intrinsic recombination mechanisms on the conversion efficiency was shown to be negligible [7]. However, for narrow-bandgap $\text{Ge}_{1-y}\text{Sn}_y$, depending on the material quality, these loss processes could be the most dominant. For that reason, the

established formalism accounts for Auger, Shockley-Read-Hall (SRH), and radiative recombination mechanisms. The overall non-radiative recombination rate is determined through the method delineated in [8]. As for the radiative recombination rate, instead of relying on a constant bimolecular recombination coefficient B , which is primarily accurate for weakly injected non-degenerately doped semiconductors, an alternative approach is adopted. This approach utilizes the parabolic band approximation (PBA) in conjunction with Fermi's golden rule to derive a novel expression for B , dependent on both electron and hole concentrations [8].

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

The simulations are focused on fully-relaxed $\text{Ge}_{0.83}\text{Sn}_{0.17}$ homojunctions corresponding to a bandgap energy of 0.29 eV at 300 K. The $\text{Ge}_{0.83}\text{Sn}_{0.17}$ -based TPV cells, operating at 300K, are illuminated by standard black-body radiation sources whose temperature T_{bb} is within the 500 K to 1500 K range. In this range, the incident power density P_{in} varies from 0.16 to 27

TABLE I
PERFORMANCE PARAMETERS OF CURRENT
NARROW BANDGAP TPV CELLS

Parameters	GaInAsSbP <i>p-n-n</i>	InAs <i>p-i-n</i>	InAs <i>p-i-n</i>	GeSn <i>p-i-n</i>	GeSn <i>p-i-n</i>	GeSn <i>p-i-n</i>
E_g (eV)	0.35	0.35	0.35	0.291	0.291	0.291
T_{bb} (K)	1200	~ 1000	~ 1200	1200	1500	1500
P_{in} (W/cm ²)	0.5	0.72	0.32	0.3	0.7	26.96
J_{sc} (A/cm ²)	0.29	0.89	0.21	0.203	0.485	18.68
V_{oc} (V)	0.028	0.06	0.018	0.075	0.097	0.195
FF(%)	33	37	28.09	42.82	47.81	62.47
η (%)	0.53	3	0.33	2.16	3.22	8.45
P_{out} (mW/cm ²)	2.66	21.6	1.05	6.48	22.54	2.28×10^3
Ref	[9]	[10]	[3]	This work	This work	This work

W/cm², spanning both the low and high injection regimes. Under the assumption of ideal ohmic contacts, the evolution of TPV electrical parameters with radiation temperature is investigated for both front-side and back-side illuminations. To accommodate non-ideal experimental factors, such as the geometrical view factor and the emissivity of the emitter, the theoretical P_{in} can be scaled down to a specific value of interest. This approach is particularly useful for comparing our GeSn-based TPV to narrow-bandgap III-V based TPV cells for which the incident power densities are in the mW/cm² range for $T_{bb} \sim 1000$ -1500 K, as presented in table 1. These results show that TPV cells based on GeSn with relatively good material quality could performed better compared to III-V based cells.

IV. CONCLUSION

In this work, we investigated the performance of TPV cells based on narrow bandgap GeSn materials. From these analyses, power conversion efficiency up to 9% was obtained for devices under black-body radiation of temperature within the 500 K to 1500 K range. With these results, silicon- integrated mid-infrared TPV cells are presented as cost- effective and scalable alternative to compound semiconductor mid-infrared TPV materials for harvesting the infrared radiation emitted through the heat wasted by major industries.

ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

O.M. acknowledges support from NSERC Canada (Discovery, SPG, and CRD Grants), Canada Research Chairs, Canada Foundation for Innovation, Mitacs, PRIMA Québec, Defense Canada (Innovation for Defense Excellence and Security, IDEaS), and the US Army Research Office Grant No. W911NF-22-1-0277. R.S. acknowledges support from the United States AFOSR on grant FA9550-21-1-0347.

REFERENCES

- [1] X. Wang et al., "Radioisotope Thermophotovoltaic Generator Design Methods and Performance Estimates for Space Missions," *Journal of Propulsion and Power*, vol. 36, no. 4, pp. 593–603, 2020.
- [2] R. Q. Yang et al., "Narrow bandgap photovoltaic cells," *Solar Energy Materials and Solar Cells*, vol. 238, p. 111636, 2022.
- [3] Q. Lu et al., "InAs thermophotovoltaic cells with high quantum efficiency for waste heat recovery applications below 1000°C," *Solar Energy Materials and Solar Cells*, vol. 179, pp. 334–338, Jun. 2018.
- [4] M. M. A. Gamel et al., "A Review on Thermophotovoltaic Cell and Its Applications in Energy Conversion: Issues and Recommendations," *Materials*, vol. 14, no. 17, p. 4944, 2021.
- [5] O. Moutanabbir et al., "Monolithic infrared silicon photonics: The rise of (Si)GeSn semiconductors," *Applied Physics Letters*, vol. 118, no. 11, p. 110502, 2021.
- [6] C. C. Katsidis and D. I. Siapkas, "General transfer-matrix method for optical multilayer systems with coherent, partially coherent, and incoherent interference," *Appl. Opt.*, vol. 41, no. 19, pp. 3978–3987, Jul 2002.
- [7] A. Richter et al., "Reassessment of the limiting efficiency for crystalline silicon solar cells," *IEEE Journal of Photovoltaics*, vol. 3, no. 4, pp. 1184–1191, 2013.
- [8] S. L. Chuang, "Physics of Photonic Devices", 2nd ed., ser. Wiley Series in Pure and Applied Optics. Wiley, 2009.
- [9] K. J. Cheetham et al., "Low bandgap GaInAsSbP pentanary thermophotovoltaic diodes," *Solar Energy Materials and Solar Cells*, vol. 95, no. 2, pp. 534–537, Feb. 2011.
- [10] A. Krier et al., "Low bandgap mid-infrared thermophotovoltaic arrays based on InAs," *Infrared Physics & Technology*, vol. 73, pp. 126–129, Nov. 2015.

Silicon Materials Mid-Infrared Direct Spectral Emissivity Measurement at Intermediate Temperatures

Elissa Akiki, Georges Hamaoui*, Armande Herve, Frédéric Marty, Lionel Rousseau, Tarik Bourouina, Philippe Basset, Elyes Nefzaoui

ESYCOM lab, UMR 9007 CNRS, Univ Gustave Eiffel, 77454 Marne-la-Vallée, France

This study introduces a test bench developed for the direct measurement of material emissivity, which is crucial for enhancing the efficiency of systems involving thermal radiation control or conversion such as radiative cooling, solar cells, thermophotovoltaics (TPV) and infrared (IR) photodetectors. Currently under development, this test bench is designed to operate at intermediate temperature ranges from 300°C to 600°C. It is engineered to enable direct and spectral measurements, thereby improving the understanding of emissivity's, spectral, and temperature dependences. We also report on results obtained for silicon, a material widely used for thermal radiation control and conversion devices, at different doping levels and different temperatures. Obtained results can be useful to assess the suitability of these materials and related meta-materials for different applications where emissivity at intermediate temperatures plays a major role.

I. INTRODUCTION

The enhancement of waste and renewable energy utilization through advanced energy conversion technologies is pivotal in meeting the growing societal energy demands and progressing toward a carbon-neutral world. Metamaterials, engineered to possess tailored properties for specific applications, have come to the forefront over the past two decades, especially in thermal energy conversion and management a critical component of global energy production. These materials demonstrate vast potential across a spectrum of applications, including thermoelectric, photovoltaic, and thermophotovoltaic energy conversion, as well as in managing the thermal properties of electronic devices, thermal rectification, and radiative cooling for extensive thermal regulation [1].

Thermal emissivity is one of the tunable thermal properties of interest in metamaterials. It quantifies a body's ability to emit heat through thermal radiation with comparison to a perfect blackbody emitter. The two primary methods for measuring thermal emissivity are direct and indirect. The indirect method involves projecting a radiation beam onto a sample and measuring both reflectivity and transmissivity to deduce absorptivity, guided by Kirchhoff's law which states that spectral directional absorptivity and emissivity are equivalent for a material at thermal equilibrium. Conversely, the direct method calculates emissivity based on the ratio of thermal radiation emitted by the sample to that from a blackbody reference source.

The choice between these methods largely depends on the experimental setup and specific application needs. An

advantage of the indirect method is that it enables measurements at lower temperatures and/or emissivities, as it does not rely on measuring the thermal power emitted by the sample itself. The direct method is typically favored for high-temperature materials, where the signal-to-noise ratio is more favorable, enabling a clearer differentiation between the sample's emitted radiation and that reflected from ambient conditions. We have been studying for the past decade metamaterials made of randomly micro and nanostructured silicon, alternatively known as Black Silicon (BSi)[3]. Direct measurement of emissivity is particularly interesting for the case of BSi due to its complex surface geometry and the critical role that emissivity plays in its performance when used for different applications. This emissivity, important up to nearly 1 μm due to bandgap absorption of silicon, complies with Kirchhoff's law of thermal radiation (indirect measurements), making BSi a standout candidate for enhancing solar cell efficiency [2,3]. Notably, silicon nanostructures featuring anti-reflective and hydrophobic properties have been developed to craft efficient, self-cleaning solar energy harvesting devices [4]. The standard indirect methods for measuring emissivity, while useful, often fall short in capturing the precise thermal radiative properties of materials like BSi that are designed to operate under specific thermal and optical conditions. For BSi, the direct method comparing the thermal radiation emitted by the material to that of a blackbody reference provides a more accurate image of its thermal properties under operational conditions such as intermediate or high temperatures.

Given these limitations, there is a clear need to develop new methodologies for the direct measurement of emissivity that can accurately assess its directional, spectral, and temperature-dependent properties. Such developments might be useful when considering such material for TPV applications either as a selective emitter or on the cell side to enhance IR radiation absorption.

II. EXPERIMENTAL SETUP AND MEASUREMENT PROTOCOL

A. Direct emissivity setup

A schematic of the experimental setup developed in this study is shown in Fig 1. The setup is based on a standard Fourier-transform infrared (FTIR) spectroscope (PerkinElmer Spectrum 400) that features a DTGS detector functioning at room temperature and a KBr beam splitter, facilitating a spectral range of 2.5 – 22 μm . The spectral resolution is

maintained at 2 cm^{-1} , with the resulting spectra being the average of 10 scans. The optical components are housed within a blackout chamber which possesses nearly 100% absorptance in the mid-infrared range. This design minimizes any unwanted multi-reflections between the sample and the chamber walls which can be considered as a blackbody.

Fig. 1. Direct emissivity measurement setup developed in this work. The orange and dashed beams show the infrared radiation of the blackbody and the sample, respectively, measured by the FTIR spectrometer. Identical sample-FTIR and blackbody-FTIR optical paths are ensured using the rotating parabolic mirror.

B. Measurement principle

The direct method involves measuring the radiative power emitted by a sample and comparing it to that emitted by a blackbody reference source. The spectral directional emissivity of a real body ranges from 0 to 1. This emissivity is quantified as the ratio of the spectral and directional radiative intensity $S_s(\lambda, \theta, T_s)$ emitted by a sample at a specific temperature T_s , to the spectral and directional intensity $S_{BB}(\lambda, \theta, T_s)$ of a blackbody at the same temperature, as calculated by Planck's law, as

$$Ae_s(\lambda, \theta, T_s) = \frac{S_s(\lambda, \theta, T_s)}{S_{BB}(\lambda, \theta, T_{BB})} \quad (1)$$

Normal incidence ($\theta = 0$) is considered in the first instance.

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Several samples have been characterized including low-doped (LD) Si wafers (resistivity $\rho = 1 - 10 \text{ }\Omega\text{cm}$) and highly-doped (HD) Si ($\rho = 0.01 \text{ }\Omega\text{cm}$). Directly measured emissivity was also compared to the emissivity obtained by the indirect method at room temperature (using a PerkinElmer Spectrum 3 FTIR spectrometer), with the absorbance A calculated as:

$$A = 1 - R - T \quad (2)$$

where A is the absorbance, R the reflectance, and T the transmittance. According to Kirchhoff's law, we deduce the emissivity ϵ assumed to be equal to its absorptivity A for any given wavelength, incidence angle and temperature at thermal equilibrium ($\epsilon = A = Ae$).

We show Fig. 2 the results obtained for HD and LD Si.

Fig. 2. Direct Emissivity and the absorptance (A) of HD and LD Si.

From these first results, we observe that HD Si emissivity is larger than that of the LD Si and the sample temperature did not have a significant effect on the emissivity. These findings are consistent with results from other studies on the emissivity of flat silicon [5,6]. This work is currently being continued to measure the emissivity of BSi samples with different geometric features, doping levels and surface coatings. The experimental setup is also being upgraded to enable variable angle emissivity measurements.

IV. CONCLUSIONS AND PERSPECTIVES

Several thermal radiation conversion and management applications such as TPV require operating materials at intermediate or high temperatures. On the other hand, materials emissivity is a key material property governing the emission and absorption of thermal radiation. For these reasons, materials direct emissivity measurement at the targeted operating temperature is of paramount importance accurately assess the material suitability for a given application and the expected performances under realistic conditions. We have developed a new experimental setup for materials direct emissivity measurement at intermediate temperatures up to $600 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$. Preliminary results on Silicon at different doping levels and temperatures have been obtained and show good agreement with the literature. The characterization of silicon-based metamaterials that can be used as emitters or absorbers for TPV applications is currently ongoing and the upgrade of the experimental setup to perform variable angle measurement is also expected in the near future.

REFERENCES

- [1] Y. Zhang, Y.J. Heo, Y.R. Son, I. In, K.H. An, B.J. Kim, S.J. Park, Recent advanced thermal interfacial materials: A review of conducting mechanisms and parameters of carbon materials, Carbon N Y 142 (2019) 445–460. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.carbon.2018.10.077>.

- [2] M. Algasinger, J. Paye, F. Werner, J. Schmidt, M.S. Brandt, M. Stutzmann, S. Koynov, Improved black silicon for photovoltaic applications, *Adv Energy Mater* 3 (2013) 1068–1074. <https://doi.org/10.1002/aenm.201201038>.
- [3] S. Sarkar, A.A. Elsayed, Y.M. Sabry, F. Marty, J. Dré villon, X. Liu, Z. Liang, E. Richalot, P. Basset, E. Nefzaoui, T. Bourouina, Black Silicon Revisited as an Ultrabroadband Perfect Infrared Absorber over 20 μm Wavelength Range, *Adv Photonics Res* 2200223 (2022) 2200223. <https://doi.org/10.1002/adpr.202200223>.
- [4] H. Savin, P. Repo, G. Von Gastrow, P. Ortega, E. Calle, M. Garín, R. Alcubilla, Black silicon solar cells with interdigitated back-contacts achieve 22.1% efficiency, *Nat Nanotechnol* 10 (2015) 624–628. <https://doi.org/10.1038/nnano.2015.89>.
- [5] P.J. Timans, Emissivity of silicon at elevated temperatures, *J Appl Phys* 74 (1993) 6353–6364. <https://doi.org/10.1063/1.355159>.
- [6] Z. Li, Y. Zhang, H. Peng, L. Liu, W. Zhu, Z. Liu, Spectral narrowing of sub-bandgap absorbance and emissivity in highly doped silicon, *Mater Res Express* 6 (2019). <https://doi.org/10.1088/2053-1591/ab637d>.

Enhancement of TPV power density with surface-engineered emitters

Shomik Verma¹, Minok Park², Sean Lubner³, Asegun Henry¹

¹Department of Mechanical Engineering, Massachusetts Institute of Technology, Cambridge, Massachusetts, 02139, USA

²Energy Technologies Area, Lawrence Berkeley National Laboratory, Berkeley, California, 94720, USA

³Department of Mechanical Engineering, Division of Materials Science and Engineering, Boston University, Boston, Massachusetts, 02215, USA

Abstract — TPV power density is a critical metric to reduce the amount of TPV area required for power conversion. Increasing the emitter surface emissivity is one way of increasing power density, but traditional coatings delaminate at high temperatures. Here we show a laser processing technique applicable to a wide variety of materials to create near-black surfaces. We then test a laser-processed Ta emitter, showing it more than doubles the power density of a TPV cell compared to a plain Ta emitter (2.18 vs. 4.91 W/cm²) while retaining the same efficiency of 27%. Further, the emitter is thermally stable with limited degradation after both high temperature and long lifetime exposure. This work demonstrates a promising way forward for high-performing, non-carbon emitter materials for TPV cells.

I. INTRODUCTION

Thermophotovoltaics (TPV) are rapidly gaining traction as an alternative heat engine to turbines [1]. TPVs have many benefits including being solid state with no moving parts and having a higher theoretical efficiency than many heat engines [1]. The efficiency of TPV cells is defined as the ratio of electric power produced to total absorbed energy:

$$\eta_{TPV} = \frac{P_{elec}}{P_{elec} + Q_{abs}} \quad (1)$$

However, the efficiency only tells half the story. As a photovoltaic device, TPV operates by converting photons with energy above its bandgap into electricity. One can imagine a device that filters out all wavelengths of light except the photons at the bandgap of the cell, therefore theoretically achieving 100% efficiency. However, the electricity produced from such a device would be low since the number of photons at the bandgap is low. Therefore, another important metric for TPV cells is power density, defined as the electricity produced divided by the device area:

$$P_{dens} = \frac{P_{elec}}{A_{TPV}} \quad (2)$$

Both of these performance metrics are important for TPV and are reported in previous works [2]. Clearly we would want to maximize both efficiency and power density for the best device. However, either the efficiency or power density may be more important in certain applications.

To understand when each metric may be more important, consider a TPV system that takes power as input (sunlight, electricity, fuel) and through some system infrastructure (emitters, TPV cells) converts that power into electricity. If we consider a fixed power input, the TPV efficiency impacts how

much power can be output, and the power density impacts how much TPV area is required to output that power. Therefore, if the TPV area is the dominating cost in a system (e.g. if the power input such as solar is cheap) increasing the TPV power density is critical.

TPV power density can be increased by: (a) increasing the emitter temperature, (b) increasing the view factor, (c) lowering the bandgap of the cell, or (d) increasing the emissivity of the emitter. However, oftentimes the emitter temperature and view factor are fixed, and decreasing the bandgap can result in a lower cell efficiency. Therefore, this work focuses on increasing the emitter emissivity. One option for doing so is using a high-emissivity material such as graphite or CFC, but these face issues with high vapor pressure potentially causing deposition on the cell. Another option is using coatings, but these degrade or delaminate at high temperatures [3].

Therefore, this work pioneers a surface engineering technique to improve the emissivity of a wide variety of materials. Specifically, we use a laser ablation process to create light-trapping valleys that increase the broadband emissivity (absorptivity) of the materials, as shown in Fig. 1. We then use laser-processed tantalum (Ta) as an emitter for TPV, comparing its performance to a plain Ta emitter and a CFC emitter.

Fig. 1: Overview of laser processing technique, resulting samples, and resulting emissivity improvement.

II. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

To test TPV performance we used the experimental apparatus described in LaPotin [4], namely a TPV cell spaced 5mm away from an emitter with an aperture plate in between to limit parasitic heating of other components. Electric power was measured with a 4-wire measurement and heat flux with a custom heat flux sensor featuring 4 thermocouples embedded in a copper block. The experimental setup is shown in Fig. 2.

Fig. 2: Experimental setup of TPV performance characterization.

We used a 1.2/1.0 eV tandem TPV cell with an Au back-reflector for these tests, the same architecture as the MT671 cell used in LaPotin et al. [5]. We tested the 3 emitters at temperatures ranging from 1500°C to 2100°C. We measured IV curves, and at the maximum power point measured electrical power generated and heat absorbed. With these two measurements and the area of the cell (0.7145 cm²) we calculated the power density and efficiency, as shown in Fig. 3.

Fig. 3: Power density and efficiency measurements for the 3 emitters tested in this work.

As seen, the laser processed (LP) tantalum more than doubled the power density of the TPV cell compared to the plain Ta, approaching the power density of the CFC emitter and is among the highest reported. Further, this increase in power density did not impact the efficiency significantly, with all 3 emitters exhibiting similar efficiency. This can be attributed to the high sub-bandgap reflectance of the cell, reducing parasitic heating. The lower than expected efficiency (LaPotin [4] used the same experimental setup and reported 37% efficiency with a CFC emitter at 2100°C) suggests the cell used in this work is low quality with poor EQE or high series resistance.

In terms of thermal stability, there was limited degradation after testing for 10 minutes at each temperature for ~1.5 hours total, with the above-bandgap spectrally-weighted emissivity only decreasing from 0.98 to 0.95. For a longer-term longevity study, the LP Ta was heated to 1500°C for 100 hours in an argon environment, and the emissivity decreased from 0.98 to 0.92 in that time, as shown in Fig. 4.

Figure 4: Thermal stability setup and results for the LP Ta.

III. CONCLUSIONS AND FUTURE WORK

Increasing TPV power density is critical in applications where the TPV cell cost dominates. Increasing the emissivity of the emitter material is one way of improving TPV power density, but conventional techniques are too inflexible. In this work we demonstrate that laser processing through ablation can be used to engineer the surfaces of many materials to make them near-black. Using this laser processing on Ta, we more than double the power density compared to a plain Ta emitter, from 2.18 W/cm² to 4.91 W/cm², while retaining an efficiency of 27% ± 1%, at 2100°C. Not only was the laser processing able to withstand these temperatures, but we also demonstrated long lifetime stability with the emissivity only decreasing by 0.06 after 100 hours at 1500°C, which coatings would not withstand.

Future work involves testing other emitters including oxidation resistance materials such as silicon carbide (SiC) and oxides such as alumina (Al₂O₃) and zirconia (YSZ).

Overall, we have shown TPV power density can be improved significantly by engineering the emitter surface, indicating a promising way forward for high-performing non-carbon emitter materials.

REFERENCES

- [1] C. Ferrari, F. Melino, M. Pinelli, P. R. Spina, and M. Venturini, "Overview and Status of Thermophotovoltaic Systems," *Energy Procedia*, vol. 45, pp. 160–169, Jan. 2014, doi: 10.1016/j.egypro.2014.01.018.
- [2] M. Giteau, M. F. Picardi, and G. T. Papadakis, "Thermodynamic figure of merit for thermophotovoltaics," *J. Photonics Energy*, vol. 14, no. 4, p. 042402, Feb. 2024, doi: 10.1117/1.JPE.14.042402.
- [3] N. Martínez, M. Lopez-Herraiz, A. Rico, C. J. Múñez, and P. Poza, "Influence of different thermal degradation processes on the optical property of Pyromark-2500," *Sol. Energy*, vol. 253, pp. 58–72, Mar. 2023, doi: 10.1016/j.solener.2023.02.004.
- [4] A. D. LaPotin, "Characterization of Thermophotovoltaics and Materials for High-Temperature Thermal Energy Storage," Thesis, Massachusetts Institute of Technology, 2024. Accessed: Mar. 18, 2024. [Online]. Available: <https://dspace.mit.edu/handle/1721.1/153694>
- [5] A. LaPotin et al., "Thermophotovoltaic efficiency of 40%," *Nature*, vol. 604, no. 7905, Art. no. 7905, Apr. 2022, doi: 10.1038/s41586-022-04473-y.

Improved Near-Field Thermophotovoltaics with Matched Radiator and Receiver

Mathieu Giroux,¹ Sean Molesky,² Raphael St-Gelais,^{1,3} Jacob J. Krich^{3,4}

¹Department of Mechanical Engineering, University of Ottawa, Ottawa K1N 6N5, Ontario, Canada

²Department of Engineering Physics, Polytechnique Montreal, Montreal H3T 1J4, Quebec, Canada

³Department of Physics, University of Ottawa, Ottawa K1N 6N5, Ontario, Canada

⁴Nexus for Quantum Technologies, University of Ottawa, Ottawa K1N 6N5, Ontario, Canada

Abstract — Indium arsenide (InAs), with a band gap of 0.35 eV, is a promising photovoltaic (PV) material for near-field thermophotovoltaics (NFTPV). The development of an accurate dielectric model for InAs is therefore imperative for designing InAs-based NFTPV. Based on existing measurements of InAs absorption, we find that a traditional Drude model overestimates free carrier absorption in InAs. We propose a revised model derived from ionized impurity scattering. Using this revised model, we maximize the spectral efficiency of a NFTPV system by optimizing the spectral coupling between a radiator and an InAs PV cell. We find that when the radiator and the PV cell are both made of InAs, a four-fold improvement of spectral efficiency is possible compared to a traditional silicon radiator with the same InAs cell.

I. INTRODUCTION

Near-field thermophotovoltaic (NFTPV) systems have significant potential for waste heat recovery applications, with both high theoretical efficiency and power density, up to 40% and 11 W/cm² [1]. Despite such potential, experimental demonstrations have only achieved up to 14% efficiency and modest power densities (i.e., 0.75 W/cm²) [2].

While experimental works have recently started to focus on PV cells custom-made for NFTPV [2], most work still relies on conventional doped silicon (Si) radiators. Indium-tin-oxide (ITO), with a plasmon resonance just above the PV cell band gap, has been proposed as an improved radiator [3], but it is hard to ensure the reproducibility with ITO at high temperatures.

The radiator must be designed in concert with the photovoltaic cell. For the temperature range of waste heat recovery applications up to 1000 K, indium arsenide (InAs) is a promising material, with a bandgap of 0.35 eV. Dielectric function models for PV cells generally involve relatively simple parameterization, and the standard Drude model for InAs results in an overestimation of absorption both above and below the bandgap.

In this work, we correct the overestimation of free carrier absorption in InAs dielectric models by substituting the Drude model for the model described in Ref. [4]. Additionally, we design an optimized NFTPV radiator to improve spectral coupling, arising from employing the same material for the radiator and PV cell.

II. DIELECTRIC FUNCTION

The fluctuational electrodynamics framework, employed in this work, requires the dielectric functions of all materials used; for our system we need only Si and InAs. The dielectric model of Si uses the lattice and interband contributions from Ref. [5] and the Drude free-carrier model from Ref. [6], while incorporating the mobility, decay rates and donor and acceptor contributions from Ref. [7].

In the case of InAs, the dielectric model is based on Ref. [8], including a Drude-Lorentz model to account for both lattice and free carrier contributions. Interband absorption includes non-parabolicity corrections and the Moss-Burstein shift. Unfortunately, the Drude model overestimates the free carrier absorption. We address this overestimation by incorporating the model described in Ref. [4], which substitutes the imaginary component of the Drude model, in the case of highly n-doped InAs, for frequencies exceeding the plasma frequency.

Fig. 1(a) compares the InAs absorption coefficient from the dielectric model to experimental n-doped InAs absorption data at different donor concentrations N_d taken from Refs. [9, 10, 11]. The comparison suggests that the Drude contribution from Ref. [8] results in a significant overestimate of free carrier absorption at energies near the bandgap. This discrepancy becomes more noticeable at higher doping levels, even resulting in an overestimation of the absorption above the bandgap. This overestimation could lead to inaccurate predictions of NFTPV performances since above-bandgap absorptivity originating from free carrier absorption will not generate collectible electron-hole pairs and parasitic heating reduces overall performance. Our proposed model, results in a good agreement with the experimental data at doping levels below 10¹⁸ cm⁻³. While this is a significant improvement, we still encounter approximately a threefold overestimation of the free carrier contribution at high doping levels.

III. RADIATOR OPTIMIZATION

We use a one-dimensional fluctuational electrodynamics model from Ref. [12] to perform NFTPV simulations. We assess the performances of NFTPV systems using two key

metrics: the useful transferred power P and the spectral efficiency η ,

$$P = \int_{E_g/\hbar}^{\infty} \frac{E_g}{\hbar\omega} Q(\omega) d\omega, \quad (1)$$

$$\eta = \frac{P}{\int_0^{\infty} Q(\omega) d\omega}, \quad (2)$$

where E_g is the bandgap energy, \hbar is Planck's constant, ω is the frequency, and $Q(\omega)$ is the spectral heat flux.

The PV device consists of a p-i-n-n+ InAs structure with the n+ layer forming a back reflector for subgap radiation.

Replacing a standard doped Si radiator with an InAs radiator can increase the spectral efficiency by up to a factor of 4, as shown in Fig. 1(b). When the PV cell and radiator are both made from InAs, subgap heat transfer is reduced, improving the spectral efficiency and reducing cooling requirements for the cell.

Fig. 1. (a) InAs absorption coefficient from the dielectric model of Ref. [8] (dashed lines) compared to data on n-doped InAs (markers). Our proposed model significantly improves the agreement with absorption data above and below the bandgap, especially at high doping. (b) Spectral efficiency ratio comparing a NFTPV system employing an InAs radiator to an identical system using a Si radiator.

IV. CONCLUSION

During our analysis, we also uncover an overestimation of the free carrier absorption in InAs dielectric function models. We implement a corrective model and demonstrate that it accurately represents the absorption at low doping levels but could be further refined for improved accuracy at higher doping levels. Using this revised model, we demonstrate that the spectral efficiency of NFTPV systems can be greatly enhanced when both the PV cell and radiator are made of InAs. In such a case, spectral coupling results in a four-fold enhancement of the spectral efficiency. This improvement reduces the parasitic heating of the PV cell and increases its overall efficiency while not significantly affecting the power density.

REFERENCES

- [1] B. Zhao, C. Kaifeng, S. Buddhiraju, G. Bhatt, M. Lipson and S. Fan, "High-performance near-field thermophotovoltaics for waste heat recovery," *Nano Energy*, vol. 41, pp. 344-350, 2017.
- [2] C. Lucchesi, D. Cakiroglu, J.-P. Perez, T. Taliercio, E. Tournié, P.-O. Chapuis and R. Vaillon, "Near-Field Thermophotovoltaic Conversion with High Electrical Power Density and Cell Efficiency above 14%," *Nano Letters*, vol. 21, pp. 4524-4529, 2021.
- [3] R. St-Gelais, G. R. Bhatt, L. Zhu, S. Fan and M. Lipson, "Hot Carrier-Based Near-Field Thermophotovoltaic Energy Conversion," *ACS Nano*, vol. 11, pp. 3001-3009, 2017.
- [4] R. von Baltz and W. Escher, "Quantum Theory of Free Carrier Absorption," *physica status solidi (b)*, vol. 51, pp. 499-507, 1972.
- [5] B. J. Lee, Z. M. Zhang, E. A. Early, D. P. DeWitt and B. K. Tsai, "Modeling Radiative Properties of Silicon with Coatings and Comparison with Reflectance Measurements," *Journal of Thermophysics and Heat Transfer*, vol. 19, pp. 558-565, 2005.
- [6] C. Fu and Z. Zhang, "Nanoscale radiation heat transfer for silicon at different doping levels," *International Journal of Heat and Mass Transfer*, vol. 49, pp. 1703-1718, 2006.
- [7] S. Basu, B. J. Lee and Z. Zhang, "Infrared Radiative Properties of Heavily Doped Silicon at Room Temperature," *Journal of Heat transfer*, vol. 132, p. 023301, 2010.
- [8] D. Milovich, J. Villa, E. Antolin, A. Datas, A. Marti, R. Vaillon and M. Francoeur, "Design of an indium arsenide cell for near-field thermophotovoltaic devices," *Journal of Photonics for Energy*, pp. 025503, 2020.
- [9] J. R. Dixon and J. M. Ellis, "Optical Properties of n-Type Indium Arsenide in the Fundamental Absorption Edge Region," *Physical Review*, vol. 123, no. 5, pp. 1560-1566, 1961.
- [10] R. M. Culpepper and J. R. Dixon, "Free-Carrier Absorption in n-Type Indium Arsenide*," *Journal of the Optical Society of America*, vol. 58, pp. 96-102, 1968.
- [11] J. R. Dixon, in *Proceedings of 5th International Conference on Physics of Semiconductors*, Prague, 1960.
- [12] S. Molesky, *HeatSlabs: A Python Package for Modeling Nanoscale Radiative Heat Transfer*, GitHub, 2022.

Micro/nanoscale spacers for enhanced thermophotovoltaic and thermionic energy conversion: a comprehensive review

Nicolas Loubet¹, Katie Bezdjian¹, Esther Estrada Lopez¹, Alejandro Datas¹

¹Instituto de Energía Solar – Universidad Politécnica de Madrid, Avenida Complutense 30, 28040 Madrid, Spain

Abstract — In both thermophotovoltaic and thermionic energy converters, the emitter/cathode and receiver/anode are separated by a gap enabling the transfer of photons and electrons, respectively. Reducing this gap has the potential to significantly improve the power density in both technologies. In thermophotovoltaics, a nano-scale vacuum gap allows evanescent waves to tunnel through the gap, leading to higher output power densities. Conversely, in thermionics, a micron-scale vacuum gap reduces the space charge effect, enabling higher conversion efficiencies. To achieve these effects, affordable and scalable solutions are needed to maintain a consistent gap between the emitter/cathode and receiver/anode. Nano/micro-spacers, patterned materials with minimal thermal and electrical conduction and resistance to high working temperatures, have emerged as promising solutions. The goal of this study is to provide an overview of current spacer technologies, and to outline remaining progress to be made to unlock the full potential of micro/nanoscale gaps for heat conversion.

I. INTRODUCTION

Thermophotovoltaic (TPV) and thermionic energy converters (TEC) represent a promising solution for converting heat into electricity. However, they are currently limited by low output power densities compared to other technologies such as thermoelectric devices. One pathway to drastically improve these two aspects is to reduce the gap separating the hot emitter/cathode from the cold receiver/anode. In TPV systems, reducing the separation between the emitter and the cell to the order of nanometers enables evanescent waves to tunnel across the gap, enabling heat transfer above the blackbody limit [1]. In the case of thermionics, efficiency is tempered by the formation of a cloud of electrons between the cathode and anode [2]. This effect, called the space charge effect, has been typically suppressed by introduction of a cesium plasma between the cathode and anode. While this method has been successful in reducing the space charge effect, plasma also has a parasitic effect on the electron flux and consumes additional energy, making it a less efficient than micro gaps [3][4].

Near-field effects in heat transfer have been demonstrated on a small scale (a few microns or millimeters) using actuators with a sphere-to-plane or tip-to-plane design, as well as microelectromechanical systems (MEMS). These options, while valuable for concepts studies, lack the scale for practical energy conversion. With the progress of microfabrication, spacer-based approaches with scalability potential have been developed in TPV and thermionic devices. For example, a

uniform layer of material is deposited on either side of the device and patterned through conventional photolithography and etching methods to obtain pillars of a given shape (e.g., cylindrical, trapezoidal) and height, thus enabling a uniform gap. Other approaches considered here include the use of nano- or microspheres directly dispersed onto the receiver to maintain a constant gap, or the use of any material as a sandwich layer that is not fixed to either side.

II. MATERIALS USED AS SPACERS

The spacers require a very low thermal conductivity to avoid parasitic heat transmission from the hot side to the cold one, as well as high resistance to elevated temperatures (>1200°C) for several cycles. The main difference between spacers for TPV devices and thermionics is the desired gap size. In TPV devices, the radiative heat transfer coefficient depends on d^{-2} [5]; therefore, both sides should be as close as possible to take advantage of the near-field effect. For thermionic converter, there is an acceptable lower limit: passing this threshold will lead to near-field heat transfer with a parasitic effect on the energy conversion. Thus, the height of the spacers should be of the order of nanometers for TPV devices and microns for thermionics [6][7].

In literature, this difference is evident. Figure 1 depicts the relationships between maximum emitter/cathode temperature and the minimum gap achieved by spacers reported in various studies. Two regions are clearly visible: one using big gaps and high temperatures for thermionics applications, and the other reaching for smaller gaps and only achieving low temperatures for heat transfer demonstrations. In Fig. 1, it is also notable that the most common material used for spacers so far is silicon dioxide, mostly due to its low thermal conductivity and resistance to high temperatures, as well as ease of patterning through well-known methods. Similarly, Alumina is another strong candidate for spacers. Photoresist resins, such as SU-8, have also been utilized as spacers during near-field radiative heat transfer experiments between plane-plane geometries. Photoresists are advantageous because they are easily processable, but they lack the resistance to high temperatures that is crucial for these devices. Many opportunities exist to further develop and optimize nanospacers for higher emitter temperatures. In thermionics, most of the designs studied relied on spacers that are not attached to either side of the device

which could pose a reliability issue for industrial devices. As such, for both technologies, a lot of effort remains to obtain reliable spacers.

Fig. 1. Maximum temperature of the emitter/cathode for heat transfer (circles) or thermionics (triangles) against the minimum gap distance reported in literature. Each color represents a spacer material.

III. IMPORTANT PARAMETERS FOR SPACERS DESIGN

The goal of this review is to identify the work that has been done by the scientific community in the design and fabrication of micro/nanospacers, and to provide an idea of what remains to be done. For both TPV and thermionic devices, one important metric is the thermal conductivity of the spacer material. This parameter has been extensively studied in thermionics [2][8][9][10] but to a lesser degree in the context of near-field radiative heat transfer [11][12][13]. Research on near-field radiative heat transfer more commonly involves computing the radiative heat transfer coefficient. Based on the literature, the radiative heat transfer coefficient was most often measured in devices using silicon dioxide spacers and photoresists at temperatures between room temperature and 100°C, and in some case without consideration for thermal losses, indicating a knowledge gap in higher-temperature near-field radiative heat transfer experiments for various materials. Depending on the spacer shape and/or material, other parameters such as contact thermal resistance at the interface between the spacer and the surface of the device could be important in maximizing device performance; this is particularly important when the spacer is not attached to any side of the device. Fabricating spacers for near field thermophotovoltaic and thermionic devices involves several considerations, such as material, geometry, and gap distance (which is often dictated by spacer height). The design process should include considerations of thermal and electrical conductivity and contact thermal resistance, depending on the application targeted in order to take full advantage of micro/nanoscale effects.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENT

This work is funded by the Spanish Research State Agency MCIN/AEI/10.13039/501100011033 through the projects PID2020-115719RB-C22 (GETPV) and TED2021-131778B (TROPIC). Project TED2021-131778B (TROPIC) is also funded by European Union "NextGenerationEU"/PRTR.

REFERENCES

- [1] C. Lucchesi, R. Vaillon, and P.-O. Chapuis, "Temperature dependence of near-field radiative heat transfer above room temperature," *Materials Today Physics*, vol. 21, p. 100562, Nov. 2021, doi: 10.1016/j.mtphys.2021.100562.
- [2] R. Y. Belbachir, Z. An, and T. Ono, "Thermal investigation of a micro-gap thermionic power generator," *J. Micromech. Microeng.*, vol. 24, no. 8, p. 085009, Jul. 2014, doi: 10.1088/0960-1317/24/8/085009.
- [3] N. S. Rasor, "Thermionic energy conversion plasmas," *IEEE Transactions on Plasma Science*, vol. 19, no. 6, pp. 1191–1208, Dec. 1991, doi: 10.1109/27.125041.
- [4] J.-H. Lee *et al.*, "Microfabricated Thermally Isolated Low Work-Function Emitter," *Journal of Microelectromechanical Systems*, vol. 23, no. 5, pp. 1182–1187, Oct. 2014, doi: 10.1109/JMEMS.2014.2307882.
- [5] M. Francoeur, "Near-Field Thermal Radiation," in *Handbook of Thermal Science and Engineering*, F. A. Kulacki, Ed., Cham: Springer International Publishing, 2017, pp. 1–43. doi: 10.1007/978-3-319-32003-8_63-1.
- [6] R. S. DiMatteo *et al.*, "Enhanced photogeneration of carriers in a semiconductor via coupling across a nonisothermal nanoscale vacuum gap," *Applied Physics Letters*, vol. 79, no. 12, pp. 1894–1896, Sep. 2001, doi: 10.1063/1.1400762.
- [7] J.-H. Lee, I. Bargatin, N. A. Melosh, and R. T. Howe, "Optimal emitter-collector gap for thermionic energy converters," *Applied Physics Letters*, vol. 100, no. 17, p. 173904, Apr. 2012, doi: 10.1063/1.4707379.
- [8] A. Bellucci *et al.*, "Dielectric Micro- and Sub-Micrometric Spacers for High-Temperature Energy Converters," *Energy Technology*, vol. 9, no. 1, p. 2000788, 2021, doi: 10.1002/ente.202000788.
- [9] R. Y. Belbachir, Z. An, and T. Ono, "Impact of thermal contact resistances on micro-gap heat losses for microthermionic power generators," *Microsyst Technol.*, vol. 22, no. 12, pp. 2811–2820, Dec. 2016, doi: 10.1007/s00542-015-2591-7.
- [10] M. F. Campbell *et al.*, "Nanostructured Spacers for Thermionic and Thermophotovoltaic Energy Converters," *Journal of Microelectromechanical Systems*, vol. 29, no. 5, pp. 637–644, Oct. 2020, doi: 10.1109/JMEMS.2020.3000422.
- [11] X. Ying, P. Sabbaghi, N. Sluder, and L. Wang, "Super-Planckian Radiative Heat Transfer between Macroscale Sum Gaps Down to 190 nm Directly Created by SU-8 Posts and Characterized by Capacitance Method," *ACS Photonics*, vol. 7, no. 1, pp. 190–196, Jan. 2020, doi: 10.1021/acsp Photonics.9b01360.
- [12] K. Ito, A. Miura, H. Iizuka, and H. Toshiyoshi, "Parallel-plate submicron gap formed by micromachined low-density pillars for near-field radiative heat transfer," *Applied Physics Letters*, vol. 106, no. 8, p. 083504, Feb. 2015, doi: 10.1063/1.4913692.
- [13] S. Lang *et al.*, "Dynamic measurement of near-field radiative heat transfer," *Sci Rep*, vol. 7, no. 1, Art. no. 1, Oct. 2017, doi: 10.1038/s41598-017-14242-x.

Selectively enhanced near-field radiative transfer between Tungsten and GaSb with Si 2D gratings for thermophotovoltaics

Tianbing Wang, Song Li, Junming Zhao*

School of Energy Science and Engineering, Harbin Institute of Technology, Harbin 150001, China

Abstract — III-V group semiconductors like GaSb and InAs are often used as PV cells in near-field thermophotovoltaic (NFTPV) systems. These polar semiconductors usually generate surface phonon polaritons (SPhP) at low frequencies at the interface with a vacuum, which will induce parasitic heat flow. This work investigates the radiative characteristics of a NFTPV system composed of a bulk tungsten emitter and a GaSb PV cell, with a Si 2D grating above the GaSb. By changing the grating height, size, and period, spectral tuning is achieved. The spectral radiative heat flux is calculated by rigorous coupled-wave analysis (RCWA) and effective medium theory (EMT). The results show that under a 200 nm gap, Si gratings effectively suppresses low-energy photon transmission compared to the NFTPV system without intermediate medium, while enhancing the spectrum above the cell bandgap, especially when the fill ratio is around 0.8 and the thickness is 300 nm. In addition, the effects of period are discussed in this work, which cannot be predicted by the equivalent medium theory. This investigation will be beneficial for the design of better-performing experimental near-field TPV system structures.

I. INTRODUCTION

Near-field thermophotovoltaic (NFTPV) is attracting more and more interest for its potential of achieving high-performance in waste heat recovery. Recent work in NFTPV systems has leveraged advances in III-V PV cells^[1,2], as these low band-gap PV cells can utilize a large part of the spectrum. However, as polar semiconductors, they usually generate surface phonon polaritons (SPhP) at low frequencies at the interface with a vacuum, which will induce parasitic heat flow^[3]. One way to suppress sub-bandgap phonon-polariton is to add a non-polarized layer (usually using silicon) between the emitter and the PV cell. While low-energy photon transmission is suppressed by non-polarized layer, thermal radiation transmission above the bandgap is also affected. To achieve spectrally selective enhancement and spectral matching between the emitter and the PV cell, nano structures can be utilized. The geometric parameter of nano structures has great influence on its optical properties. Yu et al.^[4] investigated the radiation transfer of NFTPV system with two-dimensional rectangular grating on the GaSb surface as an “anti-reflective” pattern, and they observed strong spectral enhancement above the cell’s bandgap and suppression for low-energy photon transmission. Inspired by their investigation, the effects of grating geometrical parameters is explored in this work to achieve spectrally selective enhancement.

II. COMPUTATIONAL RESULTS

Figure 1 shows the schematic structure of the model used in this computational work. The near-field TPV system consists of a bulk tungsten emitter and GaSb PV cell with a Si 2D grating added above the GaSb. Spectral tuning is performed by varying the grating parameters. The filling ratio f of the grating is $f = (a/P)^2$. Calculations are carried out with effective medium theory and Multilayer Electromagnetic Solver for Heat transfer (MESH), an open source electromagnetic solver for far-field and near-field radiative heat transfer for layered periodic structures, which combines rigorous coupled wave analysis and scattering matrix formalism to simulate the radiative heat transfer both in the near-field and far-field^[5].

Fig. 1. Illustration of the geometry configuration, the structural parameters, and the assigned coordinates.

A. Effects of Fill Ratio

Fig. 1 shows the spectral heat flux with different filling ratios for $d = 200$ nm and $h = 300$ nm, and the vertical lines indicate the corresponding frequencies of the GaSb bandgap. Compared with the NFTPV system without intermediate medium, radiative transmission below the bandgap is suppressed with Si grating, indicating that the Si grating has a good reflection effect on the low-frequency photons. In the meanwhile, the spectral heat flux of NFTPV systems with Si gratings are partially enhanced above the bandgap for the range of calculated filling ratios. Among them, when the filling ratio is 0.8, the spectral selectivity is enhanced more effectively. It should be noted that the peak of the spectral heat flow should be just above the bandgap, which is important for reducing the thermal losses^[6] and improving the efficiency of the system.

Fig. 2. Spectral heat flux with different filling ratios for $d = 200$ nm and $h = 300$ nm

B. Effects of Height

Fig. 1 shows the spectral heat flux with different grating thicknesses for $d = 200$ nm and $f = 0.8$. Within the grating height increasing, low-frequency photon transmission is suppressed more effectively. When $h = 300$ nm, the spectral selectivity is enhanced more effectively above the bandgap. As the grating height increases, the penetration depth of high-frequency photons is smaller and the absorption in the grating layer is stronger, so that the spectral heat flux decreases. And as the grating height decreases, the spectral heat flux becomes closer to that of planar case. Therefore, the grating height needs to be kept in a suitable range.

Fig. 3. Spectral heat flow with different grating thicknesses for $d = 200$ nm and $f = 0.8$.

C. Effects of Period

At the certain filling ratio, if period length gets shorter, the grating becomes more homogenous, and theoretically, its optical properties are going to be similar to those of a homogeneous film with the same filling rate. Since the

equivalent medium theory can only be used to explore the effect of filling rate, and it cannot reflect the specific geometrical structure of the grating. Thus, accurate theoretical models such as rigorous coupled-wave analysis are required.

III. SUMMARY

In this work, the radiative characteristics of a NFTPV system with a Si 2D grating are investigated. By changing the geometric parameter of the gratings, spectral tuning is achieved. The results show that under a 200 nm gap distance, Si gratings effectively suppresses low-frequency transmission while enhancing the spectrum above the cell bandgap. When the filling ratio is around 0.8 and the height of gratings is 300 nm, the spectral selectivity is enhanced more effectively. By reducing the filling ratio, low-frequency transmission is further suppressed, but it also affects the high-frequency transmission above band-gap. Height of gratings should be kept in a suitable range. If it's too thick, it exhibits high absorption of low-frequency radiation. And if it's too thin, it fails to tune the spectrum. Then the spectral heat flux becomes closer to that of bulk GaSb case. At the certain filling ratio, if period length gets shorter, the grating becomes more homogenous. For low-temperature NFTPV, a large portion of the thermal radiation is distributed below the bandgap, making it difficult to achieve high efficiency. By spectral tuning, the spectral heat flow below the bandgap is suppressed for photon recovery below the bandgap while selectively enhancing the photon transmission above the bandgap. This is important for reducing the system radiative losses and thus improving the system performance.

REFERENCES

- [1] T.Inoue et al, "Integrated Near-Field Thermophotovoltaic Device Overcoming Blackbody Limit", ACS Photonics, vol.8, 8, abr. 2021, doi: 10.1021/acsp Photonics.1c00698.
- [2] R.Mittapally et al, "Near-field thermophotovoltaics for efficient heat to electricity conversion at high power density", Nature Communications, vol.12, 1, abr. 2021, doi: 10.1038/s41467-021-24587-7.
- [3] Chen K, Santhanam P, Fan S, "Suppressing sub-bandgap phonon-polariton heat transfer in near-field thermophotovoltaic devices for waste heat recovery", Applied Physics Letters, vol.107, 9, abr. 2015, doi: 10.1063/1.4929949
- [4] Yu H, Liu D, Yang Z, Duan Y, "Simple Rectangular Gratings as a Near-Field "Anti-Reflection" Pattern for GaSb TPV Cells", Scientific Reports, vol.7, 1, Art. 1026, abr. 2017, doi: 10.1038/s41598-017-01197-2.
- [5] Chen K, Zhao B, Fan S, "MESH: A free electromagnetic solver for far-field and near-field radiative heat transfer for layered periodic structures", Computer Physics Communications, vol.231, abr.2018, doi: 10.1016/j.cpc.2018.04.032.
- [6] P.Bernardi M et al, "Impacts of propagating, frustrated and surface modes on radiative, electrical and thermal losses in nanoscale-gap thermophotovoltaic power generators", Scientific Reports, vol.5, 1, Art.11626, abr.2015,doi: 10.1038/srep11626.

Spectral Efficiency Optimized Near-field Thermophotovoltaics Using Germanium-based PV Cells

Nada Boubrik¹, Mathieu Giroux¹, Gavin Forcade², Abderraouf Boucherif³,
Sean Molesky⁴, Karin Hinzer⁵, Raphael St-Gelais^{1,2,*}

¹Department of Mechanical Engineering, University of Ottawa, Ottawa, Canada

²Department of Physics, University of Ottawa, Ottawa, Canada

³Department of Mechanical Engineering, University of Sherbrooke, Sherbrooke, Canada

⁴Department of Engineering Physics, Polytechnique Montreal, Montreal, Canada

⁵SUNLAB, School of Electrical Engineering and Computer Science, University of Ottawa, Ottawa, Canada

*rstgelai@uottawa.ca

Abstract — Most experiments and theoretical designs on near-field thermophotovoltaic (NFTPV) are based on III-V material platforms, which typically comprise toxic elements (e.g. arsenic) and have relatively high cost. In comparison, germanium (Ge) is relatively abundant and has lower cost and toxicity. This work investigates the viability of Ge-based materials for NFTPV. We first develop two permittivity models for infrared absorption in germanium: an experimental interpolation model and a Drude model. We then evaluate spectral efficiencies of a Ge PV cell illuminated by a radiator at 1200 K temperature and 0.1 microns distance. We find that the Drude model is adequate for modeling free carrier absorption only in n-type Ge. We also find that germanium NFTPV cells must be impractically thick to achieve high spectral efficiencies. For n-type Ge, a minimum thickness of 80 microns is needed to achieve 25% spectral efficiency. For p-type Ge, a thickness between 30 to 70 microns is required for achieving 19% spectral efficiency. This necessity for a thick layer stems from the indirect bandgap of Ge, resulting in low absorption of photons with near-bandgap energies. Thus, our work shows that pure germanium-based PV cells are not well suited for NFTPV. Alloying Ge with other materials (e.g., Sn) to obtain a direct bandgap is a promising direction to correct this limitation.

Near-Field Thermophotovoltaic (NFTPV) devices are promising for directly converting waste heat to electrical energy [1]. Recent experiments and designs [2] proved the potential of NFTPV for waste heat recycling by demonstrating high efficiency energy conversion, up to $\sim 6.8\%$ experimentally using an uncooled cell [1]. However, they typically rely on toxic III-V material platforms comprising, for example, arsenic.

To address these limitations, we investigate NFTPV using lower cost and lower toxicity germanium-based PV cells. In this specific work, we first investigate the potential of using solely Ge as the PV material, with a longer-term objective of incorporating tin (Sn) to create direct-bandgap PV cells suitable for NFTPV [3].

We model radiation transport between a silicon radiator and a germanium PV cell using a custom-built fluctuational electrodynamics solver [4],[5] that conceptualizes the devices as laterally infinite layered structures (see Fig. 1), with the radiator and gold layers extending semi-infinitely up and down in Fig. 1. We assume that the cell maintains a constant uniform

temperature of 300 K. The gold back surface reflector (BSF) (see Fig. 1) is incorporated to recycle sub-bandgap photons and improve spectral efficiency. Doping is considered uniform in the germanium layer, such that we can identify which of p-type or n-type germanium yields the highest spectral efficiency. Doping distribution can eventually be refined later on to consider base and emitter layers.

We calculate the doping-dependent interband permittivity of germanium ϵ_{IB} using interpolations on collected experimental data reported in [6]. Conversely, we model the free carrier contribution to germanium permittivity using two different approaches. The first approach uses a Drude model, for which the electron and hole doping-dependent mobilities are calculated using an empirical model from [7], and the fitting parameters for Ge are taken from [8]. The hole effective mass is calculated using a density of states model and the electron effective mass is taken from [8]. However, the Drude model was found to inadequately predict the free carrier contribution, especially for p-type Ge [9]. Therefore, we use a second approach [9] based on a mix of measurements and theoretical models when simulating p-type germanium. To compute the permittivity of the doped silicon radiator (see Fig. 1), we use the model from [10], which accounts for doping as well as thermally excited free carriers.

Fig. 1 Simulated Ge PV cell structure. A heavily doped silicon radiator in close proximity with a Ge PV cell emits radiation absorbed by the cell. A back surface reflector (BSR) is incorporated in the design to reflect unabsorbed sub-bandgap photons back to the radiator.

To produce our simulation results, we compute the useful power (P_{useful}) and spectral efficiency ($\eta_{spectral}$) under a radiator temperature of 1200 K (used for a comparable bandgap in [1]) and a vacuum gap of 0.1 microns. The useful power (P_{useful}) is defined as the portion of absorbed thermal energy that is convertible into electricity [11], and is given by:

$$P_{useful} = \int_{E_g}^{\infty} \frac{Q(E)E_g}{E} dE, \quad (1)$$

where E_g is the bandgap energy (0.66 eV for Ge) and $Q(E)$ is the calculated net radiation intensity spectrum (in units of $\text{Wm}^{-2}\text{eV}^{-1}$) as a function of photon energy E . In turn, the spectral efficiency $\eta_{spectral}$ quantifies the ratio of this useful radiated power (P_{useful}) to the total radiated heat transfer between the radiator and the PV cell (Q_{tot}) [11].

$$\eta_{spectral} = \frac{P_{useful}}{Q_{tot}} \quad (2)$$

Fig. 2 Spectral efficiency as a function of germanium thickness for various n-type (a) and p-type (b) doping concentrations, for a radiator temperature of 1200 K and a vacuum gap of 0.1 microns.

Our results suggest that a relatively thick layer, especially for n-type doped Ge, is required to achieve high spectral efficiencies (see Fig. 2). This is attributed to the indirect bandgap of Ge, which strongly limits its absorption near the bandgap compared to direct-bandgap III-V cells. Such a thick layer is impractical and would cause an unacceptable rate of recombination during charge transport [3]. We also find that a low doping concentration ($\sim 10^{17} \text{ cm}^{-3}$ or lower) is required to achieve high spectral efficiencies for both doping types. Low doping concentrations reduce free carrier absorption and therefore increase spectral efficiency. Our results finally suggest that a thinner layer is possible for p-type Ge due its higher interband absorption compared to n-type Ge [6],[9]. However, we find that p-type Ge exhibits lower spectral efficiencies overall, due to higher free carrier absorption [9].

In conclusion, our work shows that pure germanium-based PV cells are not suitable for NFTPV. In future work, it will be useful to investigate the potential of achieving high overall conversion efficiencies by incorporating tin (Sn) into Ge (GeSn) [3]. This will allow the transition to a direct bandgap that can also be tuned to lower energy values better suited for lower radiator temperatures. Furthermore, GeSn material platforms can potentially be transfer printed, as previously shown for germanium [12], and would therefore be naturally well suited for incorporating a back surface reflector.

- [1] Mittapally, R., Lee, B., Zhu, L., Reihani, A., Lim, J. W., Fan, D., Forrest, S. R., Reddy, P., & Meyhofer, E. (2021). *Nature Communications*, 12(1), 4364.
- [2] Forcade, G. P., Valdivia, C. E., Molesky, S., Lu, S., Rodriguez, A. W., Krich, J. J., St-Gelais, R., & Hinzer, K. (2022). *Applied Physics Letters*, 121(19), 193903.
- [3] Daligou, G., Soref, R., Attiaoui, A., Hossain, J., Atalla, M. R. M., Vecchio, P. D., & Moutanabbir, O. (2023). *IEEE Journal of Photovoltaics*, 13(5), 728–735.
- [4] Reid, M. T. H., Rodriguez, A. W., & Johnson, S. G. (2013). *Proceedings of the IEEE*, 101(2), 531–545.
- [5] S. Molesky and S. Lu, “heatSlabs” (2020). <https://Github.Com/SeanMolesky/HeatSlabs>
- [6] Muneshue, S., & Arai, T. (1964). *Japanese Journal of Applied Physics*, 3(5), 269.
- [7] Masetti, G., Severi, M., & Solmi, S. (1983). *IEEE Transactions on Electron Devices*, 30(7), 764–769.
- [8] Hellings, G., Eneman, G., Krom, R., De Jaeger, B., Mitard, J., De Keersgieter, A., Hoffmann, T., Meuris, M., & De Meyer, K. (2010). *IEEE Transactions on Electron Devices*, 57(10), 2539–2546.
- [9] Nedeljkovic, M., Soref, R., & Mashanovich, G. Z. (2015). *IEEE Photonics Journal*, 7(3), 1–14.
- [10] Fu, C. J., & Zhang, Z. M. (2006). *International Journal of Heat and Mass Transfer*, 49(9–10), 1703–1718.
- [11] St-Gelais, R., Bhatt, G. R., Zhu, L., Fan, S., & Lipson, M. (2017). *ACS Nano*, 11(3), 3001–3009.
- [12] Paupy, N., Oulad Elhmaid, Z., Chapotot, A., Hanuš, T., Arias-Zapata, J., Ilahi, B., Heintz, A., Pougoué Mbeunmi, A. B., Arvinte, R., Aziziyan, M. R., Daniel, V., Hamon, G., Chrétien, J., Zouaghi, F., Ayari, A., Mouchel, L., Henriques, J., Demoulin, L., Diallo, T. M., ... Boucherif, A. (2023). *Nanoscale Advances*, 5(18), 4696–4702.

Radiative Transfer Mechanism and Performance Analysis of Near-Field Thermophotovoltaic System with Plasmonic Emitter

Song Li¹, Junming Zhao^{1,2,*}

¹ School of Energy Science and Engineering, Harbin Institute of Technology, Harbin 150001, China

² Key Laboratory of Aerospace Thermophysics, Ministry of Industry and Information Technology of China

Abstract — Performance of thermophotovoltaic (TPV) can be improved by incorporating near-field radiative heat transfer (NFRHT) and plasmonic emitter. However, the underlying mechanism of NFRHT within the system, including the possible coupling between total reflection (TR) and surface plasmon polaritons (SPPs), still requires further clarification. We derive the dispersion relation for TR-SPPs modes, showing the mode decouple as distance decreases, with SPPs modes taking over. When TR-SPPs are dominant in NFRHT, they enhance spectral heat flux across the bandgap, while SPPs enhance it significantly above the bandgap. Power density improves with decreasing distance, and efficiency sees an initial decrement from TR-SPPs enhancement, followed by an increment due to SPPs enhancement. This work can provide guidance for the design of NF-TPV.

I. INTRODUCTION

Near-field thermophotovoltaic (NF-TPV) system with plasmonic emitter has been conducted theoretical studies [1], [2]. In such system, there may be a coupling effect between total reflection (TR) at the vacuum-cell interface and surface plasmon polaritons (SPPs) excited at the vacuum-emitter interface. This work will research NFRHT mechanism and performance of NF-TPV system with plasmonic emitter. At first, we will verify the existence of TR-SPPs modes under different distance. Following that, heat transfer mechanism at different distance will be investigated. Finally, the relationship between the performance of NF-TPV system and NFRHT mechanism will be analyzed.

II. MODEL AND METHOD

NF-TPV system consists of a GZO emitter (1800 K) a 500 μm thickness GaSb cell (300 K), and a heat sink. NF-RHT between the GZO emitter and GaSb cell mediates by evanescent waves as shown in Fig. 1. The electromagnetic modes include the frustrated modes, SPPs modes, and the possibly existing TR-SPPs modes.

Fig. 1 Schematic diagram of NFRHT in NF-TPV system with GZO emitter and GaSb cell.

A. NFRHT between GZO emitter and GaSb cell

To calculate the NFRHT at various distances, fluctuational electrodynamics is employed as [3] :

$$q_{\text{rad}} = \frac{1}{4\pi^2} \int_0^\infty [\Theta(T_{\text{GZO}}, \omega) - \Theta(T_{\text{GaSb}}, \omega)] \int_0^\infty \beta \xi(\omega, \beta) d\beta d\omega \quad (1)$$

where Θ is the mean energy of a Planck oscillator, \hbar is the reduced Planck constant, ω is the angular frequency, β is the component of wavevector parallel to the interface. $\xi(\omega, \beta)$ is the energy transmission coefficient.

B. Evaluation of NF-TPV performance

The performance analysis method for NF-TPV systems involves using an ideal pn junction model. The output power P of the TPV cell can be calculated from [4]:

$$P_{\text{cell}} = I_{\text{ph}} V_{\text{oc}} \left[1 - \frac{1}{\ln(I_{\text{ph}}/I_o)} \right] \left\{ 1 - \frac{\ln[\ln(I_{\text{ph}}/I_o)]}{\ln(I_{\text{ph}}/I_o)} \right\}. \quad (2)$$

In which, V_{oc} is the open-circuit voltage calculated from $V_{\text{oc}} = k_{\text{B}}T/e \times \ln(I_{\text{ph}}/I_o)$. According to Ref. [4], the saturation current of GaSb is $6 \times 10^{-2} \text{ A/m}^2$. I_{ph} is the photogeneration current, calculated from:

$$I_{\text{ph}} = e \int_{\omega_g}^\infty \eta_q(\omega) \frac{q_\omega(T_1, T_2, \omega)}{\hbar\omega} d\omega. \quad (3)$$

In Eq.(3), q_ω is the spectral heat flux between GZO and GaSb cell, ω_g is the frequency equaling to E_g/\hbar , $\eta_q(\omega)$ is the internal quantum efficiency of GaSb cell, which derives from Ref. [5]. The efficiency of a NF-TPV system is calculated using $\eta = P_{\text{cell}}/q_{\text{rad}} \times 100\%$

C. The dispersion relation of TR-SPPs modes

Deriving the dispersion relation entails formulating the wave equation from Maxwell's equation, applying boundary condition, and employing hypothetical solutions to determine the wavevector-frequency relationship of the TR-SPPs modes. The analytical expression of TR-SPPs modes dispersion relation is derived for the first time as

$$e^{-4ak_1} = \frac{k_1/\varepsilon_1 + k_2/\varepsilon_2}{k_1/\varepsilon_1 - k_2/\varepsilon_2} \cdot \frac{ie^{(1+i)ak_3} k_1/\varepsilon_1 + k_3/\varepsilon_3}{ie^{(1+i)ak_3} k_1/\varepsilon_1 - k_3/\varepsilon_3}. \quad (4)$$

In Eq.(4), k_1 , k_2 , and k_3 are the z component of the wavevector in the vacuum (material I), emitter (material II), and the TPV cell (material III), respectively, given as $k_1 = \sqrt{\beta^2 - \varepsilon_1 k_0^2}$, $k_2 = \sqrt{k_0^2 - \varepsilon_2 \beta^2}$, $k_3 = \sqrt{\beta^2 - \varepsilon_3 k_0^2}$.

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Firstly, NFRHT mechanism is analyzed through the energy transmission coefficient. The existence of the TR-SPPs modes is determined by comparing the dispersion relation with the energy transmission coefficient contour of TM wave. The energy transmission coefficient contour at different distance is shown in Fig. 2. According to Fig. 2(c) and (d), the dispersion relation of the TR-SPPs modes coincide with the region where the photon tunneling probability is 1, verifying TR-SPPs modes. Furthermore, due to the wavevector of the TR-SPPs modes being much higher than that of other modes, this indicates that TR-SPPs modes play a dominant role in NFRHT.

Fig. 2. Energy transmission coefficient of TM wave contour at different distance. The wavevector normalized by β_0 , $\beta_0 = \omega_{\text{spp,GZO}}/c$.

Additionally, the existence of the TR-SPPs modes is related to the distance. According to Fig. 2, as d decreases, the wavevector of the TR-SPPs modes increases, eventually leading to the modes decoupling. Based on Fig. 2(a) and (b), NFRHT is mainly mediated by SPPs modes at 5 nm and 10 nm. The decoupling of the TR-SPPs modes occurs because GaSb limit the wavevector of TR. Moreover, as d decreases, not only TR-SPPs modes gradually decouple, but SPPs modes emerges.

To further study NFRHT characteristics at different distances, it is necessary to obtain the spectral radiative heat flux. Fig. 3(a) shows the variation of q_ω at different d . When TR-SPPs dominate, q_ω changes smoothly and is enhanced both above and below the bandgap as d decreases. At 5nm and 10nm, where SPPs dominate, q_ω exhibits quasi-monochromaticity, and q_ω above the bandgap is significantly enhanced.

Based on the q_ω and the performance evaluation method, the performance of NF-TPV can be obtained as shown in Fig. 3(b).

It can be seen that P increases as d decreases because the decrease in distance can enhance NFRHT. On the other hand, η first decreases and then increases with the decrease of d , which is due to the fact that when TR-SPPs dominate, q_ω is enhanced both above and below the bandgap, which generally leads to a decrease in efficiency. When SPPs dominate NFRHT, q_ω above the bandgap is significantly enhanced.

Fig. 3. Example of readable plot using different colors and line styles for clarity.

IV. CONCLUSION

This work explored NFRHT mechanism in NF-TPV system with plasmonic emitter. We derive the dispersion relation of TR-SPPs modes and verify TR-SPPs modes related to the distance. As distance decreases, the TR-SPPs modes decouple, and SPPs modes dominate. Findings reveal that when TR-SPPs dominate, the TR-SPPs modes enhances spectral heat flux above and below the bandgap. When SPPs modes dominance leads to significant enhancement above the bandgap. The power density can be improved as the distance decreases. Efficiency initially decreases with decreasing distance due to TR-SPPs modes enhancement but increases due to SPPs modes enhancement.

REFERENCES

- [1] H. Yu, D. Liu, Z. Yang, and Y. Duan, "Simple Rectangular Gratings as a Near-Field 'Anti-Reflection' Pattern for GaSb TPV Cells," *Sci Rep*, vol. 7, no. 1, p. 1026, Dec. 2017, doi: 10.1038/s41598-017-01197-2.
- [2] B. Zhao, "High-performance near-field thermophotovoltaics for waste heat recovery," *Nano Energy*, vol. 41, pp. 344–350, 2017, doi: 10.1016/j.nanoen.2017.09.054.
- [3] K. Joulain, J.-P. Mulet, F. Marquier, R. Carminati, and J.-J. Greffet, "Surface electromagnetic waves thermally excited: Radiative heat transfer, coherence properties and Casimir forces revisited in the near field," *Surface Science Reports*, vol. 57, no. 3–4, pp. 59–112, 2005, doi: 10.1016/j.surfrep.2004.12.002.
- [4] M. Laroche, R. Carminati, and J.-J. Greffet, "Near-field thermophotovoltaic energy conversion," *Journal of Applied Physics*, vol. 100, no. 6, Sep. 2006, doi: 10.1063/1.2234560.
- [5] O. V. Sulima and A. W. Bett, "Fabrication and simulation of GaSb thermophotovoltaic cells," *Solar Energy Materials and Solar Cells*, vol. 66, no. 1–4, pp. 533–540, Feb. 2001, doi: 10.1016/S0927-0248(00)00235-X.

Photon-Enhanced Thermionic Emission Devices with Perovskite Photovoltaic Anodes for Conversion of Concentrated Sunlight

A. Bellucci¹, L. Vesce², M. Mastellone¹, Y. Raoui², A. Di Carlo^{1,2}, and D. M. Trucchi¹

¹CNR-ISM, Consiglio Nazionale delle Ricerche – Istituto di Struttura della Materia, Italy.

²C.H.O.S.E. (Centre for Hybrid and Organic Solar Energy), Department of Electronic Engineering, Università di Roma Tor Vergata, Italy.

Abstract— Perovskite photovoltaic cells represent the emerging technology in solar energy conversion. For the first time, perovskite photovoltaic structures have been considered as anodes in photon-enhanced thermionic device to collect thermionic electrons emitted by high-temperature silicon/diamond cathodes as well as to convert the radiative emission. Experiments carried out using the concentrated solar radiation shows promising results for the overall device performance and, above all, stability in temperature of the perovskite photovoltaic cells up to 130 °C. These preliminary observations represent the basis for the future exploitation of the concept to large-area low production cost materials.

I. INTRODUCTION

The concept of hybrid thermionic-photovoltaic (TIPV) converters has been experimentally proven in the recent past, by using both GaAs and InGaAs photovoltaic (PV) anodes, as well as both 2-terminals (2-T) [1, 2] and 3-terminals (3-T) [3] configuration. The use of PV anodes allows the absorption and conversion of photons and electrons emitted by the hot-temperature thermionic cathode. Thus, the PV anode acts as a thermophotovoltaic cell, but additionally it must also guarantee the collection of the electrons thermionically emitted. To do it, a transparent, ultra-thin low work function coating needs to be applied on the surface of the PV anode. The choice of the PV active material depends essentially on the radiative emission spectrum of the thermionic cathode, i.e., on the cathode operating temperature. The lower the temperature, the lower the PV material's bandgap. Among the possible materials, perovskites are good candidates thanks to the bandgap tunability by acting on the composition chemistry and thanks to the flexibility of large-area deposition on different substrates. However, the thermal stability of perovskites PV cells under operations at temperatures higher than room temperature could represent an issue and it needs to be verified. In this work, we present the results of hybrid between photon-enhanced thermionic emission (PETE) cathode and PV anodes, where silicon/diamond heterostructures act as PETE cathodes and a perovskite PV structures as anodes. PETE is a thermionic-based concept, in which a semiconductor is used as a sunlight-absorbing cathode to emit both photo-excited electrons and the thermal electron population for the solar-to-electrical conversion. This kind of mechanism allows reducing

the operating temperatures with the respect to conventional thermionic systems.

II. EXPERIMENTAL DETAILS

Experiments have been carried out in the Synlight facility of DLR (Germany), in the framework of the infrastructural project SFERA III. A customized high-vacuum chamber was mounted on the focal plane to receive the concentrated sunlight up to a radiation flux of 70 W/cm². However, the testing was performed to maintain the cathode at the maximum temperature of 850 °C. The thermionic cathode is a silicon-diamond heterostructure, formed by depositing 80 nm of diamond through chemical vapour deposition on (111) p-doped silicon wafers. Both intrinsic and N-doped diamond layers were developed. The anode for the 2-T TIPV configuration is a perovskite (PSK) solar cell, developed according to the following structure: ITO/Cu:NiO_x/PSK 1.55 eV/C₆₀/Bathocuproine. An inverted structure based on the same layers have been fabricated for the 3-T configuration, with an additional Cu contact for the PV cell. Sc₂O₃ and BaF₂ coatings were deposited by electron-beam evaporation for reducing the work function of the PVSK cells. Among the two electrodes, 35 μm-thick silica spacers were mounted to maintain the two electrodes thermally and electrically insulated. The chamber was evacuated down to ~ 1 × 10⁻⁷ mbar at room temperature by an active pumping system. Electrical signals were collected by using Ta wires in the hottest zone connected to Kapton-coated copper wires, specifically designed for vacuum systems. Two electrometers (Keithley 2470) were used for performing current-to-voltage measurements.

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

A. PSK PV cell behavior in temperature: measurements with 3-T configuration

To evaluate the operations of the PV anode, the 3-T configuration was employed to characterize independently the two converters. Fig. 1 shows the short-circuit current (I_{sc}) as a function of the cathode temperature (T_C), whereas Fig. 2 correlates the anode temperature (T_A) to the cathode one. It is

possible to notice that the I_{sc} starts to increase at $T_C = 400$ °C (despite only a tiny fraction of emitted spectral energy density was collectable at such a temperature), whereas the current drastically goes down at $T_C = 560$ °C which corresponds to $T_A = 130$ °C. This upper limit represents the maximum temperature before the degradation of the cell junction occurs. Investigations of the morphological, physical, and chemical properties of the cell before and after the testing are ongoing.

Fig. 1. I_{sc} of the PVSK PV anode as a function of T_C .

Fig. 2. PV anode temperature as a function of T_C .

B. Comparison of the performance: PVSK PV cell vs PVSK active material in 2-T configuration

With the aim to understand if the PV effect contributes to increase the voltage output of the PETE-PV converter, as already validated in TIPV devices in the previous works, we compare current-to-voltage (I-V) characteristics of the PSK PV cell (with and without a low work function coating, e.g., a Sc_2O_3 ultra-thin film) and of the PSK active material. We find that the open-circuit voltage (V_{oc}) increases from 0.1 V for the PSK to 0.45 V for the PV cell, up to 1.15 V when a low-work-function functionalized coating is deposited on the top of the cell. This evolution is expected and confirms the voltage boost found for the III-V structure. Notably, a $V_{oc} = 0.4$ V was preliminarily measured for the PSK cell under 1-sun illumination. In addition, the surface engineering with scandium oxide was demonstrated to be useful for reducing the PSK work function (of about 0.7 eV). Finally, we can state that

the cathode work function (expected to be ~ 3.9 eV for the intrinsic silicon/diamond structure used in the shown experiments) results lower than the PSK material and an effort to invert this condition is requested.

Fig. 3. I-V curves of different anodes (PSK, PSK PV cell and PSK PV cell with 2.5 nm of Sc_2O_3 on the top) using the same silicon/diamond structure for the cathode.

IV. CONCLUSIONS

For the first time, a PETE-PV structure was used to convert the concentrated solar energy. It was demonstrated that PSK solar cells can act as anodes, even if they are limited by the operating temperatures of the device. We found a maximum limitation for the anode temperature of 130 °C. Therefore, a more efficient cooling system needs to be designed for this kind of converters. On the other hand, the surface engineering of the PSK cells was successful, with a significant reduction of the work function that, natively, is higher than that of the silicon/diamond cathodes. On-going supplementary and complementary analyses are being performed and will be reported in the presentation. A request for reducing the PSK bandgap must be considered for the effective implementation of these materials in hybrid PETE-PV converters.

REFERENCES

- [1] A. Bellucci *et al.*, "Photovoltaic Anodes for Enhanced Thermionic Energy Conversion," *ACS Energy Letters*, vol. 5, no. 5, pp. 1364-1370, 2020, doi: 10.1021/acscenergylett.0c00022.
- [2] A. Bellucci, P. G. Linares, J. Villa, A. Martí, A. Datas, and D. M. Trucchi, "Hybrid thermionic-photovoltaic converter with an $\text{In}_{0.53}\text{Ga}_{0.47}\text{As}$ anode," *Solar Energy Materials and Solar Cells*, vol. 238, 2022, doi: 10.1016/j.solmat.2022.111588.
- [3] A. Bellucci, P. García-Linares, A. Martí, D. M. Trucchi, and A. Datas, "A Three-Terminal Hybrid Thermionic-Photovoltaic Energy Converter," *Advanced Energy Materials*, vol. 12, no. 20, 2022, doi: 10.1002/aenm.202200357.

Designing a near-field thermophotonic device in the planar configuration for energy conversion

Wissal Sghaier*¹, Mathieu Thomas¹, Kyriaki Kontou¹, Luc M. van der Krabben², Natasha Gruginskie², John J. Schermer², Ivan Radevici³, Jani Oksanen³, and Pierre-Olivier Chapuis¹

¹*Univ Lyon, CNRS, INSA-Lyon, Université Claude Bernard Lyon 1, CETHIL UMR5008, F-69621, Villeurbanne, France*

²*Radboud University Institute for Molecules and Materials, Applied Materials Science, Nijmegen, Netherlands*

³*Engineered Nanosystems Group, Aalto University, Finland*

*wissal.sghaier@insa-lyon.fr

Background

Thermophotovoltaics (TPV) and thermophotonics (TPX) [1] are promising approaches for energy harvesting by the photovoltaic conversion of light and heat. TPV devices, while achieving efficiencies of up to 40% for single junctions [2], are constrained by Planck's law, limiting their effectiveness in delivering high power compared to other devices like thermoelectric ones. Near-field thermal radiation, observed when objects are brought within a few micrometers in the 300-1000 K range, has proved to be a promising solution to exceed the bound imposed by Planck's law through intensified radiative heat exchange driven by evanescent waves [3]. In addition, TPX uses heated light-emitting diodes (LEDs) as active emitter, exploiting the strong intensity of electroluminescence and enabling spectral control to tune the emission profile. Notably, TPX offers the advantage of operating at moderate emitter temperatures, enhancing its interest for energy harvesting. Combining near field and electroluminescence, near-field thermophotonics (NF-TPX) [4] extends the abovementioned concepts, allowing enhanced energy conversion through both electrical control and wave tunneling, offering prospects for even more efficient energy harvesting systems. To date, only limited experimental proof of TPX has been reported in spite of its interest for both energy and for refrigeration [5].

Methods & Results

Building upon previous results in near-field thermophotovoltaics with the sphere-plane geometry-based setup [6], we introduce an experimental setup tailored to investigate TPX in a planar geometry down to the near-field distance regime. This requires addressing challenges associated with planar surfaces, including issues related to parallelism, bowing, and roughness. The experiment is made of two facing flat elements independently connected electrically in order to perform IV characterizations on each side. The hot side is heated by resistive thermometry up to 600°C while the second side is maintained close to room temperature and able to be aligned both linearly and rotationally to the hot side by means of piezoelectric actuators. The heat flux flowing to the ambient heat sink is monitored at the same time, since heating is detrimental to heat harvesting. We report on the initial performances of the setup. As a key element of the emitter, the LED component must withstand the hot temperatures considered. As a consequence, characterization of pin junctions used in the LEDs across temperature variations is essential. To do so, we have therefore conducted I-V characteristics at high temperatures as well as studies with a microscope-based Fourier transform infrared and visible spectrometer in order to analyze emission spectra prior to the integration step.

We acknowledge the support of EU H2020 projects FET-PROACT-2019 951976 TPX-Power and FETOpen-2018 964698 OPTAGON.

References

- [1] N. P. Harder and M. A. Green, “Thermophotonics”, *Semiconductor Science and Technology*, 18, 5, S270, (2003), doi: 10.1088/0268-1242/18/5/319
- [2] A. LaPotin et al., “Thermophotovoltaic efficiency of 40%”, *Nature*, 604, 7905, (2022), doi: 10.1038/s41586-022-04473-y.
- [3] C. Lucchesi et al., “Radiative heat transfer at the nanoscale: Experimental trends and challenges”, *Nanoscale Horizons*, 201-208, (2021), doi:10.1039/d0nh00609b
- [4] J. Legendre and P.-O. Chapuis, “GaAs-based near-field thermophotonic devices: Approaching the idealized case with one-dimensional PN junctions”. *Solar Energy Materials and Solar Cells*, 238, 111594, (2022), doi:10.1016/j.solmat.2022.111594
- [5] T. Sadi et al., “J. Prospects and requirements for thermophotonic waste heat energy harvesting”. *Solar Energy Materials and Solar Cells*, 239, 111635, (2022), doi:10.1016/j.solmat.2022.111635
- [6] C. Lucchesi et al. “Near-Field Thermophotovoltaic Conversion with High Electrical Power Density and Cell Efficiency above 14%”. *Nano Letters*, 21, 4524–4529, (2021), doi:10.1021/acs.nanolett.0c04847

A radiative thermal device for refrigeration: the near-field thermophonic cooler

T. Châtelet^{a*}, J. Legendre^a, P.-O. Chapuis^a and O. Merchiers^a

CNRS – INSA Lyon – Université Lyon 1

Abstract — TPX devices extend the concept of TPV by replacing the hot body by an active light-emitting diode (LED). A TPX near-field refrigerator is the focus of the present work, which can be seen as another type of radiative thermal device complementary to TPV/TPX radiative engines. Single LEDs have, however, low cooling power and a low coefficient of performance (COP). Near-field TPX devices allow in theory to improve both aspects. As for any thermal engine, a trade-off between cooling power and COP is highlighted. A key issue of TPX refrigerators is that the warmer PV cell also radiates thermally towards the LED, counteracting the cooling power of the LED. The issue is particularly significant when the two components are in the near field. By means of accurate nanoscale radiative computation (fluctuational electrodynamics), we investigate the potential performances of near-field TPX refrigerators made of GaAs-based materials and the trade-off between cooling power and COP as a function of temperature and vacuum gap distance. In a first step, we set targets in terms of quantum efficiency within a detailed-balance approach. In a second step, 1D drift-diffusion models are implemented in order to consider realistic multilayer-based heterostructures on both sides of the vacuum gap. Optimized thicknesses of the layers of the pin junctions are obtained and conditions for large cooling power are evidenced.

I. EXTENDED ABSTRACT

Thermophotovoltaic (TPV) and/or thermophotonic (TPX) [1] devices are used to convert the radiated energy from a hot source into electric power by means of a photovoltaic converter. TPX devices extend the concept of TPV by replacing the passive hot body by an active light-emitting diode (LED), which is expected to improve the harvested power. The working principle is based on the fact that LEDs emit larger radiative power than the supplied electrical power under particular conditions, by extracting heat from the crystalline lattice. This results also in cooling of the LED and its surroundings. This effect is called electroluminescent cooling [2-3] and can be used either to increase power harvesting from the PV cell when the emitter is hot – as discussed above - or to design a radiation-based cooling device when the LED is at a temperature below ambient [3]. To increase the cooling power of the TPX device, near-field coupling can be used, which appears when the distance in-between the LED and PV cell is smaller than the

wavelength dominating the radiative exchange. Such effect increases the radiative exchange within the device by means of evanescent waves [4]. A TPX near-field refrigerator is the focus of the present work, which can be seen as another type of radiative thermal device complementary to TPV/TPX radiative engines.

Single LEDs have, however, low cooling power and a low coefficient of performance (COP). Near-field TPX devices allow in theory to improve both aspects. As for any thermal engine, a trade-off between cooling power and COP is highlighted. A key issue of TPX refrigerators is that the warmer PV cell also radiates thermally towards the LED, counteracting the cooling power of the LED. The issue is particularly significant when the two components are in the near field. By means of accurate nanoscale radiative computation (fluctuational electrodynamics), we investigate the potential performances of near-field TPX refrigerators made of GaAs-based materials and the trade-off between cooling power and COP as a function of temperature and vacuum gap distance. In a first step, we set the targets in terms of quantum efficiency within a detailed-balance approach. In a second step, 1D drift-diffusion models are implemented in order to consider realistic multilayer-based heterostructures on both sides of the vacuum gap. Optimized thicknesses of the layers of the pin junctions are obtained and conditions for large cooling power are evidenced.

REFERENCES

- [1] N.-P. Harder and M.A Green, *Semiconductor Science and Technology* **18** S270 (2003)
- [2] P. Santhanam et al., *Physical Review Letters* **108**, 097403 (2012)
- [3] T. Sadi et al., *Nature Photonics* **14**, 205 (2020)
- [4] J. Legendre and P.-O. Chapuis, *Solar Energy Materials and Solar Cells* **238**, 111594 (2021)

We acknowledge funding of project OPTAGON EU project (call H2020-FETOPEN-2018-2019-2020-01, GA 964698).

^a Centre d'énergétique et de thermique de Lyon, Campus LyonTech La Doua 69621 Villeurbanne, France

An Experimental Study of the Near-Field Behaviour of PIN Junctions

Mathieu Thomas^{*1}, Thomas Châtelet¹, Benoît Behaghel², Ivan Radevici², Luc van der Krabben³, Ahmad Shahahmadi², John J. Schermer³, Jani Oksanen² and Pierre-Olivier Chapuis¹

¹Univ Lyon, CNRS, INSA-Lyon, Université Claude Bernard Lyon 1, CETHIL UMR5008, F-69621, Villeurbanne, France

²Engineered Nanosystems Group, Aalto University, Finland

³Department of Applied Materials Science, Radboud University, The Netherlands

*mathieu.thomas@insa-lyon.fr

Background

An upper bound for thermophotovoltaic devices is given by the blackbody limit imposed by Planck's law in far field. At a given temperature, their power output stays therefore moderate in comparison to other types of harvesting devices such as thermoelectrics. It is therefore key to increase the output power density of low or medium-grade TPV devices. When the distance between objects decreases below the characteristic wavelength of thermal radiation (few micrometers in the 300-1000 K range), the radiative heat exchange is increased beyond the blackbody limit. This increase, explained by the additional contribution of evanescent waves to the radiative transfer, is now well documented theoretically and experimentally and is promising for thermal-energy harvesting, including thermophotovoltaics when the emitter is brought closer to the cell [1-4]. A further improvement of such a device is to replace the hot passive emitter by a heated light-emitting diode (LED), which allows controlling electrically the intensity of the above-bandgap energy spectrum; such device is termed thermophotonic (TPX) [5-9]. Note that an LED is made of a pin junction, similarly to photovoltaic cells considered for TPV and TPX. Both for TPV and TPX, it is therefore desirable to understand the near-field behaviour of the electromagnetic fields close to the pin junctions [10-11].

Methods & Results

III-V semiconductors, in particular GaAs-based pin junctions, are targeted for high efficiency. For TPX, the capability to achieve high internal quantum efficiency is also an essential criterion for the proper functioning of the device. The present work reports on near-field electroluminescence absorption measurements involving a pin GaAs light-emitting diode and micrometric spherical sensor. The sensor, a 40 μm -diameter graphite sphere glued on a Scanning Thermal Microscopy cantilever, has been selected as it is a resistive thermometer that allows us measuring subtle thermal and electrical changes in the probe. We use modulation of the LED emission to detect the absorbed power in the probe using a lock-in amplifier. The experiments consist in measuring the evolution of the probe voltage as a function of distance in the last 5 μm before contact with nanometric resolution. In particular, we discuss our recent efforts to address the distance determination in the sub-100 nm distance range, including optical contact determination and the evaluation of electrostatic interactions in this region. Electrical and electroluminescent coupling are observed depending on the applied biases. The results are compared with simplified simulations of electrical and electromagnetic phenomena above the LED. In general, the experimental results provides a better understanding of the near-field exchange between a pin junction and a passive body.

References

- [1] Lucchesi, C. et al. Near-Field Thermophotovoltaic Conversion with High Electrical Power Density and Cell Efficiency above 14%. *Nano Lett.* 21, 4524–4529 (2021).
- [2] Mittapally, R. et al. “Near-field thermophotovoltaics for efficient heat to electricity conversion at high power density”. *Nat Commun* 12, 4364 (2021).
- [3] Bhatt, G. R. et al. “Integrated near-field thermo-photovoltaics for heat recycling”. *Nat Commun* 11, 2545 (2020).
- [4] Inoue, T. et al. “Integrated Near-Field Thermophotovoltaic Device Overcoming Blackbody Limit”. *ACS Photonics* 8, 2466–2472 (2021).
- [5] Harder, N.-P. & Green, M. A. Thermophotonics. *Semicond. Sci. Technol.* 18, S270–S278 (2003).
- [6] Oksanen, J., Tulkki, J. “Thermophotonic heat pump—a theoretical model and numerical simulations”. *Journal of Applied Physics* 107,8 (2010).
- [7] Legendre, J. & Chapuis, P.-O. GaAs-based near-field thermophotonic devices: Approaching the idealized case with one-dimensional PN junctions. *Solar Energy Materials and Solar Cells* 238, 111594 (2022).
- [8] Zhao, B., Santhanam, P., Chen, K., Buddhiraju, S. & Fan, S. Near-Field Thermophotonic Systems for Low-Grade Waste-Heat Recovery. *Nano Lett.* 18, 5224–5230 (2018).
- [9] Sadi, T., Radevici, I., Behaghel, B. & Oksanen, J. Prospects and requirements for thermophotonic waste heat energy harvesting. *Solar Energy Materials and Solar Cells* 239, 111635 (2022).
- [10] Zhu, L., Fiorino, A., Thompson, D., Mittapally, R., Meyhofer, E., Reddy, P. Near-field photonic cooling through control of the chemical potential of photons. *Nature* 566, 239–244 (2019).
- [11] De Wilde, Y., Haidar, R. Optical cooling without lasers. *Nature*, 566, 186-187 (2019).

This work has received funding from projects EU H2020-EIC-FETPROACT-2019/GA951976 (TPX-Power) and H2020 FETOpen-2018-2019-01/GA964698 (OPTAGON).

Organizers

Golden Sponsors

Silver Sponsors

Bronze Sponsors

Collaborator

Organized in collaboration with the SUNSON project, funded by the European Union's Horizon Europe Research and Innovation Programme under Grant Agreement No. 101083827